

Air quality maps of EEA member and cooperating countries for 2023

PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, NO₂, NO_x and BaP spatial estimates and their uncertainties

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Data availability

The air quality maps presented in this report are available in the GeoTIFF format on the EEA geospatial data catalogue, see below.

PM₁₀ maps (annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means), 2023:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/177d85ca-1664-4357-ad5e-7e7d598c5774> (accessed 19 November 2025).

PM_{2.5} map (annual average), 2023:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/57807f24-25dc-4df3-9468-dcff8cee5468> (accessed 19 November 2025).

O₃ maps (93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35, SOMO10, AOT40 for vegetation, AOT40 for forests), 2023:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/0fd47f22-c899-4f76-979e-53386b67068e> (accessed 19 November 2025).

NO₂ map (annual average), 2023:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/317cf5a5-9909-46b2-bc17-0d40ff3138eb> (accessed 19 November 2025).

NO_x map (annual average), 2023:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a2c980b7-5632-4ff3-bf0c-b75e627339cd> (accessed 19 November 2025).

The entire time series of the maps for all pollutants:

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/82700fbd-2953-467b-be0a-78a520c3a7ef> (accessed 19 November 2025).

Summary

Air quality concentrations maps of the member and cooperating countries of the European Environmental Agency (EEA)⁽¹⁾ have been prepared for the year 2023. The maps are primarily based on air quality data as reported under the Ambient Air Quality Directives (EC, 2004, 2008). The mapping method ('Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping') follows a methodology developed earlier (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein); it combines the monitoring data with outputs from a chemical transport model and other supplementary data such as land cover and satellite data.

Population exposure

Regarding PM₁₀ (i.e. particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less), concentrations and population exposure remained above the European Union (EU) and World Health Organisation (WHO) standards in large parts of Europe in 2023. Approximately 7% of the considered European population was exposed to concentrations above the EU PM₁₀ annual limit value of 40 µg/m³ and 63% of the population was exposed to concentrations exceeding the WHO Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level of 15 µg/m³ in 2023. Furthermore, 16% of the population was estimated to live in areas where the 90.4 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily means was above the EU limit value of 50 µg/m³. When it comes to PM_{2.5}, approximately 0.2% of the considered European population (excluding Türkiye in this case of PM_{2.5}) was exposed to concentrations above the EU PM_{2.5} limit value of 25 µg/m³ and 2.4% above the EU PM_{2.5} indicative limit value of 20 µg/m³, respectively. Moreover, 96% of the population was exposed to concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 5 µg/m³. The countries with the highest values of annual averages PM_{2.5} are located in south-eastern Europe. The population-weighted concentration of the PM₁₀ indicators annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means for the considered European population is estimated to be 20.4 µg/m³ and 34.5 µg/m³, respectively, in 2023. The population-weighted concentration of the PM_{2.5} annual average for the considered European population (without Türkiye) is estimated to be 10.4 µg/m³ in 2023.

For ozone, it was estimated that 12% of the considered European population lived in areas where concentrations exceeded the ozone target value threshold (that is, the target value for just one year) based on 2023 data, and 10% based on the 3-year target value for 2021-2023. Countries with the highest values of the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means are situated in southern and central Europe. Additionally, 98% of the considered European population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the WHO AQG level of 60 µg/m³ (the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means). The population-weighted concentration of the O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means for the considered European population is estimated to be 108.1 µg/m³ in 2023.

Approximately 3% of the considered European population was exposed to NO₂ concentrations above the EU annual limit value of 40 µg/m³ in 2023. Except for Türkiye, the majority of population lived well below the limit value in 2023. However, about 67% of the considered European population including Türkiye was exposed to annual average concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³. The population-weighted concentration of the NO₂ annual average for the considered European population is estimated to be 15.5 µg/m³ in 2023.

Based on the experimental map of benzo(a)pyrene (BaP), it is estimated that 8.5% of the considered European population live in areas where BaP concentrations are above the threshold 1.0 ng/m³. The highest BaP concentrations are shown in Poland, north-eastern Czechia, west Balkan, eastern Po Valley

⁽¹⁾ The EEA member countries are the 27 Member States of the European Union (EU-27), plus Iceland, Lichtenstein, Norway, Switzerland, and Türkiye. The EEA cooperating countries are Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia. In addition, three microstates (Andorra, a country which voluntary reports air quality data, Monaco and San Marino) are also presented in this report.

in northern Italy and some populated locations in central and south-eastern Europe, Latvia and Finland. The population-weighted concentration of the BaP annual average for the considered European population (without Türkiye) is estimated to be about 0.4 ng/m³ in 2023.

Figure S.1 illustrates the population exposure to different air pollutants, for the whole considered European population (excluding Türkiye in the cases of PM_{2.5} and BaP).

Figure S.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of PM₁₀ (annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means), PM_{2.5} (annual average), O₃ (93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means), NO₂ (annual average) and BaP (annual average) in 2023

Accumulated risks

Out of the total population of 560 million in the mapped area (including Türkiye), 5% (30.1 million) people live in areas where two or three of the most frequently exceeded air quality standards (PM₁₀ daily limit value, O₃ target value and NO₂ annual limit value) as specified in EC (2008) are exceeded; 0.1% (0.5 million) people live in areas where all these three standards are exceeded. The worst situation in 2023 was observed in Cyprus, Greece, Türkiye, where less than 0.05%, 4% and 0.2% lived in areas where all three standards are exceeded, respectively.

Vegetation exposure

Based on 2023 data, ozone concentrations (AOT40 for vegetation) are above the EU target value threshold (the TV for just one year) for the protection of vegetation (EU, 2008) in about 12% of the agricultural areas and above the EU long-term objective in 91% of the agricultural areas. Ozone concentrations (AOT40 for forests) are above the critical level for the protection of forests in about 73% of the forested areas. Relating to 5-year mean 2019-2023, 16% of all European agricultural land including Türkiye has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the target value of 18 000 µg/m³·h. Considering the long-term objective of 6 000 µg/m³·h, the total European area (including Türkiye) in excess was 90%.

In 2023, POD₆ values for wheat above the highest CL (i.e. for protein yield) were observed across a large continuous area of Europe, covering western, central and south-western regions. For potatoes, POD₆ values exceeded the CL for tuber yield in large parts of western and central Europe. In contrast, exceedances for tomatoes were limited to a few coastal areas, consistent with previous years.

The CL of POD₁ for beech was exceeded in almost the entire European mapped area, with the exception of large areas of the Iberian Peninsula and Türkiye and many smaller areas throughout the mapped area. The CL of POD₁ for spruce was exceeded almost throughout the entire mapped European area, with the exception of large areas in northern Europe and a larger area in Romania.

In a limited number of cases, concentrations of NO_x are above the EU critical level. However, since most of these cases happen in urban areas, this is only relevant if there is vegetation in those areas.

Changes over time

Since 2005, maps for most of the pollutants have been prepared in an overall consistent way (although the mapping methodology has been subject to continuous improvement). This enables an analysis of changes in exposure over time. Apart from minor methodological changes, a major change was introduced for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} since the 2017 maps, taking into account air quality in urban traffic areas. For some pollutants, maps of several years are not available.

The evolution of the population-weighted concentrations (as a measure of population exposure), expressed as relative change from 2005, is shown in Figure S.2. For absolute numbers, see Chapter 7. It can be seen that the population-weighted concentrations of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂ show in 2023 the lowest values in the nineteen-year time series.

Figure S.2 Population-weighted concentration of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂ (annual mean), and ozone (SOMO35) in 2005-2023, and agricultural-weighted concentration of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation in 2005-2023, expressed as relative change (index, 2005 = 100)

The PM population-weighted concentrations show a steady decrease of about 0.6 µg/m³ per year for PM₁₀ annual average and 0.5 µg/m³ per year for PM_{2.5} annual average. For the ozone population-weighted concentration (expressed as SOMO35) no trend is observed for the period 2005-2023, due to the year-to-year variability. Also, no trend is observed for the agricultural-weighted concentration, in terms of AOT40 for vegetation. The NO₂ population-weighted concentration (in terms of annual average) shows a decrease of about 0.7 µg/m³ per year over the period 2005-2023.

1 Introduction

This report provides air quality concentration maps, population exposure and vegetation exposure estimates for 2023 for the area of the EEA member and cooperating countries. It builds on previous similar reports (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein). The analysis is based on interpolation of annual statistics of validated monitoring data from 2023, reported by the EEA member and cooperating countries (and the voluntary reporting microstate of Andorra) in 2023. Two other microstates (Monaco and San Marino) are also included in the assessment. Türkiye (including both European and Asian areas) is included in the mapping area for all pollutants except PM_{2.5} and BaP, due to the lack of enough PM_{2.5} and BaP reported data to the AQ e-reporting database from rural stations in Türkiye in 2023 (EEA, 2025a).

In this report 2023 results for particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5})⁽²⁾, ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) are presented, being the most relevant pollutants for annual updating due to their potential impacts on health and ecosystems. The analysis method applied is similar to that of previous years.

The mapping method is primarily based on air quality measurements. It combines monitoring data, chemical transport model results and other supplementary data (such as altitude and meteorology) using a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model ("residual kriging"). Separate mapping layers (rural, urban background and urban traffic, where relevant) are created separately and subsequently merged together into the final map. In order to reflect the three steps applied, the methodology is called *Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping (RIMM)*. It should be noted that this methodology does not allow for formal compliance checking with the legal standards as set by the ambient air quality directives (EC, 2004, 2008).

The maps of health-related indicators are created for the rural and urban (including suburban) background areas separately on a grid of 10 km resolution (for O₃) or 1 km resolution (for other pollutants, i.e. for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and BaP). Subsequently, the rural and urban background map layers are merged into one final combined air quality indicator map using a 1 km population density grid, following a weighting criterion applied per grid cell. In the mapping of health-related indicators of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and NO₂, together with the rural and urban background map layers, the urban traffic map layer is also constructed and incorporated into the final merged map using the road data. The map of BaP is labelled as experimental (as recommended in Horálek et al., 2022b) to indicate that it does not yet meet the same accuracy standards as the regularly produced maps of other pollutants.

The maps of O₃ and NO_x vegetation-related indicators are constructed at a grid resolution of 2 km and applicable for rural areas only. They are based on rural background measurements; in the case of O₃, they serve as input to the EEA's indicator AIR004 (EEA, 2025b). Among the O₃ vegetation-related maps, Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_Y) indicators are also presented. POD_Y is the O₃ flux through the stomata of leaves above a specific threshold Y accumulated during a specified time; it is calculated based on the methodology described in the Air Convention Mapping Manual (CLRTAP, 2024) according to Jarvis (1976) and Emberson et al. (2000a). Maps of the POD_Y for representative species of crops in Europe i.e. wheat, potato and tomato are presented, as well as the maps of the POD_Y for representative trees i.e. beech and spruce. The POD_Y annual maps are calculated based on hourly O₃ rural maps (created similarly to the annual O₃ maps), hourly meteorological data and the soil hydraulic properties data.

Next to the annual indicator maps, tables showing the population exposure to PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃ and NO₂, and the exposure of vegetation to ozone in terms of AOT40 indicators are presented. The tables of population exposure are prepared using the concentration and population density maps in 1 km grid

⁽²⁾ PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm and 2.5 µm or less, respectively.

resolution. For PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂, the population exposure in each grid cell is calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas, in order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic emissions. The tables of the vegetation exposure are prepared using the concentration maps in 2 km grid resolution and the Corine Land Cover 2018 dataset in 100 m resolution (EU, 2020).

Where applicable, the maps and population exposure estimates are presented both with respect to the EU standards to be already attained (EC, 2004; EC, 2008) and the new or revised EU standards to be attained by 1 January 2030 (EU, 2024). Where possible, exposure estimates are also assessed in relation to the WHO air quality guidance (AQG) levels (WHO, 2021a); in case of BaP in relation to the reference level (RL; WHO, 2021b). Table 1.1 presents a comparison of these different standards. This comparison is only possible for annual average concentrations, for which both current and revised limit values are defined, as well as the WHO AQG levels. For other air quality metrics based on short-term concentrations, such an assessment cannot be made, as the 2004 and 2008 Directives and the 2024 Directive differ in the allowed number of exceedances of the short-term limit values.

Table 1.1 Overview of the current (EC, 2004; EC, 2008) EU annual limit (LV) and target (TV) values, revised (EU, 2024) EU annual limit values to be attained by 1 January 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀) and WHO Air Quality Guidelines (AQG) levels and WHO reference level (RL) (WHO, 2021a; WHO, 2021b) for the pollutants assessed in this report

Pollutant	Averaging period	LV (µg/m ³)	LV ₂₀₃₀ (µg/m ³)	WHO AQG level (µg/m ³)
PM ₁₀	calendar year	40	20	15
PM _{2.5}	calendar year	25	10	5
NO ₂	calendar year	40	20	10
		TV (ng/m ³)	LV ₂₀₃₀ (ng/m ³)	WHO RL (ng/m ³)
BaP	calendar year	1	1.0	0.12

All tables present exposure results for individual countries, for the EU-27, for the whole mapped area and for five large European regions (i.e. Northern Europe, Western Europe, Central Europe, Southern Europe and South-eastern Europe, see Annex 1, Section A1.2, Map A1.1) ⁽³⁾.

Chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5 present the concentration maps and exposure estimates for particulate matter, O₃, NO₂ and NO_x, and BaP, respectively. Chapter 4 presents only the concentration map for NO_x; concentrations above the critical level for the protection of vegetation occur in very limited areas and, as such, it is considered not to provide relevant information from the European scale perspective. Chapter 6 provides information of accumulated risks, showing in which areas population is exposed to concentrations above the legal standards for more than one pollutant. Finally, Chapter 7 summarizes the trends in exposure estimates in the period 2005-2023.

Annex 1 describes briefly the different methodological aspects. Annex 2 documents the input data applied in the 2023 mapping and exposure analysis. Annex 3 presents the technical details of the maps and their uncertainty analysis including the cross-validation results. Annex 4 presents the concentration maps including concentration values measured at the stations, in order to provide more complete information of the air quality in 2023 across Europe.

⁽³⁾ Northern Europe: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden; Western Europe: Belgium, France north of 45°, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands; Central Europe: Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland; Southern Europe: Andorra, Cyprus, France (metropolitan) south of 45°, Greece, Italy, Malta, Monaco, Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira), San Marino, Spain (without Canarias); South-eastern Europe: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Türkiye.

2 Particulate matter

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets limit values for long-term and for short-term PM₁₀ concentrations and for long-term PM_{2.5} concentrations. In 2024, the revised Directive on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe (EU, 2024) entered into force, which new or revised air quality standards to be reached by 1 January 2030. The 2008 EU long-term annual average PM₁₀ limit value is set at 40 µg/m³, while the revised 2030 EU annual limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) of the same indicator is set at 20 µg/m³. The Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2021 (WHO, 2021a) is set to 15 µg/m³. The EU 2008 short-term limit value indicates that the daily average PM₁₀ concentration should not exceed 50 µg/m³ during more than 35 days per year. It corresponds to the 90.4 percentile of daily PM₁₀ concentrations in one year. This daily limit value is the most frequently exceeded 2008 air quality PM limit value in Europe. The new 2030 EU short-term limit value means that from 2030, the daily average PM₁₀ concentration of 45 µg/m³ should not be exceeded more than 18 times per year. The AQG levels recommended by the WHO in 2021 (WHO, 2021a) for short-term PM₁₀ concentrations indicates that the 99 percentile of the daily average PM₁₀ concentrations should not exceed 45 µg/m³ (99 percentile means 3-4 exceedance days per year).

The 2008 EU annual limit value (LV) for the annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations is set at 25 µg/m³. In EC (2008), there is also an indicative limit value (ILV) of 20 µg/m³ defined as Stage 2, in place since 2020. The 2030 EU PM_{2.5} annual limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) is set to 10 µg/m³. The Air Quality Guideline level recommended by the World Health Organization in 2021 (WHO, 2021a) for the PM_{2.5} annual average is set to 5 µg/m³. A new 2030 EU short-term limit value means that from 2030, the daily average PM_{2.5} concentration of 25 µg/m³ should not be exceeded more than 18 times per year (EU, 2024).

This chapter presents the 2023 situation in relation to both 2008 EU PM₁₀ limit values, i.e. the annual average and the 90.4 percentile of the daily averages, and the PM_{2.5} annual average. The 90.4 percentile of the daily averages is a more relevant PM₁₀ indicator in the context of the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) than the 36th highest daily mean, which was used up to 2013 maps (Horálek et al., 2017a).

The maps of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are based on the improved mapping methodology developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2019). The map layers are created for the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. Subsequently, the urban background and urban traffic map layers are merged together using the gridded GRIP road data (Meijer et al., 2018) into one urban map layer. This urban map layer is further combined with the rural map layer into the final PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5} map using a population density grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. The supplementary data used are chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, wind speed and land cover for rural areas, CTM output for urban background areas and CTM output and wind speed for urban traffic areas (Annex 3, Sections A3.1 and A3.2). For all PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators, the final combined map is presented in the 1 km grid resolution. Be it noted that this final map is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas (which are smoothed in this 1 km spatial resolution).

The current number of PM_{2.5} measurement stations is still somewhat limited and its spatial distribution is irregular over Europe. Therefore, in this paper the mapping of the health-related indicator PM_{2.5} annual average is based on a mapping methodology developed in Denby et al. (2011). This methodology derives additional pseudo PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations from PM₁₀ annual mean measurement concentrations. As such, it increases the number and spatial coverage of PM_{2.5} 'data points' and these data are used to derive a European wide map of annual mean PM_{2.5}. Pseudo PM_{2.5} stations data are estimated using PM₁₀ measurement data, surface solar radiation, latitude and longitude.

The population exposure tables are calculated based on the concentration maps, according to the methodology described in Horálek et al. (2019), i.e. they are calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas, in order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic. For details, see Annex 1, Equation A1.6.

Annex 3, Sections A3.1 and A3.2 provide details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} maps, as well as the uncertainty analysis of these maps.

2.1 PM₁₀ annual average

2.1.1 Concentration map

Map 2.1 presents the final combined concentration map for the 2023 PM₁₀ annual average. Light green areas show concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 15 µg/m³, yellow areas show concentrations above the LV₂₀₃₀ of 20 µg/m³. Red and purple areas indicate concentrations above the LV of 40 µg/m³.

The stations are not presented in the map, in order to better visualise the urban areas. However, concentration values from the station measurements used in the kriging interpolation methodology (Annex 3, Section A3.1) are considered to provide relevant information to the concentration map. In Map A4.1 of Annex 4 these point values are presented on top of Map 2.1. This illustrates the smoothing effect that the interpolation method can have on the gridded concentration fields.

Map 2.1 shows annual mean concentrations above the LV in urban areas of south-eastern Europe states (Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Greece), similarly to previous years. A larger, more continuous area with concentrations above LV occurs in the south-eastern and eastern parts of Türkiye. In general, the south-eastern, the south and the central parts of Europe appear with higher concentrations and population-weighted concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

Map 2.1 Concentration map of PM₁₀ annual average, 2023

Map 2.2 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for annual average for PM₁₀. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM₁₀ concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average PM₁₀ difference map the highest increases are observed in Türkiye, parts of southern and south-eastern Europe with the highest increases in Cyprus, Greece, Bulgaria and parts of Italy (Sardinia and south of Italy). On the other hand, there are decreases in the most of remaining countries, mainly central Europe with the most notable decrease in Poland, parts of some countries in south-eastern Europe with the most notable decrease in eastern Romania.

Map 2.2 Difference in concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for PM₁₀ annual average

Be it noted that besides the actual changes in the concentrations, the variability of the linear regression model and variogram parameters, changes in the measurement network and changes in the dispersion model may cause minor differences in the concentration levels estimated.

The uncertainty of the concentration map can be expressed in relative terms of the absolute Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) uncertainty related to the mean air pollution indicator value for all stations (see Annex 1, Section A1.4). This relative mean uncertainty (RRMSE, relative RMSE expressed as percent) of the final combined map of PM₁₀ annual average is 25% for rural areas and 31% for urban background areas including Turkish stations (i.e. quite similar to the last years), and 20% for rural areas and 19% for urban background areas without Turkish stations (Annex 3, Section A3.1). This means quite good mapping uncertainty, compared to the data quality objective for models of PM₁₀ annual average (i.e. 50%) as set in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). The main reason for presenting the results also without Turkish stations is to enable the comparison with previous years.

2.1.2 Population exposure

Table 2.1 and Figure 2.1 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM₁₀ concentrations for individual countries, for five European regions, for EU-27, and for the total considered area. Table 2.1 also presents the 2023 population-weighted concentration and the difference in the population-weighted concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 according to Equation A1.7.

Table 2.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, PM₁₀ annual average, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM ₁₀ – annual average, exposed population (%)					Population-weighted concentration			
			< 15	15-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	> 50	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762	6.8	12.2	58.6	22.4			25.6	26.9	-1.2
Andorra	AD	80	100.0	0.0					12.7	17.9	-5.2
Austria	AT	9 105	81.9	15.6	2.5				13.5	15.9	-2.4
Belgium	BE	11 743	33.0	66.3	0.7				15.8	18.6	-2.8
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194	7.5	18.0	38.5	31.0	4.9		26.6	32.3	-5.8
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	4.6	22.0	67.7	5.7			22.8	26.4	-3.6
Croatia	HR	3 851	21.7	42.5	35.7	0.0			18.6	21.9	-3.3
Cyprus	CY	1 419		0.1	17.3	75.3	7.3		33.1	32.1	1.0
Czechia	CZ	10 828	39.7	56.0	4.3				15.5	19.7	-4.2
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	98.9	1.1					11.9	14.9	-3.0
Estonia	EE	1 366	97.1	2.9					9.8	11.4	-1.6
Finland	FI	5 564	99.9	0.1					8.1	9.1	-1.1
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	63.2	34.1	2.6				14.4	16.0	-1.7
Germany	DE	83 119	93.3	6.7					12.6	15.2	-2.6
Greece	GR	10 414	1.1	9.6	55.3	33.8	0.2		27.0	26.2	0.8
Hungary	HU	9 600	6.7	71.2	22.1				18.2	22.4	-4.2
Iceland	IS	388	100.0						9.2	9.1	0.2
Ireland	IE	5 271	100.0						10.8	11.9	-1.2
Italy	IT	58 997	4.2	21.7	67.2	6.9			22.7	23.8	-1.1
Latvia	LV	1 883	55.2	43.7	1.1				13.9	17.3	-3.4
Liechtenstein	LI	40	100.0						11.4	12.2	-0.8
Lithuania	LT	2 857	40.1	53.1	6.8				15.2	18.8	-3.5
Luxembourg	LU	661	91.9	8.1					13.3	15.4	-2.1
Malta	MT	542		0.4	99.6				26.8	27.6	-0.8
Monaco	MC	39		80.5	19.5				17.0	19.9	-2.9
Montenegro	ME	617	12.9	51.4	35.7				19.2	26.0	-6.8
Netherlands	NL	17 811	44.4	55.6					15.3	17.5	-2.2
North Macedonia	MK	1 830	3.0	6.4	47.5	38.2	4.9		29.0	34.1	-5.1
Norway	NO	5 489	97.3	2.7					8.8	10.0	-1.3
Poland	PL	36 754	9.0	45.9	45.1				19.9	25.3	-5.4
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022	28.8	49.7	21.5				16.9	17.9	-1.0
Romania	RO	19 055	14.2	52.5	33.3				18.9	22.5	-3.7
San Marino	SM	34	5.2	83.6	11.2				19.2	20.8	-1.7
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	2.5	19.7	53.7	24.1			25.0	30.8	-5.8
Slovakia	SK	5 429	16.9	75.3	7.9				16.8	21.1	-4.3
Slovenia	SI	2 117	38.4	44.1	17.5				16.5	19.0	-2.5
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	18.3	48.8	33.0				18.5	19.7	-1.2
Sweden	SE	10 522	97.6	2.4					9.1	10.7	-1.6
Switzerland	CH	8 815	92.0	7.4	0.6				12.2	13.6	-1.4
Türkiye	TR	85 280	0.3	2.5	12.6	38.3	30.4	15.9	40.5	40.0	0.5
Total		560 170	37.5	26.1	21.4	8.1	4.5	2.3	20.4	22.2	-1.8
			63.6				6.8				
EU-27		443 198	43.9	31.4	22.6	2.1	0.0		16.8	19.2	-2.4
			75.3				0.0				
Northern Europe		34 055	90.8	8.6	0.6				10.2	12.2	-2.1
Western Europe		86 334	58.6	39.8	1.6				14.4	16.5	-2.0
Central Europe		165 805	61.5	25.9	12.6				15.0	18.5	-3.5
Southern Europe		142 589	15.6	32.8	45.4	6.1	0.1		20.6	21.5	-1.0
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	3.9	14.4	24.6	27.9	19.3	10.0	33.6	34.4	-0.8
Kosovo	XK	1 709	2.2	20.4	77.0	0.4			22.4	28.1	-5.7
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	2.5	19.5	47.7	30.2			25.7	31.5	-5.8

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and 5-year mean 2018-2022.

Figure 2.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different PM₁₀ annual averages (µg/m³) at country level, 2023

It is estimated that 63% and 36% of population of the considered mapped area has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the WHO Air Quality Guideline levels of 15 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021a) and the new 2030 EU limit value of 20 µg/m³ (EU, 2024), respectively. The same is true for 56% and 25% of the EU-27 population.

Approximately 7% of population of the considered mapped area has been exposed to concentrations above the EU annual limit value (ALV) of 40 µg/m³; the same is the case for 0.02% of the EU-27 population.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in 36 out of 41 mapped countries. A limited fraction of the population (up to 7%) has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in Greece, North Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Cyprus (in ascending order). 46% of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in Türkiye. However, as the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values (see Annex 3, Section A3.1), the percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the ALV will most likely be underestimated. Additional population exposure above the ALV could therefore be expected in countries like Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cyprus, Greece, North Macedonia, Serbia and Türkiye where a relatively large fraction (ca. 20-40%) of the population lives in areas with concentration levels 30-40 µg/m³.

The population-weighted concentration of the annual average for 2023 for the considered European population (including Türkiye) is estimated to be 20.4 µg/m³ and 16.8 µg/m³ for the EU-27 only. Values decreased by 1.8 and 2.4 µg/m³ compared to the previous 5-year mean 2018-2022, respectively. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Montenegro (6.8 µg/m³), the highest increase was estimated in Cyprus (1 µg/m³).

Figure 2.2 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 µg/m³. The highest population frequency can be seen for classes between 9 and 25 µg/m³. One can see a quite continuous strong decline of population frequency for classes between 25 and 30 µg/m³ and a mild decline for classes beyond 40 µg/m³.

Figure 2.2 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM₁₀ annual average, 2023. The WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2030 EU limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the current EU LV (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.14% of population lived in areas with PM₁₀ annual average concentrations between 75 and 230 µg/m³.

Figure 2.3 shows for individual countries the PM₁₀ annual average concentration to which the population in that country was exposed in 2023. It can be seen that, as already pointed out, the countries with the highest mean exposures to PM₁₀ annual average are located in the central and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 2.3 PM₁₀ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2023. The WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2030 EU limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the current EU limit value (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line.

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

2.2 PM₁₀ – 90.4 percentile of daily means

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) describes the PM₁₀ daily limit value (DLV) as “a daily average of 50 µg/m³ not to be exceeded more than 35 times a calendar year”. This requirement can be evaluated by the indicator 36th highest daily mean, which is in principle equivalent to the indicator 90.4 percentile of daily mean. However, for measurement data these two indicators are equivalent only if no data is missing, which is in general not the case. As shown in de Leeuw (2012), the additional uncertainty related to incomplete time series is substantially smaller when using percentile values instead of the x-th highest value. Furthermore, the Air Quality Directive requires the use of the 90.4 percentile when random measurements are used to assess the requirements of the PM₁₀ DLV. As in the previous reports since the maps for 2014 (Horálek et al., 2017a), the PM₁₀ daily means are expressed as the 90.4 percentile instead of the formerly used 36th highest daily mean. The analysis does not include comparisons against the WHO AQG levels and the revised LV₂₀₃₀ for daily means, due to the different pollutant aggregations (i.e. corresponding 99 and 95.1 percentile of daily means, respectively).

2.2.1 Concentration map

Map 2.3 presents the final combined map, where red and purple marked areas indicate values of the 90.4 percentile of daily means above 50 µg/m³ (i.e. concentrations above the DLV of 50 µg/m³ on more than 35 measurement days). The similar mapping procedure as in the case of the annual average is used. The mapping details and the uncertainty analysis are presented in Annex 3. Large areas with concentrations above the DLV are observed in northern Italy (i.e. the Po Valley) and in southern, south-eastern and eastern parts of Türkiye. Urban and surrounding areas with concentrations above the DLV are observed in Balkan countries and Cyprus.

In general, the south-eastern, the south and the central parts of Europe appear with higher concentrations and population-weighted concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

Map 2.3 Concentration map of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2023

The relative mean uncertainty (relative RMSE or RRMSE) of the final combined map of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means is 26% for rural and 30% for urban background areas including Turkish

stations. The mean uncertainty for the map without Türkiye is 20% for both rural areas and 22% for urban background areas (Annex 3, Section A3.1). Thus, the mapping uncertainty of this is at the similar level as in the case of the PM₁₀ annual average.

Map 2.4 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for the 90.4 percentile of daily means for PM₁₀. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM₁₀ concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease.

Map 2.4 Difference in concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for PM₁₀ 90.4 percentile

The situation is similar to that of the annual average value of PM₁₀. The highest increases are observed in Türkiye, parts of southern and south-eastern Europe with the highest increases in Cyprus, Greece and parts of Italy (Sardinia, Sicilia and south of Italy). On the other hand, there are decreases in the most of remaining countries, mainly central Europe with the most notable decrease in Poland, parts of some Balkan countries with the most notable decrease in western Romania, and in Po Valley in Italy.

2.2.2 Population exposure

Table 2.2 and Figure 2.4 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means for individual countries, for five European regions, for EU-27, and for the total considered area. More detailed Table 2.2 also presents the 2023 population-weighted concentration and the difference in the population-weighted concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 according to Equation A1.7.

In 2023 about 16% of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and 3% of the EU-27 population are estimated to live in areas with PM₁₀ concentrations above the EU daily LV of 50 µg/m³.

Table 2.2 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM ₁₀ - perc90.4, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50-75	> 75	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762	0.2	11.6	12.4	18.4	57.5		48.7	48.2	0.6
Andorra	AD	80	14.5	85.4	0.1				26.0	31.3	-5.4
Austria	AT	9 105	20.8	74.8	4.4				23.2	27.6	-4.4
Belgium	BE	11 743	2.2	88.5	9.3				27.3	32.4	-5.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194	0.0	12.4	20.9	16.6	36.4	13.6	51.3	64.0	-12.7
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	0.7	17.8	42.2	36.4	2.9		37.2	45.3	-8.2
Croatia	HR	3 851	1.3	38.6	34.3	24.2	1.6		33.1	40.9	-7.8
Cyprus	CY	1 419			2.4	14.0	80.2	3.5	55.6	52.8	2.8
Czechia	CZ	10 828	8.2	80.6	11.2				25.8	34.8	-9.0
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	79.4	20.6					19.3	25.0	-5.7
Estonia	EE	1 366	59.0	38.6	2.5				18.4	20.5	-2.1
Finland	FI	5 564	87.9	10.9	1.2				15.3	17.0	-1.7
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	13.6	79.8	6.5	0.0			24.4	26.9	-2.5
Germany	DE	83 119	39.8	60.2					20.7	25.6	-5.0
Greece	GR	10 414	0.0	6.0	29.5	41.1	23.3		43.7	43.1	0.6
Hungary	HU	9 600	0.0	39.6	59.8	0.7			31.1	39.7	-8.6
Iceland	IS	388	72.7	27.3					18.0	16.7	1.3
Ireland	IE	5 271	81.4	18.6					18.0	20.6	-2.6
Italy	IT	58 997	0.8	11.7	47.0	27.8	12.7		39.6	42.1	-2.5
Latvia	LV	1 883	27.8	45.0	27.2				24.6	30.2	-5.6
Liechtenstein	LI	40	66.9	33.1					20.0	21.7	-1.6
Lithuania	LT	2 857	22.1	55.1	22.8				26.1	32.1	-6.0
Luxembourg	LU	661	18.0	82.0					21.4	25.4	-4.0
Malta	MT	542			2.6	97.4			42.5	42.9	-0.4
Monaco	MC	39		80.5	19.5				27.4	30.7	-3.4
Montenegro	ME	617	0.6	28.0	37.4	32.3	1.7		36.0	50.7	-14.8
Netherlands	NL	17 811	1.9	98.1	0.0				23.6	28.8	-5.1
North Macedonia	MK	1 830	0.2	5.0	7.6	22.9	59.4	4.9	55.9	66.0	-10.1
Norway	NO	5 489	66.2	30.8	2.9	0.1			17.2	18.6	-1.4
Poland	PL	36 754	0.4	34.5	53.9	11.2			32.7	45.3	-12.6
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022	9.3	58.8	30.7	1.2			27.6	29.3	-1.7
Romania	RO	19 055	4.0	41.6	41.8	12.5	0.0		31.6	38.5	-6.9
San Marino	SM	34		15.8	84.2				32.6	37.1	-4.5
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	0.2	10.0	33.7	26.1	30.0	0.0	43.1	57.3	-14.2
Slovakia	SK	5 429	1.6	69.1	29.3				28.7	37.7	-9.0
Slovenia	SI	2 117	3.0	56.7	39.4	0.9			28.8	33.8	-5.0
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	4.8	40.2	53.5	1.5			29.9	31.8	-1.8
Sweden	SE	10 522	83.3	14.4	2.2	0.1	0.0		16.6	19.2	-2.6
Switzerland	CH	8 815	27.6	70.2	1.9	0.3			21.8	24.2	-2.3
Türkiye	TR	85 280	0.0	0.9	4.8	7.9	60.0	26.4	68.6	69.1	-0.5
Total		560 170	14.3	40.7	21.1	7.9	12.1	4.0	34.5	38.4	-3.9
			55.0				16.1				
EU-27		443 198	16.6	48.8	24.5	7.5	2.6	0.0	28.1	32.9	-4.7
			65.4				2.6				
Northern Europe		34 055	71.1	23.9	5.0	0.0	0.0		18.3	21.7	-3.4
Western Europe		86 334	13.6	82.8	3.6				24.0	27.8	-3.8
Central Europe		165 805	23.0	55.9	18.4	2.7			24.9	32.2	-7.3
Southern Europe		142 589	3.9	29.6	42.8	16.0	7.8	0.0	34.7	36.4	-1.7
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	0.7	10.4	16.1	12.7	43.1	17.0	57.2	60.2	-3.0
Kosovo	XK	1 709	0.1	5.3	56.2	34.6	3.7	0.0	39.0	54.8	-15.8
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	0.2	11.2	27.9	23.9	36.7		44.2	57.9	-13.7

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and 5-year mean 2018-2022.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the DLV in 27 out of 41 mapped countries. A limited fraction of the population (up to 4%) was exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Sweden, Romania, Croatia, Montenegro, Bulgaria and Kosovo (in ascending order). More than 10% but less than 50% of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Italy, Greece and Serbia. More than half of the population has been estimated to be exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Bosnia and Herzegovina (50%), Albania (58%), North Macedonia (64%), Cyprus (83%) and Türkiye (86%).

Figure 2.4 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2023

The European-wide population-weighted concentration of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means is estimated for 2023 at 34.5 µg/m³ for the total mapped area and 28.1 µg/m³ for the EU-27. The population-weighted concentration of this PM₁₀ indicator decreased by 3.9 µg/m³ for the considered European population and by 4.7 µg/m³ for EU-27 compared to the previous 5-year mean 2018-2022. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Kosovo (15.8 µg/m³), the highest increase was estimated in Cyprus (2.8 µg/m³).

Figure 2.5 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 2 µg/m³. One can see the highest population frequency for classes between 18 and 50 µg/m³, then a continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes above 50 µg/m³.

Figure 2.5 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2023. The EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) is marked by the red line.

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.13% of population lived in areas with values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means between 135 and 690 µg/m³.

Figure 2.6 shows for individual countries the P90.4 of the PM₁₀ daily concentrations to which the population was exposed in 2023. It can be seen that the countries with the highest values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means are located mainly in south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 2.6 PM₁₀ expressed as indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means to which the population was exposed in 2023, per country. The EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) is marked by red line

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

As in previous years, the daily LV was more widely exceeded than the annual LV in 2023.

2.3 PM_{2.5} annual average

2.3.1 Concentration map

Map 2.5 presents the final combined map for the 2023 PM_{2.5} annual average. Light green areas show concentrations above WHO AQG of 5 µg/m³, while yellow areas show concentrations above the LV₂₀₃₀ of 10 µg/m³. Red areas show concentrations above the indicative LV of 20 µg/m³ defined as Stage 2 (ILV). The dark red areas show concentrations above the annual limit value (ALV) of 25 µg/m³.

Due to the lack of enough rural PM_{2.5} stations in Türkiye, no proper interpolation results could be estimated for this country in a rural map. Therefore, the estimated PM_{2.5} values for Türkiye are not presented in the final map.

According to Map 2.5, the areas with the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations appear to be the Po Valley in northern Italy, in the Krakow – Katowice (Poland) – Ostrava (Czechia) industrial region and areas of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, North Macedonia, Albania, Romania, Bulgaria and Greece. Concentrations above the ALV appear in urban areas in Bosnia and Herzegovina and in North Macedonia. Several other cities and areas in south-eastern and central Europe also show elevated PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations. Like in the case of PM₁₀, the central and the south and south-eastern parts of Europe show higher concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

Similarly to the PM₁₀, the final map in 1 km resolution is representative for the rural and the urban background areas, but not for the urban traffic areas (which are smoothed in the 1 km resolution). In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.3 of Annex 4.

Map 2.5 Concentration map of PM_{2.5} annual average, 2023

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of PM_{2.5} annual average is 27% for rural and 26% for urban background areas and it is determined exclusively on the actual PM_{2.5} measurement data points, i.e. not on the pseudo stations (Annex 3, Section A3.2). Similarly as in the case of PM₁₀, this uncertainty

is satisfactory, compared to the data quality objective for models of PM_{2.5} annual average (i.e. 50%) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Map 2.6 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for annual average for PM_{2.5}. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM_{2.5} concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average PM_{2.5} difference map the highest increases are in parts of southern Europe with the highest increases in Greece, Bulgaria and parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina, as well as in the north of Italy and parts of northern Europe (Norway and Sweden). Moderate increases are also observed in southern Italy and parts of southern Spain. On the other hand, there are decreases in most of the remaining countries, mainly in central Europe (especially in Poland, Hungary, Slovakia), extending into Czechia, Germany, the Benelux countries and Austria, and in parts of some countries in south-eastern and southern Europe (northern Spain, northern Italy, Serbia and Romania).

Map 2.6 Difference in concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for PM_{2.5} annual average

2.3.2 Population exposure

Table 2.3 and Figure 2.7 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM_{2.5} concentrations calculated on a grid of 1 km resolution. Table 2.3 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area.

About 96% and 42% of the considered European population (excluding Türkiye), has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the WHO Air Quality Guideline level of 5 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021a) and the new 2030 EU limit value of 10 µg/m³ (EU, 2024), respectively. The same is true for 97% and 41% of the EU-27 population.

The total considered and the EU-27 population exposed to concentrations above the EU ALV of 25 µg/m³ has been 0.2% and none, respectively.

Table 2.3 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, PM_{2.5} annual average 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM _{2.5} – annual average, exposed population (%)					Population-weighted concentration			
			< 5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	> 25	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762	0.0	4.1	27.7	45.5	22.7		16.8	17.4	-0.6
Andorra	AD	80	23.9	76.1					5.8	8.7	-2.9
Austria	AT	9 105	1.3	78.9	19.8				9.1	10.9	-1.8
Belgium	BE	11 743	0.3	85.8	13.9				8.8	10.8	-2.0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194		4.6	21.2	25.3	33.4	15.5	19.3	23.6	-4.3
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	0.0	3.9	54.1	41.7	0.3		14.6	17.2	-2.7
Croatia	HR	3 851	0.0	22.2	39.5	36.6	1.7		13.2	15.4	-2.2
Cyprus	CY	1 419		2.4	48.0	47.1	2.5		14.7	14.4	0.3
Czechia	CZ	10 828	0.0	31.4	63.2	5.4			10.9	14.3	-3.3
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	2.4	97.6					6.6	8.6	-2.0
Estonia	EE	1 366	42.9	57.1					5.2	5.9	-0.6
Finland	FI	5 564	80.0	20.0					4.3	5.0	-0.7
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	0.7	89.5	9.8				8.5	9.5	-1.1
Germany	DE	83 119	0.1	98.9	1.0				7.9	10.0	-2.1
Greece	GR	10 414		2.5	33.0	52.9	11.5		16.5	16.0	0.5
Hungary	HU	9 600		2.4	94.6	3.0			12.4	15.1	-2.7
Iceland	IS	388	100.0						4.1	4.1	-0.1
Ireland	IE	5 271	20.5	79.5					6.2	7.3	-1.1
Italy	IT	58 997	0.2	15.4	49.7	26.2	8.5		14.0	14.7	-0.8
Latvia	LV	1 883	1.7	82.0	16.3				8.0	10.2	-2.1
Liechtenstein	LI	40	0.6	99.4					7.8	8.3	-0.5
Lithuania	LT	2 857		91.1	8.9				8.3	11.2	-2.9
Luxembourg	LU	661	0.5	99.5					7.2	8.0	-0.9
Malta	MT	542		3.5	96.5				10.9	11.4	-0.5
Monaco	MC	39		100.0					8.7	11.1	-2.4
Montenegro	ME	617	0.0	9.7	60.3	30.0			13.4	17.9	-4.5
Netherlands	NL	17 811		99.9	0.1				8.2	10.2	-1.9
North Macedonia	MK	1 830		2.2	12.9	41.9	26.3	16.7	19.5	23.2	-3.7
Norway	NO	5 489	46.8	53.2					5.0	5.5	-0.5
Poland	PL	36 754		6.8	59.5	33.3	0.4		14.0	17.9	-3.9
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022	7.2	79.8	13.0				7.7	8.3	-0.6
Romania	RO	19 055	0.0	8.2	68.5	23.2	0.0		13.2	15.3	-2.1
San Marino	SM	34		12.1	87.9				12.5	12.9	-0.5
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350		0.8	28.3	42.8	28.0	0.0	17.5	21.5	-4.1
Slovakia	SK	5 429	0.0	6.5	86.7	6.8			12.3	15.3	-2.9
Slovenia	SI	2 117	0.0	20.5	63.9	15.6			12.1	13.4	-1.4
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	2.6	54.5	42.9				9.5	10.2	-0.7
Sweden	SE	10 522	60.3	39.7					4.7	5.5	-0.7
Switzerland	CH	8 815	3.3	93.9	2.3	0.5			7.7	8.7	-1.0
Total (without Türkiye)		474 890	3.8	54.1	28.4	11.1	2.4	0.2	10.4	12.2	-1.7
			57.9				2.6				
EU-27		443 198	3.4	55.5	29.4	10.3	1.5		10.3	12.0	-1.7
			58.9				1.5				
Northern Europe		34 055	42.8	55.5	1.7				5.5	6.8	-1.2
Western Europe		86 334	1.5	90.5	8.0				8.3	9.8	-1.4
Central Europe		165 805	0.3	62.4	28.6	8.6	0.1		10.0	12.7	-2.6
Southern Europe		142 589	1.5	38.8	39.6	15.5	4.5		11.7	12.3	-0.6
South-Eastern Europe without Türkiye		46 106	0.0	6.7	48.4	32.9	10.1	1.8	15.1	17.8	-2.7
Kosovo	XK	1 709		0.7	27.3	68.6	3.3	0.1	16.4	20.1	-3.8
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641		0.9	28.6	36.2	34.4		17.8	21.9	-4.1

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and 5-year mean 2018-2022.

No population in 37 out of 40 countries has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV. In Kosovo, 0.1% of population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV. In Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia, 16% and 17% of the population have been exposed above this ALV, respectively.

Concentrations above the indicative limit value (ILV) of 20 µg/m³ were found in areas with 3% of the considered European population and with 2% of the EU-27 population. No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ILV in 28 countries. In Romania, Bulgaria, Poland, Croatia, Cyprus, Kosovo and Italy (in ascending order) between 0.02 and 9% of the population is exposed to concentrations above the ILV. In Greece, Albania, Serbia, North Macedonia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, 12-49% of the population suffers from exposures above this ILV.

Figure 2.7 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of PM_{2.5} annual average (µg/m³), 2023

Since PM_{2.5} is one of the most relevant pollutants linked to health problems and premature mortality (EEA, 2024) it should be mentioned that at least some part of the population, with the exception of Iceland, was exposed to PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations above the WHO AQG level in each country (a minimum of 20% in Finland). More than 90% and 100% of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the WHO AQG level in 33 and 13 countries, respectively.

As the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values (Annex 3, Section A3.2), the percentages and/or the number of countries with population exposed to concentrations above both the current ALV and the indicative ILV will most likely be higher.

The population-weighted concentration of the PM_{2.5} annual means has been estimated for 2023 at 10.4 µg/m³ for European population (excluding Türkiye) and 10.3 µg/m³ for the EU-27, which means a decrease about 1.7 µg/m³ compared to 5-year mean for both characteristics. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Montenegro (4.5 µg/m³), the highest increase was estimated in Greece (0.5 µg/m³).

Figure 2.8 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 0.5 µg/m³. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 6 and 14 µg/m³.

Figure 2.8 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM_{2.5} annual average, 2023. The WHO AQG level (5 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the new 2030 EU annual limit value level (10 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the EU annual indicative limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the orange line and the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.02% of population lived in areas with PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations between 30 and 32 µg/m³.

The boxplot showing for individual countries the PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2023 is presented in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9 PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2023. The WHO AQG level (5 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2030 EU limit value (10 µg/m³) by the yellow line, the EU PM_{2.5} indicative limit value (20 µg/m³) by the orange line and the current EU limit value (50 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

3 Ozone

For ozone, four health-related indicators, i.e. 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means (calendar year and 3-year mean), peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10, and seven vegetation-related indicators, i.e. AOT40 for vegetation, AOT40 for forests, POD₆ for crops (wheat, potato and tomato) and POD₁ for trees (beech and spruce) are considered. For the definition of the SOMO35, SOMO10 and AOT40 and POD indicators, see following sections and Annexes 1 and 2.

The separate rural and urban background health-related indicator map layers are calculated at a resolution of 10 km. Subsequently, the final health-related indicator maps are created by combining rural and urban areas based on the 1 km resolution population density map, following the procedure as described in Annex 1, Section A1.1. The supplementary data used are chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude and surface solar radiation for rural areas and CTM output, wind speed and surface solar radiation for urban areas (Annex 3). The final concentration maps are presented on the 1 km grid resolution. The population exposure tables are calculated on the basis of these health-related indicator maps.

The vegetation-related indicator maps are created for rural areas only, as urban areas are considered not to represent areas covered by vegetation (although the vegetation located in the outskirts of agglomerations might be excluded by this approach). These maps are calculated from observations at rural background stations and are representative for rural areas only. The supplementary data used are CTM output, altitude and surface solar radiation. These supplementary data sources are the same as those used for the human health related ozone indicators in the rural areas. The maps have a resolution of 2 km. This resolution serves the needs of the EEA's AIR004 indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2025b).

Annex 3, Section A3.3 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the maps of the ozone indicators, as well as the uncertainty analysis of the maps.

3.1 Ozone – 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) describes the O₃ target value (TV) for the protection of human health as “a maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 25 times a calendar year, averaged over three years”. On an annual basis, what it is called the target value threshold ⁽⁴⁾, can be evaluated by the indicator 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean, which is in principle equivalent to the indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means. However, for measurement data these two indicators are equivalent only if no data is missing, which is in general not the case. As shown in de Leeuw (2012), the additional uncertainty related to incomplete time series is substantially smaller when using percentile values instead of the x-th highest value. As in the previous reports since 2014 maps, this ozone indicator is expressed as the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means instead of the formerly used 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean. In this report, the 3-year mean of the indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means is also presented for the first time. The analysis does not include comparisons against the WHO AQG levels and the revised LV₂₀₃₀ for maximum daily 8-hour mean, due to different pollutant aggregations (i.e. corresponding 99 and 95.1 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, respectively).

3.1.1 Concentration map

Map 3.1 presents the final combined map for 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means for the current calendar year (2023) and 3-year mean (2021-2023). In the maps, the red and dark red areas show values of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means above 120 µg/m³ on more than 25

⁽⁴⁾ A maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 25 times a calendar year.

days in 2023, i.e. above the TV threshold in 2023 and above the TV in the 3-year mean 2021-2023, respectively.

The map shows that percentile values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ occur in several areas of Europe in 2023. Those values are particularly evident in large areas of Türkiye, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, northern Italy and Switzerland. To a lesser extent, values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ occurred in Greece, France, Slovenia, Austria, Spain, Liechtenstein, Germany, Cyprus, Poland, Czechia, Albania, Hungary, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Kosovo, Andorra, Bulgaria, Malta, Slovakia and Monaco.

Regarding the 3-year mean (2021-2023) of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, that percentile values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ occur in large areas of Türkiye, Bosnia and Herzegovina, northern Italy and Switzerland. To a lesser extent, values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (3-year mean) occurred in Greece, Austria, France, Croatia, Slovenia, Cyprus, Liechtenstein, Spain, Portugal, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Germany, Albania, Bulgaria, Poland, Malta, Hungary, Montenegro, Monaco, Serbia, Andorra and Czechia.

In general, the southern, the south-eastern and central parts of Europe show higher ozone concentrations than the northern parts, which is caused mainly by higher solar radiation and temperature in these areas. Nevertheless, concentrations above the TV threshold can occur even in northern Europe during warm year as it was presented for 2018 (Horálek et al., 2021).

Map 3.1 Concentration map of ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023 (left) and 3-year mean 2021-2023 (right)

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map for 2023 including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.4 of Annex 4.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h ozone means is about 8% for rural and 11% for urban areas (Annex 3, Section A3.2). The low uncertainty values are influenced by the character of this ozone indicator. Note that the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets no modelling uncertainty for ozone annual indicators.

In 2023, the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima for O₃ showed mixed patterns across the entire mapped area compared to the 2018-2022 average. The highest decreases (more than 10 µg/m³) were observed particularly in a large area of Türkiye; smaller decreases (between 4 and 10 µg/m³) were observed in parts of different states of southern and south-eastern Europe. Regarding western and central Europe, decreases were observed in large areas of France, Germany, Ireland and Poland.

In contrast, the largest areas with increases were observed in parts of southern, central and northern Europe, especially in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Romania, Poland, the Baltic states, and southern Finland, where levels rose by more than 4 µg/m³ in some areas.

Map 3.2 Difference in concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima

3.1.2 Population exposure

Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1 give, for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes in 2023. Table 3.1 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area. Table 3.2 and Figure 3.2 present the same characteristics for the 3-year mean (2021-2023) of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means.

In 2023, it has been estimated that 12% of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and 12% of the EU-27 population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the health-related target value threshold of 120 µg/m³.

Table 3.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	Ozone — perc93.2, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 90	90-100	100-110	110-120	120-140	> 140	2023	5-yr mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762		1.4	47.8	50.1	0.8		110.0	109.8	0.2
Andorra	AD	80		72.4	9.7	14.2	3.6		101.9	102.2	-0.3
Austria	AT	9 105		0.2	12.7	76.4	10.7		115.1	116.6	-1.5
Belgium	BE	11 743		3.3	75.6	21.0			107.5	110.7	-3.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194			2.1	37.3	60.6	0.1	122.4	113.4	9.0
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	28.9	49.6	20.2	1.3	0.0		94.2	96.4	-2.2
Croatia	HR	3 851			21.7	54.9	23.4	0.0	115.8	113.7	2.1
Cyprus	CY	1 419		7.0	48.6	42.3	2.1		108.8	110.0	-1.2
Czechia	CZ	10 828			13.0	86.3	0.7		113.8	116.1	-2.4
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	11.3	66.5	22.2				96.5	98.2	-1.7
Estonia	EE	1 366		99.0	1.0				96.4	93.3	3.1
Finland	FI	5 564	0.9	99.0	0.1				95.0	91.3	3.7
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	0.1	8.3	56.6	23.9	11.1		109.3	112.3	-2.9
Germany	DE	83 119		0.2	31.2	59.4	9.2		112.8	115.1	-2.2
Greece	GR	10 414	0.0	2.8	11.7	31.2	54.3	0.0	118.1	113.8	4.4
Hungary	HU	9 600		0.1	42.0	40.5	17.4		112.7	112.1	0.5
Iceland	IS	388	27.0	72.2	0.8				90.7	88.7	2.0
Ireland	IE	5 271	80.1	19.9					87.4	91.5	-4.2
Italy	IT	58 997	0.9	3.3	27.6	27.3	28.8	12.1	119.2	121.8	-2.5
Latvia	LV	1 883		65.6	34.4				97.9	94.0	3.9
Liechtenstein	LI	40				99.9	0.1		118.4	120.2	-1.8
Lithuania	LT	2 857		0.1	99.9				104.2	98.3	5.9
Luxembourg	LU	661			5.1	94.9			112.1	111.2	0.9
Malta	MT	542			72.1	27.7	0.1		109.1	106.5	2.6
Monaco	MC	39					100.0		120.5	122.2	-1.7
Montenegro	ME	617		4.0	38.5	57.5	0.0		109.9	107.5	2.5
Netherlands	NL	17 811		7.5	77.8	14.7			105.6	106.1	-0.6
North Macedonia	MK	1 830	0.9	40.8	53.0	5.0	0.3		102.3	102.3	0.0
Norway	NO	5 489	2.9	96.2	1.0	0.0			94.7	94.1	0.5
Poland	PL	36 754		0.8	59.8	38.9	0.5		109.2	109.4	-0.2
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022		5.8	70.1	24.1			106.1	101.9	4.2
Romania	RO	19 055	3.4	46.0	47.8	2.7			100.3	99.7	0.6
San Marino	SM	34				100.0			115.5	117.6	-2.1
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	1.4	20.6	41.8	36.2	0.0		106.4	106.2	0.2
Slovakia	SK	5 429		2.3	58.9	38.9	0.0		108.4	110.8	-2.4
Slovenia	SI	2 117			19.8	76.3	3.9		113.5	116.2	-2.8
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	0.4	14.4	32.7	40.8	11.7		109.8	109.5	0.3
Sweden	SE	10 522	4.4	90.2	5.4				95.0	96.2	-1.2
Switzerland	CH	8 815			2.5	27.4	70.0	0.1	122.2	121.7	0.5
Türkiye	TR	85 280	33.1	20.1	24.2	17.1	5.5	0.0	96.7	103.7	-7.0
Total		560 167	6.4	13.7	36.2	31.6	10.8	1.3	108.1	110.0	-1.9
				20.1			12.1				
EU-27		443 198	1.9	11.6	39.6	34.5	10.7	1.7	110.0	111.1	-1.1
				13.5			12.4				
Northern Europe		34 055	4.1	79.7	16.2	0.0			96.2	95.3	0.9
Western Europe		86 334	4.7	8.7	62.3	20.3	4.1		106.6	109.1	-2.4
Central Europe		165 805		0.4	35.6	54.1	10.0	0.0	112.5	113.9	-1.4
Southern Europe		142 589	0.5	7.1	32.9	31.7	22.7	5.1	114.4	115.1	-0.7
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	22.9	24.3	29.1	17.8	5.8	0.0	99.5	103.5	-4.0
Kosovo	XK	1 709		33.6	55.5	10.8	0.1		102.8	104.8	-2.0
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	1.7	17.3	38.3	42.7			107.3	106.5	0.8

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and 5-year mean 2018-2022.

Table 3.2 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2021-2023 (3-year mean)

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	Ozone — perc93.2, exposed population (%)					Population-weighted concentration	
			< 90	90-100	100-110	110-120	120-140	> 140	2021-2023
Albania	AL	2 762		4.4	26.9	67.5	1.2		111.8
Andorra	AD	80		72.3	12.2	13.6	1.9		98.5
Austria	AT	9 105		0.0	10.5	88.4	1.1		114.4
Belgium	BE	11 743		6.2	89.2	4.6			105.3
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194			1.6	75.0	23.4		117.6
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	36.2	47.1	13.1	3.6	0.0		93.9
Croatia	HR	3 851			10.4	75.0	14.6		114.6
Cyprus	CY	1 419		4.4	45.3	40.5	9.8		109.9
Czechia	CZ	10 828			18.9	81.0	0.0		112.9
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	16.6	79.1	4.2				94.1
Estonia	EE	1 366	28.4	71.6	0.0				92.1
Finland	FI	5 564	39.1	60.9					90.6
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	0.1	5.3	65.6	21.4	7.7		108.7
Germany	DE	83 119		3.0	46.0	50.4	0.6		110.2
Greece	GR	10 414	0.2	5.2	22.6	28.5	43.5	0.0	116.7
Hungary	HU	9 600			21.9	56.3	21.8		114.3
Iceland	IS	388	74.8	25.0	0.2				89.0
Ireland	IE	5 271	51.4	48.6	0.0				89.5
Italy	IT	58 997	0.6	2.2	26.6	26.6	26.4	17.6	121.4
Latvia	LV	1 883	2.2	97.6	0.2				93.4
Liechtenstein	LI	40				99.9	0.1		116.5
Lithuania	LT	2 857		94.2	5.8				98.2
Luxembourg	LU	661			87.6	12.4			107.0
Malta	MT	542			72.1	27.2	0.7		109.2
Monaco	MC	39					100.0		121.9
Montenegro	ME	617		3.6	63.6	32.8	0.0		108.4
Netherlands	NL	17 811		37.4	61.0	1.6			102.0
North Macedonia	MK	1 830	4.0	15.9	55.0	24.8	0.3		104.2
Norway	NO	5 489	26.0	73.6	0.4	0.0			91.2
Poland	PL	36 754		4.9	59.1	35.8	0.2		107.9
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022	1.8	27.0	60.2	10.6	0.4		102.6
Romania	RO	19 055	2.4	40.0	53.8	3.8			100.6
San Marino	SM	34				100.0			114.9
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	0.1	5.9	37.7	56.1	0.2		110.5
Slovakia	SK	5 429			54.7	45.3			109.3
Slovenia	SI	2 117			3.3	81.8	14.9		116.2
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	1.5	14.9	40.0	37.8	5.8		108.2
Sweden	SE	10 522	24.0	75.2	0.8				92.4
Switzerland	CH	8 815			0.5	71.3	27.5	0.7	118.6
Türkiye	TR	85 280	37.6	13.6	15.0	22.6	11.0	0.2	99.0
Total		560 167	8.1	13.8	37.1	31.1	8.0	2.0	
			21.9				10		107.5
EU-27		443 198	2.9	13.7	42.5	31.2	7.3	2.4	
			16.6				9.7		109.0
Northern Europe		34 055	23.0	75.5	1.5	0.0			92.7
Western Europe		86 334	3.0	14.9	68.0	13.7	0.4		105.0
Central Europe		165 805		2.6	41.4	52.7	3.3	0.0	110.8
Southern Europe		142 589	0.9	8.2	34.9	28.8	19.7	7.5	114.6
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	26.0	17.8	22.9	25.1	8.0	0.1	101.1
Kosovo	XK	1 709		5.1	76.3	17.9	0.7		106.4
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	0.1	6.2	27.8	65.8	0.1		111.5

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold in 15 countries. In Slovakia, Bulgaria, Kosovo, Montenegro, Liechtenstein, Malta, North Macedonia, Poland, Czechia, Albania, Cyprus, Andorra, Slovenia, Türkiye, Germany (in ascending order) up to 10% of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold. In Austria, France, Spain, Hungary, Croatia, Italy, this was the case for between 11% and 50% of the population. More than half of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold in Greece, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland and Monaco.

Figure 3.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 2023

Figure 3.2 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 3-year mean (2021-2023)

Based on the 3-year mean (2021-2023), it is estimated that 10% of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and 9.7% of the EU-27 population lived in areas where ozone concentrations exceeded the health-related target value of $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV in 2021-2023 in 15 countries. In Montenegro, Bulgaria, Czechia, Liechtenstein, Poland, Serbia, North Macedonia, Portugal, Germany, Malta, Kosovo, Austria, Albania, Andorra, Spain, France and Cyprus up to 10% of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV. In Türkiye, Croatia, Slovenia, Hungary, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Greece and Italy, this was the case for between 11% and 50% of the population. More than half of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV in Monaco.

As the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values due to interpolation smoothing (Annex 3, Section A3.3), the percentage of population exposed to values above the TV threshold is most likely somewhat underestimated; additional population exposure above the TV threshold in 2023 might be expected in some other countries: Albania, Austria, Croatia, Czechia, Germany, Luxembourg, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, Slovenia and San Marino, and above the TV in Albania, Austria, Bosnia, Croatia, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Liechtenstein, San Marino, Serbia, Slovenia and Switzerland (in the case of 3-year mean). The reason is that in these countries the estimated percentage population exposed to the concentrations between 110 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is considerable (more than 50%).

The overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in 2023 in terms of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means has been estimated to be 108.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 110.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the considered European area and for the EU-27, respectively, i.e. of about 1.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 1.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ lower than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean concentration, respectively. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Türkiye (7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), the highest increase was estimated in Bosnia and Herzegovina (9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Based on the 3-year mean (2021-2023), the overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in terms of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means has been estimated to be 107.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 109.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the considered European area and for the EU-27.

One can see that more population was exposed to concentrations above the 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2023 compared to the 3-year mean 2021-2023, indicating that 2023 was a year with higher O₃ levels than the previous two.

Figure 3.3 (left) shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 100 and 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For classes above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a sharp decline of population frequency can be seen. Figure 3.3 (right), based on 3-year mean (2021-2023), shows that the highest frequency is concentrated in the range of approximately 104 to 114 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For classes above 114 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a sharp decline in population frequency is observed.

Figure 3.3 Population exposure frequency distribution, O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023 (left) and 3-year mean 2021-2023 (right). The EU target value threshold (120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the red line

The boxplot showing for individual countries the ozone concentrations expressed as the indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means for year 2023 and 3-year mean (2021-2023) to which the population per country was exposed is presented in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Concentrations of O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means to which the population per country was exposed in 2023 (top) and 3-year mean 2021-2023 (bottom)

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

3.2 Ozone – peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means

In September 2021, the WHO introduced new AQG for O₃. The new long-term Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level ⁽⁵⁾ for O₃ is set to 60 µg/m³ and it is related to the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean

⁽⁵⁾ Besides the short-term AQG of 100 µg/m³ defined as 99th percentile of the annual distribution of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration (WHO, 2021a).

O₃ concentration of the so-called peak season. The peak season is defined as the six consecutive months of the year with the highest six-month running-average ozone concentration (WHO, 2021a). For details of the calculations of this indicator, see Annex 2 Section A2.1.

The new long-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (i.e. 60 µg/ m³, not to be exceeded by the average of the daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration during the peak season) was determined based on average concentrations observed in studies that examined the health effects of long-term O₃ exposure. By setting this guideline, WHO aims to minimize the health risks associated with long-term ozone exposure and non-accidental mortality (WHO, 2021a). This peak season indicator is not regulated in any of the EU air quality directives, and there are no associated limit or target values defined.

3.2.1 Concentration map

Map 3.3 presents the final combined map for ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means. In the map, all coloured area except the dark green ones show values of peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means above 60 µg/m³.

The map shows that in 2023, areas with peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means exceeding 60 µg/m³ cover the entire mapped region with the exception of a few urban areas in Türkiye and Bulgaria. Similar to other O₃ characteristics, lower values (< 80 µg/m³) were observed in northern and western Europe (Finland, northern Sweden and Ireland), while higher values (> 100 µg/m³) are observed in central Europe (Switzerland, Slovenia, parts of Austria), as well as in southern and south-eastern Europe (parts of Italy, parts of Spain and Portugal, southern France, parts of Balkan countries, Cyprus, and large areas of Türkiye).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.5 of Annex 4.

Map 3.3 Ozone indicator peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023

Since the concentration map for ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means was presented for the first time for 2022, it was not possible to calculate a 5-year mean (2018-2022) and subsequently create a differences map, as done for other pollutants and indicators.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means is about 8% for rural and 10% for urban areas (Annex 3, Section A3.2). The low uncertainty values are influenced by the character of this ozone indicator. Note that the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets no modelling uncertainty for ozone long-term indicators.

3.2.2 Population exposure

Figure 3.5 and Table 3.3 give, for the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area. Table 3.3 also presents the population-weighted concentration.

In 2023, it has been estimated that 98% of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and almost 100% of the EU-27 population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means of $60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 3.5 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023

The overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in terms of peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means has been estimated to be $87.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2023 for the considered European area (including Türkiye) and $89.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the EU-27. When considering individual countries, the highest overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in terms of peak season average has been estimated to be $102.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Monaco and $99.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Bosnia and Herzegovina, respectively, while the lowest was estimated to be $74.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Ireland.

Table 3.3 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs·1000)	Ozone — peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means (%)						Population-weighted concentration 2023
			< 60	60 - 80	80 - 90	90 - 100	100 - 120	> 120	
Albania	AL	2 762			20.5	78.6	0.9	92.1	
Andorra	AD	80			73.9	14.9	11.2	87.9	
Austria	AT	9 105			21.0	78.4	0.6	93.0	
Belgium	BE	11 743		2.7	97.0	0.4		84.5	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194			1.0	52.8	45.3	0.9	99.9
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	0.7	65.0	28.7	5.7	0.0	78.8	
Croatia	HR	3 851			30.4	45.8	23.7	0.0	95.7
Cyprus	CY	1 419		47.6	37.8	12.7	1.9	81.5	
Czechia	CZ	10 828			9.1	90.9	0.0	93.0	
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987		23.3	76.7	0.0		81.6	
Estonia	EE	1 366		19.0	81.0			81.8	
Finland	FI	5 564		76.9	23.1			78.7	
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017		1.1	69.1	26.7	3.1	88.1	
Germany	DE	83 119		0.0	59.7	40.3	0.0	89.4	
Greece	GR	10 414		2.8	30.0	33.3	33.9	94.3	
Hungary	HU	9 600			29.6	70.4		92.4	
Iceland	IS	388		93.1	6.9			77.8	
Ireland	IE	5 271		97.4	2.6			74.4	
Italy	IT	58 997		2.6	17.0	40.3	40.1	97.7	
Latvia	LV	1 883			100.0	0.0		85.2	
Liechtenstein	LI	40				99.9	0.1	93.3	
Lithuania	LT	2 857			65.6	34.4		89.1	
Luxembourg	LU	661			94.6	5.4		87.2	
Malta	MT	542				98.2	1.8	97.0	
Monaco	MC	39					100.0	102.3	
Montenegro	ME	617			4.3	94.0	1.7	93.8	
Netherlands	NL	17 811		0.6	99.4	0.0		85.1	
North Macedonia	MK	1 830		22.2	67.9	9.4	0.5	83.3	
Norway	NO	5 489		53.4	46.4	0.2		80.2	
Poland	PL	36 754			53.1	46.9	0.0	89.3	
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022		14.6	64.7	20.8	0.0	86.3	
Romania	RO	19 055		20.4	70.9	8.6	0.0	84.3	
San Marino	SM	34				100.0		97.6	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350		8.7	58.7	32.5	0.2	87.5	
Slovakia	SK	5 429			54.2	45.8	0.0	89.4	
Slovenia	SI	2 117			18.5	76.9	4.6	93.8	
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872		10.8	15.5	46.0	27.6	93.8	
Sweden	SE	10 522		51.1	48.9	0.0		80.0	
Switzerland	CH	8 815			3.4	93.4	3.1	95.0	
Türkiye	TR	85 280	11.6	48.2	21.3	16.8	2.0	0.0	75.6
Total		555 254	1.7	14.0	43.1	32.7	8.5	0.0	
			15.7				8.5		87.7
EU-27		443 198	0.0	7.7	48.0	34.5	9.8	0.0	
			7.7				9.8		89.8
Northern Europe		34 055		42.8	54.2	3.0			81.2
Western Europe		86 334		6.8	80.3	12.8	0.0		85.4
Central Europe		165 805		0.0	47.5	52.2	0.3		90.3
Southern Europe		142 589		6.1	23.6	40.6	29.7		94.8
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	7.3	37.8	32.1	19.5	3.3	0.0	79.7
Kosovo	XK	1 709		6.1	73.2	19.8	0.9		86.2
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641		9.3	55.0	35.7	0.0		87.8

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure.

Figure 3.6 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 84 and 96 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For classes above 96 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a sharp decline of population frequency can be seen.

Figure 3.6 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023. The WHO AQG level (60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the green line

The boxplot in Figure 3.7 shows for individual countries the ozone concentrations expressed as peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means to which the population per country was exposed in 2023. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern, south-eastern and central parts of Europe.

Figure 3.7 Population frequency distribution, O₃ peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023. The WHO AQG level (60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the green line.

3.3 Ozone – SOMO35 and SOMO10

SOMO35 is the annually accumulated ozone maximum daily 8-hourly means in excess of 35 ppb (i.e. $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). It is not regulated in the EU air quality directives and there are no associated limit or target values defined. Nevertheless, it is considered by the WHO as a good indicator of human exposure to ozone (WHO, 2013). Comparing the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means versus the SOMO35 for all background stations shows no simple relationship between the two indicators. However, it seems that the TV threshold of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means ($120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is related approximately with a SOMO35 value in the range of $6\,000\text{--}8\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. This comparison motivates a somewhat arbitrarily chosen threshold of $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, in order to facilitate the discussion of the estimated SOMO35 levels in their spatial and temporal context. This threshold is used in this and previous papers (Horálek et al., 2023, and the references cited therein) when dealing with the population exposure estimates.

SOMO10 is the annually accumulated ozone maximum daily 8-hourly means in excess of 10 ppb (i.e. $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). This indicator was introduced due to its link to the health impact assessment, since the WHO recommended using the SOMO10 as an alternative to the SOMO35 when estimating the health impact of ozone (WHO, 2013).

3.3.1 Concentration maps

Maps 3.4 and 3.5 present the final combined map for SOMO35 and SOMO10 in 2023. In the final combined map of SOMO35, the orange areas show values above $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, while the red and dark red areas show values above $8\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. In the case of SOMO10, the boundaries of concentration classes have been chosen quite arbitrary, in order to reflect the concentration distribution of this indicator. In the final combined map of SOMO10, the red and dark red areas show values above $24\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Map 3.4 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO35, 2023

Like in the case of the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means, generally the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe show higher ozone SOMO35 and SOMO10 concentrations than the northern parts. Higher levels of ozone also occur more frequently in mountainous areas south of 50

degrees latitude than in lowlands. In 2023, SOMO35 levels above 6 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ were estimated in large areas of Türkiye, Italy, Spain, Austria, in parts of many Balkan countries and in southern France. SOMO10 levels above 24 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ were mainly found in the same areas.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 maps of the SOMO35 and SOMO10 is about 33% and 12%, respectively, for rural areas and 39% and 14%, respectively, for urban areas (see Annex 3).

Map 3.5 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO10, 2023

Map 3.6 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for the O_3 indicators SOMO35 and SOMO10. Orange to red areas show an increase of those O_3 indicators in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease. Quite similar patterns as in Map 3.2 can be seen.

The largest increases in SOMO35 and SOMO10 levels were recorded in some areas of several Balkan countries, in Poland and in the Baltic states. Increases were also observed in smaller areas of Italy, Spain, and Portugal; in the case of SOMO10, also in Germany, Austria, and the Benelux countries. Areas with the highest decreases were found in Türkiye and some Balkan states, plus, parts of Italy, France, Germany, Austria, Slovakia and Hungary in the case of SOMO35.

Map 3.6 Difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for SOMO35 and SOMO10

3.3.2 Population exposure

SOMO35

Table 3.4 and Figure 3.8 give for SOMO35 the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes. Table 3.4 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area.

It has been estimated that in 2023 about 16% of the considered European population (including Türkiye), and about 17% of the EU-27 population, lived in areas with SOMO35 values above 6 000 µg/m³·d (see above on the motivation of this criterion).

In 2023, like in the previous several years, the northern and western European countries (with the exception of France) have had almost no inhabitants exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. No population has been exposed to concentrations SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d in 11 countries. In Norway, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Czechia, Romania, Germany, Portugal, Serbia, Liechtenstein, Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Switzerland, Kosovo, France, Austria (in ascending order) up to 10% of population was exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. In Montenegro, Türkiye, Albania, Andorra, Slovenia, San Marino, Croatia and Spain, between 13 and 49% of population has been exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. More than half of population has been exposed to concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d in Italy, Greece, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cyprus, Monaco and Malta.

Table 3.4 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator SOMO35, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inths·1000)	Ozone — SOMO10, exposed population, 2023 (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 2 000	2 000- 4 000	4 000- 6 000	6 000- 8 000	8 000- 10 000	> 10 000	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762		1.5	77.1	21.2	0.2		5 676	5 764	-89
Andorra	AD	80		71.0	4.8	14.6	9.6		4 786	4 619	167
Austria	AT	9 105		7.9	83.1	8.5	0.4	0.0	4 982	5 440	-457
Belgium	BE	11 743		95.6	4.4				3 365	3 542	-178
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194			13.6	48.8	34.1	3.4	7 499	5 512	1 987
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	20.4	65.4	12.6	1.6	0.0		2 788	3 170	-382
Croatia	HR	3 851			53.5	26.5	9.9	10.1	6 706	5 733	973
Cyprus	CY	1 419			0.4	95.7	4.0		7 194	6 730	464
Czechia	CZ	10 828		2.8	97.0	0.2			4 673	5 059	-385
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	10.3	89.4	0.3				2 827	2 853	-26
Estonia	EE	1 366	1.1	98.9	0.0				2 360	2 138	222
Finland	FI	5 564	55.9	44.1					1 962	1 872	91
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	0.1	57.6	34.2	8.0	0.1	0.0	4 177	4 513	-336
Germany	DE	83 119		51.9	47.7	0.3	0.0		4 104	4 447	-343
Greece	GR	10 414		2.5	21.7	55.9	12.6	7.3	7 111	6 883	228
Hungary	HU	9 600		18.7	81.3	0.0			4 727	4 877	-151
Iceland	IS	388	78.0	21.8	0.2				1 907	1 829	77
Ireland	IE	5 271	79.8	20.2					1 659	2 121	-462
Italy	IT	58 997	0.5	8.6	37.6	39.0	14.3	0.0	6 194	6 452	-257
Latvia	LV	1 883		99.9	0.1				2 873	2 198	675
Liechtenstein	LI	40			98.5	1.4	0.1		4 925	5 573	-648
Lithuania	LT	2 857		55.9	44.1				3 979	2 599	1 380
Luxembourg	LU	661		80.2	19.8				3 888	3 894	-6
Malta	MT	542				86.1	13.9		7 576	6 241	1 335
Monaco	MC	39				100.0			7 353	7 204	149
Montenegro	ME	617		17.0	70.3	12.8	0.0		5 051	5 342	-291
Netherlands	NL	17 811		99.7	0.3				3 356	3 235	121
North Macedonia	MK	1 830		71.5	24.5	4.0	0.1		3 875	4 020	-146
Norway	NO	5 489	29.9	69.5	0.6	0.0			2 255	2 361	-105
Poland	PL	36 754		44.2	55.8	0.0	0.0		4 063	3 972	91
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022		34.8	64.3	0.9	0.0		4 223	3 843	380
Romania	RO	19 055	4.6	76.6	18.5	0.3	0.0		3 367	3 300	67
San Marino	SM	34			55.2	44.8			5 889	5 785	104
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	1.3	58.0	38.2	2.5	0.0		3 919	4 142	-224
Slovakia	SK	5 429		45.8	54.1	0.1	0.0		4 204	4 730	-526
Slovenia	SI	2 117		0.9	71.9	26.9	0.3		5 542	5 802	-260
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	1.4	15.4	34.7	48.3	0.2		5 612	5 191	421
Sweden	SE	10 522	46.2	53.8	0.0				2 168	2 612	-445
Switzerland	CH	8 815		0.1	93.7	5.6	0.6	0.0	5 292	5 749	-456
Türkiye	TR	85 280	23.8	36.4	26.6	11.4	1.6	0.3	3 491	4 931	-1 440
Total		560 167	6.6	40.5	37.0	13.2	2.4	0.3	4 346	4 635	-289
EU-27			3.5	41.9	38.2	13.8	2.4	0.3	4 488	4 593	-105
		443 198	45.3			16.5					
Northern Europe		34 055	31.0	65.1	3.9	0.0			2 460	2 437	22
Western Europe		86 334	4.6	76.3	18.9	0.3	0.0	0.0	3 554	3 776	-222
Central Europe		165 805		39.2	59.5	1.3	0.1	0.0	4 297	4 543	-246
Southern Europe		142 589	0.7	13.1	37.8	40.6	7.2	0.6	5 864	5 822	42
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	16.8	43.0	27.2	10.1	2.2	0.6	3 732	4 547	-815
Kosovo	XK	1 709		62.1	29.9	8.0	0.0		4 085	4 341	-256
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	1.6	57.0	40.4	1.1	0.0		3 876	4 095	-219

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022.

Figure 3.8 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator SOMO35 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), 2023

In 2023, the population-weighted ozone concentration in terms of SOMO35 for the total mapped area was estimated to be $4\,346 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, i.e. $289 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ lower than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean SOMO35 concentration. For the EU-27, it was $4\,488 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, i.e. $105 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ lower than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean SOMO35 concentration. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Türkiye ($1\,440 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), while the highest increase was estimated in Bosnia and Herzegovina ($1\,987 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$).

Figure 3.9 shows, for the whole mapped area, the frequency distribution of SOMO35 for population exposure classes of $250 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. The highest frequencies are found for classes between $3\,000$ and $5\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. One can see a steep decline of population frequency for exposure classes between $5\,000$ and $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ and a continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes above $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Figure 3.9 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone indicator SOMO35, 2023

Figure 3.10 shows for individual countries the ozone indicator SOMO35 to which the population was exposed in 2023. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 3.10 Ozone concentrations expressed as indicator SOMO35 to which the population per country was exposed in 2023

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

SOMO10

Figure 3.11 and Table 3.5 give for SOMO10 the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area. Table 3.5 also presents the population-weighted concentration.

Figure 3.11 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator SOMO10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), 2023

Table 3.5 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator SOMO10, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs·1000)	Ozone — SOMO10, exposed population, 2023 (%)					Population-weighted concentration			
			< 15 000	15 000-18 000	18 000-21 000	21 000-24 000	24 000-27 000	> 27 000	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762		2.2	47.3	47.4	3.1		21 290	21 309	-19
Andorra	AD	80			72.4	8.3	13.4	5.9	21 002	19 042	1 960
Austria	AT	9 105		6.9	69.4	21.2	2.4	0.1	20 268	20 014	254
Belgium	BE	11 743		17.4	82.0	0.6			18 551	17 471	1 079
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194			8.8	72.7	18.5	0.0	22 711	19 997	2 714
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	50.0	34.1	12.2	3.6	0.2	0.0	15 860	16 329	-469
Croatia	HR	3 851			39.7	38.1	22.1	0.1	22 127	20 578	1 549
Cyprus	CY	1 419			80.6	19.1	0.2		20 907	21 633	-726
Czechia	CZ	10 828			87.0	13.0	0.0		20 103	19 743	360
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987		29.4	70.5	0.0			18 621	18 439	182
Estonia	EE	1 366		91.5	8.5				17 326	16 886	441
Finland	FI	5 564		97.9	2.1				16 853	16 307	546
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017			78.1	21.2	0.7	0.0	20 237	19 823	414
Germany	DE	83 119		3.7	90.9	5.4	0.0		19 392	18 587	805
Greece	GR	10 414	0.5	3.0	16.7	47.9	25.1	6.8	23 010	22 424	586
Hungary	HU	9 600		5.6	89.3	5.1			19 535	18 962	573
Iceland	IS	388		89.9	9.9	0.2			17 300	16 898	402
Ireland	IE	5 271		67.6	32.4				17 013	17 527	-515
Italy	IT	58 997		1.5	40.6	52.0	5.8	0.0	21 289	21 139	149
Latvia	LV	1 883		65.0	35.0				17 497	16 518	980
Liechtenstein	LI	40			96.2	3.7	0.1		19 596	19 563	33
Lithuania	LT	2 857		0.1	99.9				19 129	16 962	2 167
Luxembourg	LU	661			97.7	2.3			19 407	18 132	1 275
Malta	MT	542					99.8	0.2	25 705	24 252	1 453
Monaco	MC	39				100.0			24 000	23 388	612
Montenegro	ME	617		15.7	60.4	22.6	1.3		19 984	20 414	-430
Netherlands	NL	17 811		12.0	87.9	0.1			18 781	17 349	1 432
North Macedonia	MK	1 830		68.0	23.7	7.7	0.6	0.0	17 701	17 572	128
Norway	NO	5 489		63.5	36.3	0.2			17 669	17 206	463
Poland	PL	36 754		11.3	87.9	0.8	0.0		18 927	18 145	781
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022		0.5	56.6	42.8	0.1		20 414	19 236	1 179
Romania	RO	19 055	2.8	68.3	24.4	4.5	0.1		17 651	17 037	614
San Marino	SM	34			51.9	48.1			21 209	20 441	768
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350		61.4	28.9	9.5	0.2		17 986	17 685	301
Slovakia	SK	5 429		30.1	65.2	4.7	0.0		19 096	19 197	-101
Slovenia	SI	2 117		0.8	57.4	38.8	3.0	0.0	20 722	20 604	118
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872		4.3	18.8	63.6	13.3	0.0	22 106	21 255	852
Sweden	SE	10 522		78.4	21.6	0.0			17 503	17 704	-201
Switzerland	CH	8 815			83.8	14.8	1.3	0.1	20 688	20 213	475
Türkiye	TR	85 280	55.0	24.3	13.6	6.4	0.7	0.0	14 631	17 563	-2 932
Total		560 167	8.8	15.2	53.8	19.2	2.8	0.2	19 095	19 033	62
EU-27			0.9	12.2	61.8	21.6	3.3	0.2	19 892	19 300	592
		443 198	13.1				25.0				
Northern Europe		34 055		64.2	35.8	0.0			17 739	17 336	404
Western Europe		86 334		8.7	86.1	5.1	0.1	0.0	19 229	18 504	725
Central Europe		165 805		6.1	87.1	6.5	0.2	0.0	19 459	18 780	679
Southern Europe		142 589	0.0	2.2	32.5	55.5	9.2	0.5	21 688	21 222	466
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	37.6	32.7	18.0	9.9	1.7	0.0	16 048	17 672	-1 624
Kosovo	XK	1 709		73.9	13.5	12.2	0.5		17 686	18 220	-534
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641		58.2	32.9	8.8	0.2		18 063	17 557	506

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and 5-year mean 2018-2022.

Figure 3.12 shows the population frequency distribution of SOMO10 for population exposure classes of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. The graph shows the highest frequencies for classes between 16 000 and 23 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Figure 3.12 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone indicator SOMO10, 2023

Figure 3.13 shows for individual countries the ozone indicator SOMO10 to which the population was exposed in 2023. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 3.13 Ozone concentrations expressed as indicator SOMO10 to which the population per country was exposed in 2023

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

3.4 Ozone – AOT40 vegetation and AOT40 forests

In the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) a target value (TV) and a long-term objective (LTO) for the protection of vegetation from high ozone concentrations accumulated during the growing season have been defined. TV and LTO are specified using “accumulated ozone exposure over a threshold of 40 parts per billion” (AOT40). This is calculated as a sum of the difference between hourly concentrations greater than 40 ppb (i.e. $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and 40 ppb, using only observations between 08:00 and 20:00 Central European Time (CET) each day, calculated over three months from 1 May to 31 July. The TV is $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ (averaged over five years) and the LTO is $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$.

Note that the term “vegetation” as used in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) is not further defined. Nevertheless, the TV used in the directive is quite similar as the critical level used in the Mapping Manual (CLRTAP, 2024) for “agricultural crops” (although the definitions of AOT40 by the EU and the CLRTAP are slightly different), so the term vegetation in the Air Quality Directive has been interpreted as primarily agricultural crops. Therefore, the exposure of agricultural crops has been evaluated here based on the AOT40 for vegetation as defined in the Air Quality Directive and the agricultural areas, defined as the CORINE Land Cover level-1 class 2 Agricultural areas (encompassing the level-2 classes 2.1 Arable land, 2.2 Permanent crops, 2.3 Pastures and 2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas), see Annex 2 Section A2.3. Note that in addition to these agricultural areas there are several other CLC classes that could be considered “vegetation”, namely level-2 classes 1.4 Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas (encompassing the level-3 classes 1.4.1 Green urban areas and 1.4.2 Sport and leisure facilities), 3.1 Forests (see below) and 3.2 Scrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations. These other CLC classes have not been considered (apart from forests, see below).

Next to the AOT40 for vegetation protection, the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) defines also the AOT40 for forest protection, which is calculated similarly as the AOT40 for vegetation, but is summed over six months from 1 April to 30 September. For AOT40 for forests there is no TV defined in the Air Quality Directive. However, there is a critical level (CL) established by the CLRTAP, see CLRTAP (2024). This critical level is set at $10\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$. Although CLRTAP (2024) calculates the AOT40 indicators somewhat differently (e.g. it uses the ozone concentration corrected at canopy height), this CL level is further used for the AOT40 for forests calculated according to the EC (2008).

For the exposure of forests evaluation, the CLC level-2 class 3.1 Forests has been used.

The ecosystem based accumulative ozone indicators described in this section are specifically prepared for calculation of the EEA indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2025b). For the estimation of the vegetation and forested area exposure to accumulated ozone, the maps in this section are created on a grid of 2 km resolution. The exposure frequency distribution outcomes are based on the overlay with the 100 m grid resolution of the CLC2018 land cover classes.

3.4.1 Concentration maps

The interpolated maps of AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests are applicable for rural areas only. Map 3.7 presents the final map of AOT40 for vegetation in 2023. Note that in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) the TV is actually defined as $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ averaged over 5 years. Here both 2023 data and 5-year mean (2019-2023) are presented (5-year mean for AOT40 for vegetation is presented for the first time in this report). Data for the current calendar year (i.e. 2023) are evaluated against what it is called the target value threshold, an AOT40 of $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ for just one year.

Map 3.7 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation, rural map, 2023 (left) and 5-year mean 2019-2023 (right)

The areas in the map with AOT40 for vegetation in 2023 above the TV threshold of 18 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ are marked in red and dark red. The areas below the long-term objective (LTO) are marked in green. AOT40 levels above the TV threshold for vegetation occur specifically in southern and south-eastern of Europe (Italy, parts of Spain, France and parts of the Balkan countries and Türkiye) and also in central Europe (parts of Switzerland, Germany, Austria, Slovenia, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland and Hungary). The highest levels (dark red) were estimated, similarly to previous years, in the north of Italy, in the south-west of Türkiye and in Cyprus. Based on the 5-year mean of AOT40 for vegetation, the situation is quite similar in terms of the spatial distribution of AOT40 values, a bit worse in Türkiye and the Balkans. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of the AOT40 for vegetation is about 36% (Annex 3, Section A3.3).

Map 3.8 presents the final map of AOT40 for forests in 2023. The areas in the map with concentrations below the critical level (CL) defined by CLRTAP (2024) are marked in green. One can see large forested areas exceeding this level in most of Europe, with the exception of parts of some northern countries and Ireland. The highest values of the AOT40 for forests in 2023 were found mainly in southern Europe (Spain, south of France, parts of the Balkan states, the Po Valley and Cyprus) and Türkiye. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of the AOT40 for forests is about 30% (Annex 3, Section A3.3).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the AOT40 maps including the AOT40 values based on the actual rural background measurement data at stations are presented in Maps A4.8 and A4.9 of Annex 4.

Map 3.8 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, rural map, 2023

Map 3.9 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for AOT40 for vegetation and for AOT40 for forests. Orange to red areas show an increase of AOT40 in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease.

Map 3.9 Difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for ozone indicators, AOT40 for vegetation (left) and AOT40 for forests (right)

The most notable increases in AOT40 for vegetation were recorded in southern Spain, eastern France, parts of Germany and northern Europe. In northern Europe, specifically in the Baltic states, an increase also in AOT40 for forests was also observed. Elsewhere, a decrease in AOT40 has been observed across various parts throughout the mapped area, with the most notable decrease in Türkiye, the Balkan states, Italy and parts of France and Spain. Regarding AOT40 levels for forests, a noticeable decline is observed in similar areas, i.e. in Türkiye, the Balkan states, Italy and parts of Spain and most of France and Germany.

3.4.2 Vegetation exposure

Agricultural crops

The rural map with the ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation has been combined with the land cover CLC2018 map. Following a similar procedure as described in Horálek et al. (2007), the exposure of agricultural areas (as defined above) has been calculated at the country-level.

Tables 3.6 and 3.7 give the absolute and relative agricultural area in 2023 and for the 5-year mean (2013-2023) for each country and for five European regions where ozone concentrations are above the target value (TV) threshold and the long-term objective (LTO) for the protection of vegetation as defined in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). The frequency distribution of the agricultural area over some exposure classes per country is presented as well.

Table 3.6 illustrates that in 2023, 12% of all European agricultural land including Türkiye was exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold of 18 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$. For the area for the EU-27, it was also 12%. None of the agricultural area presents ozone levels in excess of the TV in 17 countries. Agricultural areas with ozone concentrations above TV threshold covered less than 25% in Portugal, Slovakia, Poland, Hungary North Macedonia, Montenegro, Kosovo, France, Albania, Liechtenstein, Czechia, Croatia, San Marino, Slovenia, Türkiye, Austria, Greece, Germany (in ascending order). In Spain, Italy and Switzerland, between 26% and 50% of agricultural area has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold. The largest proportion of the agricultural area exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold is Cyprus, Andorra and Malta (from 54% up to 100%).

Considering the LTO of 6 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, the total European area (including Türkiye) in excess has been 91%. For the area for the EU-27, it has been 94%. In 2023, values of the AOT40 for vegetation above the LTO have occurred in all countries with the exception of Iceland and Ireland. Fewer than 50% of the areas with values above the LTO have occurred in Finland (17%) and Norway (27%). In the remaining countries, the agricultural area exposed above the LTO in 2023 has been between 75% and 100%. In Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, San Marino, Serbia, Slovenia, Switzerland, the entire agriculture area was exposed to AOT40 levels above the LTO for protection of vegetation.

In 2023, the agricultural-weighted ozone concentration of vegetation-related AOT40 for the total mapped area was estimated to be 12 103 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 2 049 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ lower than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean. For the EU-27 area, it was estimated to be 12 407 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 538 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ lower than the 5-year 2019-2023 mean. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Türkiye (10 508 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$), while the highest increase was estimated in Latvia (3 838 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, respectively).

Table 3.6 Agricultural area exposure and agricultural-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation, 2023

Country	Agricultural area, 2023						Percentage of agricultural area (%)					Agricultural-weighted conc.		
	Total area	> LTO (6 000 µg/m ³ ·h)		> TV threshold (18 000 µg/m ³ ·h)		< 6 000	6 000- 12 000	12 000- 18 000	18 000- 27 000	> 27 000	2023	5-year mean	Diff.	
	(km ²)	(km ²)	(%)	(km ²)	(%)		(µg/m ³ ·h)							
Albania	8 017	8 017	100.0	416	5.2		21.4	73.5	5.2		14 254	16 602	-2 347	
Andorra	13	13	100.0	9	64.8			35.2	64.8		19 607			
Austria	26 827	26 827	100.0	4 731	17.6		0.4	81.9	17.6	0.0	16 601	17 413	-812	
Belgium	17 473	17 473	100.0				21.9	78.1			13 092	11 781	1 312	
Bosnia-Herzegovina	17 023	17 011	99.9			0.1	89.3	10.7			10 288	10 857	-570	
Bulgaria	57 390	51 940	90.5			9.5	87.8	2.7			8 330	11 538	-3 209	
Croatia	22 168	22 168	100.0	1 346	6.1		44.5	49.5	6.1		12 543	13 450	-907	
Cyprus	4 291	4 291	100.0	2 322	54.1			45.9	54.1		18 368	24 179	-5 811	
Czechia	44 784	44 784	100.0	2 524	5.6			94.4	5.6		16 229	16 883	-654	
Denmark (incl. Faroes)	31 236	31 177	99.8			0.2	99.8				7 889	6 977	913	
Estonia	14 252	14 182	99.5			0.5	99.5				6 893	4 101	2 792	
Finland	27 505	4 791	17.4			82.6	17.4				4 208	3 050	1 158	
France	323 377	321 366	99.4	5 294	1.6	0.6	61.3	36.4	1.6	0.0	11 330	11 612	-282	
Germany	204 463	204 463	100.0	51 049	25.0		32.6	42.4	25.0		14 385	14 096	289	
Greece	50 052	50 019	99.9	9 994	20.0	0.1	23.6	56.4	17.1	2.9	15 028	19 830	-4 803	
Hungary	60 390	60 390	100.0	23	0.0		25.1	74.9	0.0		13 201	15 843	-2 642	
Iceland	2 518	0	0.0			100.0	0.0				943	1 102	-158	
Ireland	46 756	0	0.0			100.0	0.0				2 116	2 932	-816	
Italy	155 718	155 673	100.0	59 443	38.2	0.0	23.7	38.1	24.0	14.2	17 674	20 868	-3 194	
Latvia	25 532	25 532	100.0				100.0				8 039	4 201	3 838	
Liechtenstein	37	37	100.0	2	5.6			94.4	5.6		16 210	17 648	-1 438	
Lithuania	38 155	38 155	100.0				100.0				9 203	5 465	3 738	
Luxembourg	1 351	1 351	100.0					100.0			16 134	13 843	2 291	
Malta	125	125	100.0	125	100.0				100.0		20 597	19 983	614	
Monaco														
Montenegro	2 243	2 236	99.7	5	0.2	0.3	56.9	42.6	0.2		11 762	13 547	-1 784	
Netherlands	23 644	23 644	100.0				69.8	30.2			11 021	9 399	1 622	
North Macedonia	9 146	9 146	100.0	15	0.2		58.2	41.6	0.2		11 731	15 892	-4 161	
Norway	15 637	4 237	27.1			72.9	27.1	0.0			4 622	3 590	1 032	
Poland	183 268	183 268	100.0	50	0.0		42.6	57.4	0.0		12 482	11 953	529	
Portugal	42 566	41 800	98.2	0	0.0	1.8	60.7	37.5	0.0		11 206	11 109	97	
Romania	135 279	122 047	90.2			9.8	85.3	4.9			8 380	10 182	-1 802	
San Marino	42	42	100.0	5	11.9			88.1	11.9		17 151	19 108	-1 957	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	46 768	46 768	100.0	18	0.0		39.3	60.6	0.0		12 249	14 078	-1 829	
Slovakia	23 100	23 090	100.0	3	0.0	0.0	31.1	68.9	0.0		13 015	14 890	-1 875	
Slovenia	6 986	6 986	100.0	1 010	14.4		2.4	83.2	14.4	0.0	15 911	16 878	-967	
Spain	241 014	231 836	96.2	78 106	32.4	3.8	12.1	51.7	32.4	0.0	15 676	15 744	-67	
Sweden	39 035	34 395	88.1			11.9	88.1				7 185	5 679	1 506	
Switzerland	11 359	11 359	100.0	5 466	48.1		0.6	51.2	48.0	0.1	17 937	18 575	-638	
Türkiye	339 984	255 707	75.2	54 998	16.2	24.8	39.6	19.4	13.6	2.5	10 717	21 225	-10 508	
Total	2 299 526	2 096 348	91.2	276 952	12.0	8.8	43.2	35.9	10.6	1.4	12 103	14 153	-2 049	
EU-27	1 846 681	1 741 774	94.3	216 019	11.7	5.7	44.0	38.6	10.4	1.3	12 407	12 945	-538	
Northern Europe	193 869	152 469	78.6			21.4	78.6	0.0			7 076	4 934	2 142	
Western Europe	346 009	298 273	86.2	1 753	0.5	13.8	50.5	35.1	0.5		10 226	10 059	167	
Central Europe	561 215	561 205	100.0	64 858	11.6	0.0	29.8	58.6	11.6	0.0	13 924	14 123	-199	
Southern Europe	560 414	549 360	98.0	153 544	27.4	2.0	26.3	44.3	23.2	4.2	15 306	16 907	-1 602	
South-Eastern Europe	638 018	535 040	83.9	56 797	8.9	16.1	55.2	19.8	7.5	1.4	10 234	16 780	-6 546	
Kosovo	4 167	4 167	100.0	18	0.4		18.3	81.2	0.4		13 506	16 119	-2 613	
Serbia (without Kosovo)	42 601	42 601	100.0				41.4	58.6			12 126	13 878	-1 752	

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022.

Relating to 5-year mean 2019-2023 (Table 3.7), 16% of all European agricultural land including Türkiye has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV of 18 000 µg/m³·h. For the area for the EU-27, it was 10%. None of the agricultural area presents ozone levels in excess of the TV in 17 countries. Agricultural areas with ozone concentrations above the TV covered less than 25% in Serbia, Portugal, Slovakia, Czechia, Montenegro, Germany, Hungary, France, Austria, Liechtenstein, Croatia, North Macedonia, Kosovo. Albania, Slovenia and Spain (in ascending order). In Switzerland, Andorra, Greece and Italy, between 27% and 50% of agricultural area has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV. The largest proportion of the agricultural area exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV is Türkiye, Malta, San Marino and Cyprus (from 54% up to 100%).

Table 3.7 Agricultural area exposure and agricultural-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation, 5-year mean (2019-2023)

Country	Agricultural area, 2019-2023			Percentage of agricultural area (%)					Agricultural-weighted conc.
	Total area	> TV	<	6 000-	12 000-	18 000-	> 27 000	($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)	
	(km^2)	(18 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)	6 000	12 000	18 000	27 000		2019-2023	
Albania	8 017	1200	15.0		2.8	82.2	15.0	15 839	
Andorra	13	6	44.7			55.3	44.7	17 290	
Austria	26 827	1074	4.0		0.6	95.4	4.0	16 087	
Belgium	17 473				91.6	8.4		10 464	
Bosnia-Herzegovina	17 023			0.5	89.3	10.3		9 975	
Bulgaria	57 390				75.5	24.5		10 609	
Croatia	22 168	1545	7.0		58.2	34.8	7.0	12 313	
Cyprus	4 291	4291	100.0				91.9	23 500	
Czechia	44 784	52	0.1		0.2	99.7	0.1	15 002	
Denmark (incl. Faroes)	31 236			66.4	33.6			5 749	
Estonia	14 251			98.3	1.7			4 435	
Finland	27 504			100.0				2 771	
France	323 377	10839	3.4	0.4	78.1	18.2	3.3	10 579	
Germany	204 463	978	0.5	0.2	44.0	55.3	0.5	12 551	
Greece	50 051	22801	45.6		5.9	48.5	42.5	17 870	
Hungary	60 387	1408	2.3		12.2	85.5	2.3	14 290	
Iceland	2 517			100.0				681	
Ireland	46 756			100.0				2 104	
Italy	155 718	77144	49.5		2.6	47.9	30.7	20 284	
Latvia	25 530			99.4	0.6			4 545	
Liechtenstein	37	2	5.5			94.5	5.5	15 711	
Lithuania	38 148			76.3	23.7			5 579	
Luxembourg	1 351				12.3	87.7		12 622	
Malta	125	70	56.3			43.7	56.3	19 842	
Monaco									
Montenegro	2 243	10	0.5		26.7	72.9	0.5	13 018	
Netherlands	23 644			0.1	99.6	0.3		8 698	
North Macedonia	9 146	805	8.8		17.4	73.8	8.8	14 647	
Norway	15 636			96.3	3.7			2 970	
Poland	183 258				64.3	35.7		10 998	
Portugal	42 566	1	0.0	2.4	59.7	37.9	0.0	11 374	
Romania	135 270			1.7	85.9	12.4		9 495	
San Marino	42	30	71.1			28.9	71.1	18 401	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	46 768	477	1.0		21.1	77.9	1.0	13 325	
Slovakia	23 100	3	0.0		30.9	69.1	0.0	13 385	
Slovenia	6 986	1189	17.0		1.7	81.3	17.0	16 131	
Spain	241 014	55388	23.0	4.4	8.7	63.9	23.0	15 344	
Sweden	39 035			73.7	26.3			4 909	
Switzerland	11 359	3065	27.0		0.1	72.9	26.6	17 367	
Türkiye	339 966	183555	54.0	1.8	9.8	34.4	44.7	18 616	
Total	2 299 474	365935	15.9	10.1	36.2	37.8	13.2	2.7	13 002
EU-27	1 846 648	176785	9.6	11.3	41.8	37.4	7.9	1.7	12 043
Northern Europe	193 857			84.1	15.9			4 579	
Western Europe	346 009	1728	0.5	13.7	71.4	14.4	0.5	9 046	
Central Europe	561 202	7772	1.4	0.1	39.7	58.8	1.4	0.0	12 772
Southern Europe	560 414	168844	30.1	2.2	17.6	50.1	24.6	5.6	16 300
South-Eastern Europe	637 992	187592	29.4	1.3	36.6	32.7	24.5	4.9	15 013
Kosovo	4 167	477	11.4		4.2	84.3	11.4	15 754	
Serbia (without Kosovo)	42 601	0	0.0		22.8	77.2	0.0	13 087	

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure.

In 2023, the agricultural-weighted ozone concentration of vegetation-related AOT40 (5-year mean) for the total mapped area was estimated to be 13 002 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$. For the EU-27 area, it was estimated to be 12 043 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$.

Forests

The rural map with ozone indicator AOT40 for forests was combined with the land cover CLC2018 map. Following a similar procedure as described in Horálek et al. (2007), the exposure of forest areas (as defined above) has been calculated for each country, for the same five European regions as for crops and for Europe as a whole. Table 3.8 gives the absolute and relative forest area where the critical level (CL) set at 10 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, the same level as defined in CLRTAP (2024), and the value 20 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ (which is equal to the earlier used reporting value, RV, as was defined in the repealed ozone directive 2002/3/EC, EC, 2002) are exceeded. Next to the forest area in exceedance, the table presents the frequency distribution of the forest area over some exposure classes.

The CL was exceeded in 2023 at 73% of all European forested area including Türkiye. For the area of the EU-27 it was exceeded at about 74%. As in previous years, most countries continue to have in 2023 the whole or considerable forest areas in excess of the CL. In 2023, there were only two countries with almost no CL exceedance (Iceland and Ireland). Up to 50% of the areas with values above the CL have occurred in Finland, Norway and Sweden. In the remaining countries, the CL for AOT40 was exceeded in more than 90% of the area of the respective country. In 27 countries, the entire forested area was exposed to AOT40 levels above the CL for forests.

In 2023, the forest-weighted ozone concentration of forest-related AOT40 for the total mapped area was estimated to be 18 143 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 2 176 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ less than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean. For the EU-27 area, it was estimated to be 17 993 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 1 445 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ less than the 5-year 2018-2022 mean. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Türkiye (12 395 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$), while the highest increase was estimated in Lithuania (4 553 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$).

In this context, it should be mentioned that the AOT40 indicator is not the best proxy for vegetation damage assessment. AOT40 does not take into account plant physiological control of ozone absorbed doses, which is taken into account in the POD (i.e. Phytotoxic Ozone Dose) indicators, as discussed in Section 3.5. POD indicators are known to be more related with ozone effects on plant growth than ambient air ozone concentrations alone. The AOT40 does not take into account the influence of meteorological conditions on growing season timing. Growing season's start and end dates can change across Europe, and between years for a given site, depending on factors such as air temperature, solar radiation, photoperiod or rainfall. High temperature and dry weather favouring ozone pollution cause a reduction of ozone absorbed doses by plants due to plant physiological response to drought (i.e. the vegetation closes its stomata protecting itself from the exposure to ozone). However, plants may still be sensitive to ozone in such weather conditions, as illustrated by foliar injury records in Aleppo pine stands growing in southern France (CLRTAP, 2016) or controlled experimental results (e.g. Alonso et al., 2014).

Table 3.8 Forested area exposure and forest-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, 2023

Country	Forested area						Percentage of forested area [%]					Forest-weighted conc. ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)		
	Total area (km^2)	> CL ($10\,000\ \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)		> RV ($20\,000\ \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)		< 10 000 (%)	10 000- 20 000	20 000- 30 000	30 000- 50 000	> 50 000	2023	5-year mean	Diff.	
		(km^2)	(%)	(km^2)	(%)		($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)	($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)	($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)	($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$)				
Albania	7 104	7 104	100.0	7 031	99.0		1.0	50.5	48.4	0.0	29 921	34 999	-5 078	
Andorra	128	128	100.0	128	100.0	0.0	0.0		14.1	85.9	34 970			
Austria	36 667	36 667	100.0	36 135	98.5		1.5	77.3	21.2		27 608	30 799	-3 190	
Belgium	6 089	6 089	100.0	3 063	50.3		49.7	50.3			20 196	22 794	-2 598	
Bosnia-Herzegovina	23 911	23 911	100.0	19 205	80.3		19.7	77.3	3.0		23 160	23 062	97	
Bulgaria	34 675	34 636	99.9	23 084	66.6	0.1	33.3	59.8	6.8		22 195	27 419	-5 224	
Croatia	19 734	19 734	100.0	17 995	91.2		8.8	75.1	16.1		25 163	27 103	-1 940	
Cyprus	1 458	1 458	100.0	1 458	100.0					0.7	41 404	48 212	-6 808	
Czechia	25 867	25 867	100.0	25 867	100.0			94.0	6.0		27 189	30 280	-3 091	
Denmark (incl. Faroes)	3 747	3 707	98.9			1.1	98.9				13 280	12 880	400	
Estonia	21 080	20 143	95.6			4.4	95.6				10 962	7 871	3 092	
Finland	211 668	3 040	1.4			98.6	1.4				6 079	5 742	337	
France	143 376	142 897	99.7	74 278	51.8	0.3	47.9	37.7	14.0	0.1	21 897	25 651	-3 754	
Germany	108 031	108 030	100.0	84 900	78.6	0.0	21.4	71.5	7.1		24 096	27 670	-3 574	
Greece	26 122	26 122	100.0	25 070	96.0		4.0	53.0	41.6	1.4	29 647	37 853	-8 206	
Hungary	17 407	17 407	100.0	15 474	88.9		11.1	86.9	2.0		24 260	29 099	-4 839	
Iceland	537	3	0.5			99.5	0.5				4 215	4 778	-563	
Ireland	4 510	11	0.2			99.8	0.2				4 857	6 611	-1 754	
Italy	79 052	79 052	100.0	77 836	98.5		1.5	41.2	51.9	5.4	33 204	37 591	-4 388	
Latvia	24 261	24 261	100.0				100.0				12 772	8 558	4 214	
Liechtenstein	79	79	100.0	79	99.4		0.6	34.5	65.0		31 505	35 937	-4 432	
Lithuania	19 455	19 455	100.0				100.0				15 546	10 993	4 553	
Luxembourg	937	937	100.0	937	100.0			100.0			22 415	25 465	-3 050	
Malta	2	2	100.0	2	100.0				100.0		41 655	43 548	-1 893	
Monaco	1	1	100.0	1	100.0					100.0	52 516	45 236	7 280	
Montenegro	5 777	5 780	100.0	5 513	95.4		4.6	75.1	20.3		26 526	30 080	-3 555	
Netherlands	3 118	3 115	99.9	137	4.4	0.1	95.5	4.4			17 660	17 794	-134	
North Macedonia	8 144	8 144	100.0	8 083	99.3		0.7	68.9	30.4		28 147	34 703	-6 557	
Norway	103 494	43 042	41.6	102	0.1	58.4	41.5	0.1			9 742	9 498	244	
Poland	96 966	96 966	100.0	54 203	55.9		44.1	55.4	0.5		20 865	21 583	-718	
Portugal	16 512	16 368	99.1	8 716	52.8	0.9	46.3	52.7	0.1		19 657	21 956	-2 299	
Romania	71 273	71 033	99.7	23 867	33.5	0.3	66.2	33.2	0.3		18 453	20 766	-2 313	
San Marino	6	6	100.0	6	100.0				100.0		35 064	35 121	-57	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	27 211	27 211	100.0	26 286	96.6		3.4	86.4	10.2		25 543	28 656	-3 113	
Slovakia	20 484	20 484	100.0	16 016	78.2		21.8	76.0	2.2		23 067	26 719	-3 652	
Slovenia	11 441	11 441	100.0	11 331	99.0		1.0	61.3	37.7		28 918	32 708	-3 790	
Spain	107 927	101 906	94.4	85 131	78.9	5.6	15.5	44.0	34.9	0.0	25 826	26 200	-374	
Sweden	261 757	118 467	45.3	0	0.0	54.7	45.3	0.0			9 382	8 845	537	
Switzerland	11 850	11 850	100.0	11 643	98.3		1.7	58.4	39.2	0.7	29 716	35 917	-6 202	
Türkiye	114 886	91 315	79.5	60 638	52.8	20.5	26.7	27.8	23.1	1.9	21 685	34 080	-12 395	
Total	1 676 742	1 227 868	73.2	724 217	43.2	26.8	30.0	32.0	10.8	0.4	18 143	20 319	-2 176	
EU-27	1 373 615	1 009 295	73.5	585 501	42.6	26.5	30.9	32.1	10.1	0.3	17 993	19 439	-1 445	
Northern Europe	645 997	232 117	35.9	102	0.0	64.1	35.9	0.0			8 740	7 975	765	
Western Europe	104 660	99 683	95.2	43 083	41.2	4.8	54.1	36.6	4.6		19 394	23 109	-3 715	
Central Europe	328 793	328 792	100.0	255 649	77.8	0.0	22.2	69.4	8.3	0.0	24 095	26 920	-2 825	
Southern Europe	284 577	278 409	97.8	233 680	82.1	2.2	15.7	43.1	37.4	1.7	27 785	30 681	-2 896	
South-Eastern Europe	312 715	288 867	92.4	191 703	61.3	7.6	31.1	46.9	13.7	0.7	22 115	28 515	-6 400	
Kosovo	4 316	4 316	100.0	4 312	99.9		0.1	59.2	40.7		29 519	33 871	-4 352	
Serbia (without Kosovo)	22 894	22 894	100.0	21 974	96.0		4.0	91.5	4.5		24 793	27 673	-2 880	

Note: The percentage value “0.0” indicates that an exposed forested area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no forested area in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022.

3.5 Ozone – Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_y) for crops and forest trees

Ozone is generally recognized to be the most relevant pollutant for plants. Visible injury, reduction in growth, changes in biomass partitioning, or a higher susceptibility to pathogen attack can be the effect of ozone influence (Krupa et al., 2000). As mentioned above, scientific evidence suggests that observed effects of ozone on vegetation are more strongly related to the uptake of ozone through the stomatal leaf pores into the leaf interior (stomatal flux) than to the concentration in the atmosphere around the plants (Reich, 1987; Ashmore et al., 2004; Mills et al., 2011).

The cumulative stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) through the stomata of leaves found at the top of the canopy are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient ozone concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to ozone. The stomatal conductance has been calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model (Emberson et al., 2000a) based on Jarvis (1976) as a

function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a single leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density, PPFD), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

POD_Y (Phytotoxic Ozone Dose) is the accumulated plant uptake (flux) of ozone above a threshold of Y during a specified time or growth period. The flux-based POD_Y metrics are preferred in risk assessment over the concentration-based AOT40 exposure index. AOT40 accounts for the ambient ozone concentration and is therefore biologically less relevant for ozone impact assessment than POD_Y as it does not take into account how ozone uptake is affected by climate, soil and plant factors.

Several POD_Y indicators are described in CLRTAP (2024). POD_YSPEC is a species or group of species-specific POD_Y that requires comprehensive input data and is suitable for detailed risk assessment. POD_YIAM is a vegetation-type specific POD_Y that requires less input data and is suitable for large-scale modelling, including integrated assessment modelling. POD_YSPEC is further used in this report.

For crops (wheat, potato and tomato), the Y value is taken equal to 6 nmol/m² PLA/s (i.e. per unit projected leaf area) as recommended in CLRTAP (2024). For the details of POD_Y (and specifically POD₆SPEC as used in this report) calculation, see Annex 1, Section A1.3.

The species-specific flux models and associated response functions and critical levels (CL) for ozone-sensitive crops and cultivars can be used to quantify the potential negative impacts of O₃ on the security of food supplies at the local and regional scale. They can be used to estimate yield losses, including economic losses. A flux-threshold Y of 6 (POD₆SPEC) provides the strongest flux-effect relationships for crops (Pleijel et al., 2007). O₃ effects proved to be significant at a 5% reduction of the effect parameter (Mills et al., 2011), hence CLs were determined for this 5% reduction of the effect parameter (i.e. yield, weight or quality of grain, tuber or fruit), based on the slope of the function. The POD₆SPEC CLs for crops were determined based on this reduction of relevant yield or weight, as shown in Table 3.9.

Wheat, potato and tomato are considered as representative species of crops in Europe (tomato can be regarded as representative horticultural crop for the Mediterranean and Black Sea regions, which is the case of potato for other regions). Therefore, POD₆SPEC for these crops (labelled further simply as POD₆ for wheat, potato and tomato, respectively) are recommended for regular map construction. This report presents maps of POD₆ for wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*).

Table 3.9 POD₆SPEC critical levels for crops as determined by CLRTAP

Crop	Effect parameter	POD ₆ SPEC critical level
Wheat	grain yield	1.3 mmol/m ² PLA
Wheat	1000-grain weight	1.5 mmol/m ² PLA
Wheat	protein yield	2.0 mmol/m ² PLA
Potato	tuber yield	3.8 mmol/m ² PLA
Tomato	fruit yield	2 mmol/m ² PLA
Tomato	fruit quality	3.8 mmol/m ² PLA

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

Regarding trees, beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and Norway spruce (*Picea abise*) were selected as the tree species for which the most comprehensive parameterization for POD is available. For them, the Y value is taken equal to 1 nmol/m² PLA/s (i.e. per unit projected leaf area). For the details of POD_Y (and specifically POD₁SPEC as used in this report) calculation, see Vlasáková et al. (2023).

A uniform O₃ flux threshold of Y = 1 nmol/m² PLA/s was adopted for use in species-specific phytotoxic O₃ doses (POD_YSPEC) for all tree species at the O₃ CLs workshop in Madrid, November 2016 (CLRTAP, 2024), based on data and analyses presented in Bükér et al. (2015). Anav et al. (2022) illustrated that POD₁ is the most reliable simple estimate of O₃ risk and recommended the use of this metric by policy makers as an air quality standard to protect vulnerable forest ecosystems in the future. The POD₁SPEC CLs for forest trees were set to values for an acceptable biomass loss, as shown in Table 3.10.

Table 3.10 POD₁SPEC critical levels for trees as determined by CLRTAP

Tree	Effect parameter	POD ₁ SPEC critical level
Beech	4% annual reduction of the whole tree biomass	5.2 mmol/m ² PLA
Spruce	2% annual reduction of the whole tree biomass	9.2 mmol/m ² PLA

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

The POD maps have been calculated based on the hourly ozone concentration maps, together with the meteorological and soil hydraulic properties data, based on the methodology described in Annex 1, Section A1.3. The ozone maps for each hour of the year 2023 have been constructed using the same methodology as the annual maps, i.e. the multiple linear regression followed by the kriging of its residuals (see Annex 1, Section A1.1) based on the measurement data, chemical transport model (CAM5-Ensemble forecast) output, altitude and the surface solar radiation. For details, see Annex 3, Section A3.3. The ozone maps have been calculated at the 2 km resolution, while the complete POD calculation has been executed in 0.1° resolution. The hourly ozone maps are created for rural areas only, based on rural background stations. The POD maps are therefore applicable to rural areas only. Next to this, it should be noted that in the POD calculations for wheat and potato, all growing areas are considered rain-fed (i.e. without irrigation), see Colette et al. (2018). Thus, the maps are directly applicable only for areas without irrigation. If applied for irrigated areas, the POD values for wheat and potato might be somewhat underestimated. On the other hand, no limitation of stomatal conductance due to soil moisture can be assumed for tomato, since it is an irrigated horticultural crop (see Annex 1, Section A1.3).

3.5.1 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose maps

Maps 3.10 to 3.12 present the maps of Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) for wheat, potato and tomato and maps 3.13 and 3.14 present the maps of POD₁ for beech and spruce in 2023. Generally, high values of the POD can be found in different parts of Europe since the POD is dependent not only on ozone levels but also on the environmental conditions and plant phenology. The lowest levels of the POD usually occur in areas with lower ozone concentrations (e.g. northern European regions) and/or in areas where environmental conditions limit the ozone stomatal conductance (dry and warm areas, including parts of the southern, south-western and south-eastern Europe). On the other hand, higher POD values can occur in areas with lower ozone concentrations, but favourable conditions for the stomatal conductance.

Crops

The areas in the Map 3.10 with POD₆ values below the lowest CL for wheat (i.e. 1.3 mmol/m² PLA for grain yield) are marked in dark green and green. The areas with POD₆ values in between CLs for grain

yield and 1 000-grain weight (i.e. between 1.3 mmol/m² PLA and 1.5 mmol/m² PLA) and in between CLs for 1 000-grain weight and protein yield (i.e. between 1.5 mmol/m² PLA and 2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in yellow and dark yellow, respectively. The areas with POD₆ values above the CL for protein yield of wheat (i.e. 2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in orange, red and dark red.

Map 3.10 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) for wheat, rural map, 2023

In 2023, POD₆ values for wheat above the highest CL (i.e. for protein yield) were observed across a large continuous area of Europe, covering especially western, central and south-eastern regions. Exceedances of the highest CL also occurred in parts of Spain, on the Italian islands of Sicily and Sardinia, in the Baltic states, and in southern Denmark. In addition, the lower CLs for grain yield and 1 000-grain weight were exceeded in parts of south-western Europe, in various areas of the Balkan countries, in smaller scattered regions of Türkiye, as well as in southern Norway and Sweden. No exceedances of CLs were observed in most of Türkiye, Cyprus and Greece, in other parts of the Balkan states, in central and southern Italy, in the Po Valley in northern Italy, across large areas of the Iberian Peninsula, and in most of northern Europe.

Map 3.11 presents the map of POD₆ for potato in 2023. The areas with POD₆ values above the CL for tuber yield of potato (i.e. 3.8 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Areas below this CL are marked in green and dark green.

In 2023, POD₆ values for potatoes exceeded the CL for tuber yield across western and central Europe — including almost the whole of France, Germany, the Benelux countries, Czechia, parts of Austria, Switzerland, Slovakia, Poland, and nearly all of Hungary and Slovenia. The CL for potatoes was also exceeded in parts of northern Europe (including Denmark and the Baltic states) and in small parts of southern Europe (parts of the Iberian Peninsula and Italy). The lowest POD₆ values, below the CL for potatoes in 2023, were observed in northern Europe, as well as in parts of central Europe, large areas of southern and south-eastern Europe, and most of Türkiye and Cyprus. This heterogeneity in POD₆ values highlights their dependence on both ozone concentrations and the meteorological conditions that determine stomatal conductance.

Map 3.11 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) for potato, rural map, 2023

Map 3.12 presents the map of POD₆ for tomato in 2023. The areas with POD₆ values above the CL for fruit yield (i.e. 2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in red and dark red, the areas with POD₆ values above the CL for fruit quality (i.e. 3.8 mmol/m² PLA) in dark red. The Modelling and Mapping Manual (CLRTAP, 2024) defines the parameterization for tomato for the Mediterranean area. EU-27 agriculture statistics show that 51% of tomato in 2024 was produced in Italy, Spain, Portugal, and Greece (EC, 2025). In the colder regions of Europe, tomato would be mostly grown in greenhouses where the methodology used to compute ozone concentrations and uptake is not applicable. For the purpose of completeness, the POD₆ has been modelled even for non-Mediterranean areas using the same parameterization (lighter colours in the Map 3.12).

Most of the Mediterranean areas showed the values of POD₆ for tomato below the lower CL for fruit yield in 2023. POD₆ values above CL for fruit yield occurred mainly in coastal areas of Spain, southern France, Italy, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Albania, Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Cyprus and Türkiye.

Map 3.12 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) for tomato, rural map, 2023

Trees

Map 3.13 shows the map of POD₁ for beech in 2023. The areas with POD₁ values below the CL for beech (i.e. 5.2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in dark green and green. The areas with POD₁ values above the CL for beech are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Since no parametrization for beech in the Boreal, Arctic and Alpine > 50° biogeographical regions is available, these areas are marked in lighter colours.

Map 3.13 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₁) for beech, rural map, 2023

The CL for beech was exceeded in almost the entire European mapped area, with the exception of large areas of the Iberian Peninsula and Türkiye, as well as numerous smaller areas across the mapped European area — particularly in Poland, Germany, Slovakia, Denmark, Sweden, Ireland, southern France, parts of Italy (notably the islands of Sardinia and Sicily), Hungary, Serbia, Romania, Bulgaria, Northern Macedonia, Greece and Cyprus).

Map 3.14 presents the map of POD_1 for spruce in 2023. The areas with POD_1 values below the CL for spruce (i.e. $9.2 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) are marked in dark green and green. The areas with POD_1 values above the CL for spruce are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Since no parametrization for spruce in the Mediterranean, Anatolian and Black Sea biogeographical regions is available, this area is marked in lighter colours.

Map 3.14 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_1) for spruce, rural map, 2023

The CL for spruce has been exceeded almost throughout the entire mapped European area, with the exception of large areas in Scandinavia and Iceland and parts of the Baltic states, a small area in Romania and a few scattered areas in Bulgaria, Hungary, Serbia, Poland, and Germany. However, many smaller areas with PODs below CL can be found in almost every country in Europe. Nevertheless, according to CLRTAP (2020), the start of the growing season in northern Europe is earlier than the start of the growing season calculated by the current recommended latitude model (boreal region). As a result of this earlier start of the growing season, POD_1 values in northern Europe (boreal region) could be higher than those presented. Unfortunately, a better approach for determining the start of the growing season for spruce is not currently available in this region.

4 NO₂ and NO_x

The methodology for creating the concentration maps follows the same principle as for the rest of pollutants: a linear regression model on the basis of European wide station measurement data, followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that regression model (residual kriging).

The map on NO₂ is based on a mapping methodology as follows. The map layers are created for the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. Subsequently, the urban background and urban traffic map layers are merged using the gridded road data into one urban map layer. This urban map layer is further combined with the rural map layer into the final NO₂ map using a population density grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. Supplementary data used consist of chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, Sentinel-5P satellite data, wind speed, population density and land cover indicators for rural areas; for urban background areas these are CTM output and temperature, altitude, Sentinel-5P satellite data, wind speed, population density and land cover indicators; for traffic areas the CTM output, altitude, and Sentinel-5P satellite data are used (Annex 3, Section A3.4). The final concentration map is presented at the 1 km grid resolution. Be it noted that this final map is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas (which are smoothed at this 1 km spatial resolution).

The map of the vegetation-related indicator NO_x annual average is created on a grid at 2 km resolution, based on rural background measurements only, as vegetation is considered not to be extensively present at urban and suburban areas. Hence, this map is applicable to rural areas only. The resolution is chosen equally to the one of the vegetation indicator for ozone.

The population exposure to NO₂ has been calculated based on the methodology described in Annex 1, see Equation A1.6. In order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic, it has been calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas and combined by the weight representing the ratio of areas inside buffers around the roads in the 1 km grid cell. Based on this, different concentration levels in urban background and traffic areas inside the 1 km grid cells are taken into account. Thus – like for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} – the population exposure refers not only to the rural and urban background areas, but to the urban traffic locations as well. However, it should be mentioned that only population density data at 1 km resolution has been used. This means that contrary to the concentration levels, the population density is constant within each 1 km grid cell. This shortcoming can increase the uncertainty of the population exposure results.

Annex 3 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the maps, as well as the uncertainty analysis of the maps.

4.1 NO₂ – Annual mean

The Ambient AQ Directive (EC, 2008) set two limit values (LV) for NO₂ for the human health protection (i.e. for annual and for hourly NO₂ concentrations), while the revised ambient AQ Directive (EU, 2024) revised them and introduced a third LV. The revised annual and hourly and the new daily NO₂ LVs have to be reached by 2030. The current 2008 annual LV (ALV) is set at the level of 40 µg/m³ (EC, 2008), the revised 2030 annual limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) is set at 20 µg/m³ (EU, 2024) and the WHO Air Quality Guideline level for the NO₂ annual average (WHO, 2021a) is set at 10 µg/m³. The 2008 hourly LV (HLV) is set at 200 µg/m³, not to be exceeded on more than 18 hours per year. The revised 2030 EU hourly LV (EU, 2024) means that from 2030, the hourly NO₂ concentration of 200 µg/m³ should not be exceeded more than 3 times per year. Finally, the revised directive (EU, 2024) introduces a daily average NO₂ concentration limit value of 50 µg/m³, which must not be exceeded more than 18 times per year.

Concentrations above the 2008 HLV were observed in 0.9% (28 stations) of all reporting stations in 2023, mostly at urban traffic stations, all in Türkiye, see Targa et al. (2025). In view of this low number of exceedances, the short-term LV has not been included in the mapping procedures.

4.1.1 Concentration map

Map 4.1 presents the final combined 1 km resolution concentration map for the 2023 NO₂ annual average. The areas where NO₂ concentrations were above the 2008 ALV of 40 µg/m³ include urbanized parts of some large cities, particularly Athens and Istanbul, and some other cities in Türkiye. Some other cities show NO₂ levels above 30 µg/m³, e.g. in Romania, Italy, France, Spain, Cyprus and Türkiye. Most of the European area shows NO₂ levels below 10 µg/m³; a larger area with NO₂ concentrations between 10 and 20 µg/m³ is located in northern Italy. Some areas above 20 µg/m³ or 30 µg/m³ can be found in the Po Valley, the Benelux, the German Ruhr region, the Île de France region, around the national capitals or large cities in southern and south-eastern Europe, and in the Krakow – Katowice (PL) – Ostrava (CZ) industrial region.

It should be noted that the interpolated map is created at 1 km resolution only. Although the urban traffic map layer is used in the map creation, the traffic locations are smoothed in the 1 km resolution. Thus, the map as such refers to the rural and urban background situations only, while the concentrations above the NO₂ limit values occur mostly at local hotspots such as dense traffic locations and densely urbanised and industrialised areas. Such concentrations are mostly not visible in the 1 km resolution map.

The relative mean uncertainty of the NO₂ annual average map is 34% for rural and 29% for urban background areas (Annex 3, Section A3.4). This means slightly worse mapping uncertainty in rural areas compared to the quality objective for models of NO₂ annual average (i.e. 30%) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.10 of Annex 4.

Map 4.1 Concentration map of NO₂ annual average, 2023

Map 4.2 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for NO₂ annual average. Orange to red areas show an increase of NO₂ concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average NO₂ difference map the highest increases are observed in Türkiye and Greece. There are increases also in parts of southern and south-eastern Europe. A smaller increase is also observed in northern Europe, specifically in disconnected areas of Scandinavia and in the Baltic states. On the other hand, there are decreases in several countries, including the Benelux region, Germany, Switzerland, northern Italy, the Île-de-France region, Romania and eastern Türkiye.

Map 4.2 Difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for NO₂ annual average

4.1.2 Population exposure

Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes calculated on a grid of 1 km resolution for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the whole mapping area. Table 4.1 also presents the population-weighted concentration.

It has been estimated that in 2023, 2.6% of the considered European population including Türkiye and 0.2% of the EU-27 population lived in areas with NO₂ annual average concentrations above the annual EU limit value of 40 µg/m³.

About 67% of the considered European population including Türkiye and 63% of the EU-27 population has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021a).

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in 35 countries. In France, Italy, Romania, Greece up to 4% of population has been exposed to concentrations above the limit value. In Cyprus and Türkiye, this is the case for 8% and 19% of the population, respectively.

Table 4.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, NO₂ annual average, 2023

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	NO ₂ — annual average, exposed population (%)					Population-weighted concentration			
			< 10	10-20	20-30	30-40	40-45	> 45	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 762	52.9	33.0	13.5	0.6			11.7	13.6	-1.9
Andorra	AD	80	27.5	72.5					12.5	17.0	-4.5
Austria	AT	9 105	32.9	52.7	14.3	0.2			13.1	15.4	-2.2
Belgium	BE	11 743	25.9	66.4	7.7	0.0			12.7	16.9	-4.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 194	25.3	61.3	13.5				14.1	13.8	0.3
Bulgaria	BG	6 448	24.5	57.4	16.3	1.8			14.5	17.5	-3.0
Croatia	HR	3 851	36.5	51.0	12.0	0.6			12.4	13.4	-1.0
Cyprus	CY	1 419	10.7	8.7	72.5		0.8	7.3	24.6	22.4	2.2
Czechia	CZ	10 828	40.8	55.9	3.3				11.5	13.6	-2.1
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 987	88.9	11.0	0.1				6.4	8.2	-1.8
Estonia	EE	1 366	80.6	19.4					6.6	6.9	-0.3
Finland	FI	5 564	84.2	15.8					6.9	7.6	-0.7
France (metropolitan)	FR	66 017	53.2	36.6	8.0	2.2	0.0		11.1	13.7	-2.7
Germany	DE	83 119	34.0	58.4	7.2	0.4			12.4	16.2	-3.8
Greece	GR	10 414	35.0	27.8	21.0	12.3	0.9	3.0	17.4	18.4	-1.0
Hungary	HU	9 600	31.8	55.4	11.2	1.6			12.9	15.7	-2.8
Iceland	IS	388	86.4	13.3	0.3				7.2	8.7	-1.5
Ireland	IE	5 271	67.5	30.2	2.2	0.1			8.0	9.3	-1.3
Italy	IT	58 997	17.2	54.3	23.5	4.8	0.2	0.0	16.7	18.7	-2.0
Latvia	LV	1 883	62.1	36.5	1.4				9.0	10.4	-1.4
Liechtenstein	LI	40	6.9	91.9	1.2				12.2	15.3	-3.2
Lithuania	LT	2 857	55.5	41.1	3.5				9.9	11.0	-1.1
Luxembourg	LU	661	44.8	53.8	1.4				10.8	16.4	-5.6
Malta	MT	542	45.7	47.3	7.0				10.8	10.9	-0.1
Monaco	MC	39		80.5	19.5				16.5	20.5	-3.9
Montenegro	ME	617	20.7	75.3	4.0				12.9	13.4	-0.5
Netherlands	NL	17 811	16.7	78.4	4.9				13.5	17.4	-3.8
North Macedonia	MK	1 830	50.5	44.6	3.4	1.5			10.8	16.2	-5.4
Norway	NO	5 489	72.9	25.4	1.7				7.4	8.6	-1.2
Poland	PL	36 754	43.4	49.4	6.7	0.4			11.8	13.9	-2.1
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	10 022	42.1	49.1	8.0	0.8			11.7	13.1	-1.4
Romania	RO	19 055	27.5	53.0	14.3	4.4	0.5	0.3	14.9	17.9	-3.0
San Marino	SM	34	30.1	65.2	4.7				11.0	14.0	-3.0
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 350	22.2	63.1	14.2	0.4			14.3	16.2	-2.0
Slovakia	SK	5 429	40.8	56.9	2.2				11.1	12.7	-1.6
Slovenia	SI	2 117	40.5	56.3	3.1				11.4	13.4	-2.1
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 872	30.9	45.1	18.9	5.1			15.0	16.6	-1.7
Sweden	SE	10 522	88.4	11.6					6.3	7.3	-1.0
Switzerland	CH	8 815	22.4	69.3	8.3				12.8	15.4	-2.6
Türkiye	TR	85 280	8.7	11.6	30.4	30.0	6.3	13.0	30.7	26.4	4.3
			33.1	43.8			1.0	2.0			
Total		560 170	73.1	13.9	6.2	2.6			15.5	16.9	-1.4
			37.4	49.0			0.1	0.1			
EU-27		443 198	81.4	11.2	2.2	0.2			12.9	15.4	-2.5
Northern Europe		34 055	80.6	18.7	0.7				7.1	8.3	-1.2
Western Europe		86 334	43.3	48.1	7.0	1.6	0.0		11.7	15.0	-3.3
Central Europe		165 805	36.1	56.2	7.3	0.4			12.2	15.2	-3.0
Southern Europe		142 589	28.1	47.4	19.5	4.6	0.1	0.3	15.3	17.0	-1.7
South-Eastern Europe		131 386	16.3	27.6	24.2	19.7	4.1	8.2	24.5	22.7	1.8
Kosovo	XK	1 709	30.5	69.1	0.4				11.6	15.4	-3.9
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS	6 641	20.0	61.6	17.8	0.6			14.9	16.4	-1.5

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. 5-year mean 2018-2022. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022.

The population-weighted concentration of the NO₂ annual mean has been estimated for 2023 at 15.5 µg/m³ for total mapped area and 12.9 µg/m³ for the EU-27, which means a decrease of 1.4 µg/m³ and 2.5 µg/m³ compared to the previous 5-year mean, respectively. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Luxembourg (5.6 µg/m³), and the highest increase was estimated in Türkiye (4.3 µg/m³).

Figure 4.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of NO₂ annual average (µg/m³), 2023

Figure 4.2 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 µg/m³. One can see the highest population frequency for classes between 4 and 22 µg/m³, a continuous decline of population frequency for classes between 22 and 40 µg/m³ and continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes between 41 and 75 µg/m³.

Figure 4.2 Population exposure frequency distribution, NO₂ annual average, 2023. The WHO AQG level (10 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2030 EU limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.13% of population lived in areas with PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations between 75 and 95 µg/m³.

The boxplot showing for individual countries the NO₂ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2023 is presented in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 NO₂ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2023. The WHO AQG level (10 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2030 EU limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the 2008 EU limit value (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50% in the case of the black marker, 25% and 75% in the cases of the box's edges, 2% and 98% in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

4.2 NO_x – Annual mean

4.2.1 Concentration map

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets a critical level (CL) for the protection of vegetation for the NO_x annual mean at 30 µg/m³ (and this standard remains unchanged under EU, 2024). According to these directives, the sampling points targeted at the protection of vegetation and natural ecosystems shall be in general sited more than 20 km away from agglomerations or more than 5 km away from other built-up areas. Thus, only the observations at rural background stations are used for the NO_x mapping and the resulting map is representative for rural areas only.

The number of NO_x measurement stations is limited. The mapping of the NO_x annual average has been therefore performed on the basis of an approach presented in Horálek et al. (2007). This approach derives additional pseudo NO_x annual mean concentrations from NO₂ annual mean measurement concentrations and increases as such the number and spatial coverage of NO_x 'data points', and applies these data to the NO_x mapping. Section A1.1 of Annex 1 provides some details.

Map 4.3 presents the concentration map of NO_x annual average. It concerns rural areas only, representing an indicator for vegetation exposure to NO_x.

Most of the European area shows NO_x levels below 20 µg/m³. However, in the Po Valley, parts of Türkiye and around some larger European cities (Athens and Barcelona) NO_x concentrations above the

CL are observed. These concentrations are expected to be the result of large emissions from transport in and around the cities, as well as energy production and industrial facilities taking place at these areas. These values above the CL would be relevant only for the so-called peri-urban vegetation where patches of agricultural land and of natural or planted vegetation can be found. On the contrary, low concentrations (below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) are observed across large areas in most of the mapped countries, with the exception of more extensive regions in Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, the Po Valley, the Benelux countries, Türkiye, and several smaller, discontinuous areas in Central Europe and on the Iberian Peninsula.

Map 4.3 Concentration map of NO_x annual average, rural map, 2023

The relative mean uncertainty of this NO_x rural map is 43%. This means higher mapping uncertainty compared to the quality objective for models of NO_x annual average (i.e. 30%) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). This higher relative uncertainty is strongly influenced by the low concentration values of NO_x in most of the areas. The NO_x annual average rural map including the data measured at rural background stations is presented in Map A4.11 of Annex 4. The map illustrates the lack of the NO_x rural stations in the Balkan area.

Map 4.4 presents the difference between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for annual average for NO_x . Orange to red areas show an increase of NO_x concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease. The highest increases are observed in Türkiye, with increases also in the eastern regions of Bulgaria and Romania. Notable decreases are primarily observed in the Île-de-France region and the Benelux countries, the Po Valley, parts of Germany, and southern Türkiye. Additional areas showing a widespread decline in NO_x concentrations include Hungary and large parts of the Balkan states. A continuous area of decrease is also observed in Germany and in several smaller regions across Central and Western Europe.

Vegetation exposure has not been calculated for NO_x , since values above the CL for protection of the vegetation would occur in limited vegetation areas only and, as such, is considered not to provide essential information from the European scale perspective. Furthermore, contrary to vegetation exposure to high ozone concentrations in Europe that leads to considerable damage, vegetation

exposure to NO_x pollution is of minor importance in terms of actual impacts. On the other hand, NO_x concentrations contribute in part to the total N-deposition, which leads to acidifying and eutrophying effects on vegetation. These effects, especially eutrophication, are still very important in Europe (e.g. EMEP, 2020). However, these effects on vegetation cannot be expressed by an exposure to NO_x as many oxidized and reduced nitrogen compounds contribute to total atmospheric nitrogen deposition.

Map 4.4 Difference concentrations between 2023 and the 5-year mean 2018-2022 for NO_x annual average

Concerning the potential exposure estimate of vegetation and natural ecosystems to NO_x there is an additional dilemma: which receptor types should be selected to estimate the exposure and CL exceedance of vegetation and natural ecosystems? An option would be the use of CLC classes (e.g. like in Horálek et al., 2008, i.e. natural areas); nevertheless, this classification is too general. Another option would be the NATURA 2000 database. However, that data source contains a wide series of receptor types, species and classes. Serious additional efforts would be needed to conclude on the most relevant set of receptors from the NATURA 2000 geographical database.

5 Benzo(a)pyrene

An annual average map for benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) has been produced and is presented in the regular mapping report for the fourth time. In agreement with the conclusions of Horálek et al. (2022b), it is labelled as an experimental map to indicate that it does not yet meet the same accuracy standards as the regularly produced maps of other pollutants.

The map of BaP is based on the mapping methodology developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2022b). The methodology for creating the concentration maps follows the same principle as for the rest of pollutants: a linear regression model based on European wide station measurement data, followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that regression model (residual kriging). The map layers are created for the rural and urban background areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. Supplementary data used in the linear regression for rural areas consist of chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, temperature, wind speed and land cover; for urban background areas they are CTM output and temperature (Annex 3, Section A3.5). The final concentration map is presented at a 1 km grid resolution.

Due to the poor spatial coverage of the BaP measurement stations, so-called pseudo-BaP stations have been used in addition. Pseudo-BaP data in locations with PM_{2.5} measurements (or with pseudo-PM_{2.5} data based on PM₁₀ measurements) and with no BaP measurements have been estimated based on the exponential regression of the observed BaP concentrations with the PM_{2.5} data, geographical coordinates and the land cover. Due to quite high uncertainty of the pseudo data, they are only used in areas with a lack of BaP measurements. Due to the serious lack of Turkish data, Türkiye is not included in the mapping area. Annex 3, Section A3.5 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the BaP map, as well as the uncertainty analysis of this map.

The 2004 Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2004) sets a target value (TV) for ambient air concentration of BaP, as a marker for the carcinogenic risk of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in ambient air. The TV for BaP (measured in PM₁₀) is set to 1 ng/m³ as an annual mean. The revised Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024) introduces the EU limit value to be reached by 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀), which is set to 1.0 ng/m³ for the annual mean.

Both the 2030 EU LV (1.0 ng/m³) and the estimated WHO reference level (RL, 0.12 ng/m³) are based on the WHO lung cancer unit risk for PAH mixtures and correspond to an additional lifetime cancer risk of approximately 9 cases and 1 case in 100 000 exposed individuals, respectively (WHO, 2021b).

5.1 Benzo(a)pyrene – Annual mean

5.1.1 Concentration map

Map 5.1 presents the final combined 1 km resolution concentration map for the 2023 annual average of BaP. Red and purple areas indicate concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³ (i.e. above the 2030 LV).

BaP concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³ are found in Poland, the north-eastern part of Czechia, west Balkan, the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy, and some populated locations in central and south-eastern Europe, Latvia and Finland. By contrast, western and southern Europe (except Italy) have low BaP values. Generally, lower levels of BaP concentrations in natural areas can be seen, compared with the other land cover types.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 map of BaP annual average is 137% for rural and 67% for urban areas and determined exclusively on the actual BaP measurement data points, i.e. not the pseudo stations (Annex 3, Section A3.5). This uncertainty is considerably high (especially in the rural areas) with respect to the quality objective for models for BaP annual average (i.e. 60%) as set in the

European directive (EC, 2004). The high uncertainty in the rural areas is probably strongly affected (besides the low density of the rural stations) by the fact that stations classified as “rural background” comprise both regional stations with low BaP values and stations located in villages, which are often highly influenced by local heating leading to high BaP concentrations.

Map 5.1 Concentration map of benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2023, experimental map

Map 5.2 Difference concentrations between 2023 and the five-year mean 2018-2022 benzo(a)pyrene annual average

Map 5.2 presents the difference between 2023 and the five-year mean 2018-2022 for BaP annual average. Orange to red areas show an increase of BaP concentration in 2023, while blue areas show a decrease. Areas with the highest decreases have been found in Poland. Areas with the highest increase

are shown in the western Balkans, however, this estimated increase can be influenced by a high uncertainty of the map and a low density of BaP stations in this area.

5.1.2 Population exposure

Table 5.1 gives the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to BaP concentrations, as well as the population-weighted concentration. Due to the experimental character of the BaP map and its high uncertainty, the population exposure is presented only for EU-27, for five European regions and for the total mapping area, not for individual countries.

Table 5.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2023, based on the experimental map

Area	Population [inhbs·1000]	BaP – annual average, exposed population, 2023 [%]						Population-weighted concentration		
		< 0.12	0.12-0.4	0.4-0.6	0.6-1.0	1.0-1.5	> 1.5	2023	5-year mean	Diff.
Northern Europe	34 055	9.6	62.5	16.5	10.6	0.8		0.37	0.53	-0.16
Western Europe	86 334	63.7	36.2	0.0	0.0			0.12	0.15	-0.03
Central Europe	165 805	27.2	35.5	8.0	14.0	8.2	7.2	0.53	0.96	-0.44
Southern Europe	142 589	21.3	63.8	8.9	4.0	1.9	0.1	0.29	0.27	0.02
South-Eastern Europe without Türkiye	46 106	1.8	18.6	15.5	39.9	17.0	7.2	0.84	1.29	-0.45
Total	474 890	28.0	44.3	8.2	10.9	5.2	3.3	0.40	0.62	-0.21
EU-27	443 198	29.7	44.3	8.3	10.7	4.2	2.8	0.38		

Note: The percentage value “0.0” indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no population in exposure.

Based on the experimental map, it is estimated that 8.5% of the population living in the considered European area was exposed to concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³ in 2023 (7% for EU27). Further, it is estimated that about 72% of the population living in the considered European area was exposed to concentrations above the WHO RL of 0.12 ng/m³ (70.3% for EU27). The population-weighted concentration of the BaP annual average for 2023 for the considered European countries is estimated to be 0.4 ng/m³ (0.38 ng/m³ for EU27).

Figure 5.1 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 0.05 ng/m³. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 0.05 and 0.20 ng/m³. A quite continuous decline of population frequency is visible for classes above 0.30 ng/m³.

Figure 5.1 Population frequency distribution, benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2023. The value 1.0 ng/m³ is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.15% of population lived in areas with BaP annual average concentrations between 3.0 and 4.3 ng/m³.

6 Accumulated risks

Although the spatial distributions of PM, NO₂ and ozone concentrations differ widely, the possibility of an accumulation of risk resulting from high exposures to all three pollutants cannot be excluded. The maps for the three most frequently exceeded EU standards (PM₁₀ daily limit value as presented in Map 2.3, O₃ target value as shown in Map 3.1 left and NO₂ annual limit value as presented in Map 4.1) have been combined, see Map 6.1.

Map 6.1 Exceedance of Health-Related Air Quality Standards, 2023

The combined population exposure shows the following results: out of the total population of 560 million in the considered area, 5% (30.2 million) people live in areas where two or three of these air quality standards are exceeded; 0.1% (0.5 million) people live in areas where all three standards are exceeded (in some urban areas affected by traffics, not visible in the 1 km resolution map). The worst situation in 2023 was observed in Greece and Türkiye, where 4% and 0.2% lived in areas where all three standards are exceeded, respectively.

7 Exposure trend estimates

This report presents the 2023 interpolated maps for the PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, ozone and NO₂ human health related air pollution indicators (annual average and the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means, annual average for PM_{2.5}, the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 for ozone, and the annual average for NO₂), as well as the BaP annual average experimental map, together with tables showing the frequency distribution of the estimated population exposures and the population-weighted concentration per country (apart from BaP), large European region, EU-27 and the total mapping area.

Furthermore, interpolated maps of ozone and NO_x vegetation related air pollution indicators have been produced. More specifically, these include maps of the ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests, and tables with the frequency distribution of estimated land area exposures and agricultural- and forest-weighted concentration per country, large region, EU-27 and the total mapping area. In addition, the maps of the Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_y) for crops (wheat, potato and tomato) and trees (spruce and beech), and the NO_x annual average map have been produced, but without exposure estimates.

The RIMM mapping methodology, similar to previous years (Horálek et al., 2024 and references therein), based primarily on observational data has been used. With the interpolated air pollution maps and exposure estimates for the year 2023 completed, a nineteen-year overview of comparable exposure estimates is now available (with full time series coverage for PM₁₀ and four ozone indicators, one year missing for PM_{2.5}, four years missing for NO₂ and five years available for BaP). In this chapter these multi-annual overviews of exposure estimates are provided for each of the PM and NO₂ indicators and for four ozone indicators (i.e. 93.2nd percentile of maximum daily 8-hour mean, SOMO35 and both AOT40 indicators), including a brief trend analysis. For most indicators, figures showing time series of population and/or vegetation exposure are presented (for 2012-2023 for health-related indicators and for 2005-2023 for AOT40s). In addition, a brief overview for BaP is also given, for 2012 and 2018-2023.

For the previous years' data, mapping results as presented in Horálek et al. (2024) and previous mapping reports have been used. Since 2017 results, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} maps have been prepared based on the most recently updated methodology (Horálek et al., 2019). For comparability reasons, results for 2015-2019 (and partly also for 2005 and 2009) are presented in two variants for these pollutants, i.e. based on the old and the updated methodologies. The maps based on the 1 km merging resolution as tested in Horálek et al. (2010) and routinely applied since 2008 results are used for the whole period, due to consistency. For the human health indicators, the exposure estimates are expressed, on one hand, as population-weighted concentration and, on the other hand, as percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the limit/target values. For the vegetation related indicators, the exposure estimates are expressed as the agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations, as well as the agricultural or forest areas exposed to concentrations above defined thresholds.

It should be noted that the percentage of population, agricultural area, or forest area exposed is a less robust indicator compared to the population-weighted, agricultural-weighted, or forest-weighted concentration, as a small concentration increase (or decrease) may lead to a major increase (or decrease) of population, agricultural or forest area exposed. This is not the case when taking the population-weighted or agricultural/forest-weighted concentration as indicator. Therefore, the trend analysis is done based on the population-weighted, agricultural-weighted and forest-weighted concentrations only.

When thinking about a trend, the following should be taken into account: (i) the meteorologically induced variations, (ii) the uncertainties involved in the interpolation (Annex 3), and (iii) the year-to-

year variation of the station density and their spatial distribution, which influence the interpolated maps. In addition, one should be aware of the fact that different trends in various parts of Europe may occur. However, bearing in mind these limitations a trend analysis is provided here for the period 2005-2023 on the population-, agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations for the total mapping area.

For comparability reasons, in this chapter the results for the total mapped area do not include Türkiye, because 2016 was the first year for which the area of Türkiye was mapped. Next to this, the results for the total mapped area include United Kingdom in this chapter. For the 16-year time series 2005-2020, the overall exposure included the United Kingdom (see Horálek et al., 2024, and the references therein). Therefore, the overall exposure for the total area including the United Kingdom has been calculated also for years 2021-2023. The relevant values were easily available, as the mapping domain includes the United Kingdom (see Section A1.1).

7.1 Human health PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators

Table 7.1 summarises the average concentration to which the considered European population has been exposed to over the nineteen-year period 2005-2023 for both human health PM₁₀ indicators, expressed as the population-weighted concentration, and the percentage of population exposed to PM₁₀ concentrations above limit values (LV), i.e. the 2008 annual (ALV) and daily (DLV) limit value, respectively, and also the 2030 annual limit value (LV₂₀₃₀).

For the years 2012 and 2013 both the 36th highest value and the 90.4 percentile of daily mean(s) are presented. Their results demonstrate an underestimation of almost 1 µg/m³ at the 36th highest daily mean. One may conclude that this underestimation is caused by the fact that when calculating the 36th highest daily mean value there is no correction for the missing values at incomplete time series. Whereas the 90.4 percentile of daily means adjusts for such missing data.

As the PM₁₀ maps have been constructed using the updated methodology since 2017 results, the table presents the results for 2015-2019 (and 2005 and 2009, for annual average) both based on the updated and the old methodologies, for comparability reasons.

Table 7.1 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the 2008 PM₁₀ limit values (LV) and above the 2030 PM₁₀ annual limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) for the protection of health for 2005 to 2023

PM ₁₀		meth.	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Annual Average																					
Pop.-weighted concentration [µg/m ³]	old	28.0	28.9	26.6	25.1	24.6	24.5	25.3	22.9	22.2	21.1	21.2	20.2	20.2	20.1	18.3					
	new	28.6				25.3							21.6	20.5	20.8	20.8	18.7	18.0	18.1	18.4	16.4
Pop. exposed > LV (40 µg/m ³) [%]	old	13.3	10.9	7.1	5.9	6.0	5.2	7.2	3.4	2.6	2.0	0.6	1.7	2.9	2.1	0.3					
	new	11.5				6.2							0.7	1.7	3.3	2.4	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.1
Pop. exp. > LV ₂₀₃₀ (20 µg/m ³) [%]	old		86.1	81.5	68.7	71.5	70.7		55.1	54.4	44.1	45.7	39.3								
	new	89.0				72.5							48.0		42.3	43.2	33.0	28.7	32.1	33.1	22.7
36th Highest Daily Mean / 90.4 Percentile of Daily Means																					
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	36 th high.	old	47.4	48.3	44.7	41.9	41.6	42.0	44.9	40.0	38.6										
	90.4 perc.	old								40.8	39.4	37.1	36.9	35.7	36.1	34.5	32.1				
	90.4 perc.	new											37.5	36.1	37.0	35.4	32.8	31.5	31.1	31.4	27.6
Pop. exposed > DLV (50 µg/m ³) [%]	36 th high.	old	35.9	37.2	27.6	20.3	17.0	20.8	24.8	16.9	16.4										
	90.4 perc.	old								18.1	17.3	13.3	14.7	14.0	15.8	12.0	7.2				
	90.4 perc.	new											16.2	14.6	17.0	13.2	8.1	9.1	8.7	6.1	3.5

In 2023 the fractions of the population exposed to annual mean concentrations of PM₁₀ above the 2008 LV of 40 µg/m³ and above the 2030 LV of 20 µg/m³ have been 0.1% and 23% of the total population, respectively, which are the lowest percentages in the overall time series. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean PM₁₀ concentration of 16.4 µg/m³, being the lowest value in the nineteen years' time series.

In the nineteen-year time series, the percentage of people living in areas with concentrations above the 2008 annual LV is lower in the latest eleven years (2013-2023) than in the first eight years, with the lowest values in the last five years (2019-2023). The overall picture of the population-weighted annual mean concentration of the whole considered mapping area (i.e. including United Kingdom and without Türkiye) demonstrates a downward trend of about $-0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ per year for the years 2005-2023, based on the old mapping method results for 2005-2014 and the new methodology for 2015-2023 (for trend estimation methodology, see Annex 1, Section A1.2). This trend is statistically significant (at the strongest level 0.001) and expresses a mean decrease of $0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ per year.

In 2023 about 3.5% of the considered European population have lived in areas where concentrations have been above the 2008 PM_{10} daily limit value (calculated using the 90.4 percentile), being the lowest of the nineteen-year period. The overall population-weighted concentration of the 90.4 percentile of the PM_{10} daily means is estimated to be $27.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2023 for the whole mapping area, which is the lowest of the nineteen years considered. This is the case even though the 36th highest daily means (i.e. possibly underestimated data if applied instead of the 90.4 percentiles, see above) have been used in the 2005-2011 calculations. The population-weighted concentrations of the whole considered mapping area show a statistically significant (at the strongest level 0.001) downward trend of about $-1.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ per year for the years 2005-2023, for the 2008 daily LV related indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means (formerly the 36th highest daily mean), as calculated based on the old mapping method results for 2005-2014 and the new methodology for 2015-2023.

Table 7.2 summarises for the human health $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ indicator (annual average) the population-weighted concentration and the percentage of the considered European population exposed to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations above the EU 2008 LV and 2030 LV for the years 2005 to 2023 (without 2006, for which neither a map nor a population exposure was prepared).

As in the case of PM_{10} , the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ maps have been constructed using the updated methodology since 2017 maps. The table presents the results for 2005, 2009 and 2015-2019 (all the years for which maps using both methods are available) both based on the updated and the old methodology, for comparability reasons.

Table 7.2 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the 2008 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ limit value (LV) and above the 2030 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ limit value (LV_{2030}) for the protection of health for 2005 to 2023

$\text{PM}_{2.5}$	meth	2005	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	
Annual average																					
Pop.-weighted conc. [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	old	18.8	not mapped	16.2	16.4	16.2	16.9	17.8	15.7	15.3	14.1	14.2	13.4	13.6	13.2	11.6					
	new	19.0				16.6							14.3	13.6	13.8	13.5	11.8	11.1	11.2	11.2	10.1
Pop. exposed > LV (25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) [%]	old			8.2	7.9	7.6	8.3	13.3	9.1	5.8	4.2	6.3	5.4	7.0	4.1	0.9					
	new	16.8				7.6						6.5	5.4	7.2	4.5	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.6	0.2	
Pop. exp. > LV_{2030} (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) [%]	old					92.2	93.1	88.9	87.8	83.3	80.8	75.4									
	new	99.8			92.1						81.7	77.0	74.2	76.4	64.0	46.5	50.0	49.6	37.2		

The percentage of population exposed in 2023 to annual mean concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ above the 2008 LV of $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ has been 0.2%, which is the lowest value in the nineteen years' time series. 37.2% of the population has been exposed to levels in excess of the 2030 limit value (LV_{2030}) of $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is also the lowest value in the nineteen-year period. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration of $10.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2023, being the lowest values in the time series.

The trend analysis of the population-weighted concentrations across the period 2005-2023 for the total mapping area has been executed, based on the old mapping method results for the period 2005-2014 and the new mapping method for 2015-2023. At European scale a statistical significant (at the strongest level 0.001) downward trend can be observed, estimated to be $-0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ per year.

Figure 7.1 gives the PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ population exposure for few concentration classes, for 2012-2023.

Figure 7.1 Population exposure, PM_{10} (left) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (right) annual average, 2012-2023

The evolution of the population-weighted concentrations for PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ is shown in Figure 7.2.

Figure 7.2 Population-weighted concentration of PM_{10} annual mean (left) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ annual mean (right) in 2005-2023. Results based on both the old (blue dots) and the updated (red dots) mapping methodology are presented, where available

7.2 Human health and vegetation related ozone indicators

Table 7.3 summarises the exposure levels of the considered European inhabitants in terms of population-weighted concentrations for two human health ozone indicators. Furthermore, it presents the percentage of considered European population exposed to concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold and above a level of $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ ⁽⁶⁾ for the SOMO35 for the years 2005 to 2023.

For 2012 and 2013, both the 26th highest value and the 93.2nd percentile of maximum daily 8-hour mean(s) have been calculated. It demonstrates an underestimation of about $0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at the 26th maximum daily 8-hour mean, which is caused by the fact that when calculating this indicator there is no correction for the missing values in the incomplete measurement time series.

⁽⁶⁾ Note that the $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ does not represent a health-related legally binding 'threshold'. In this and previous papers it represents a somewhat arbitrarily chosen threshold to facilitate the discussion of the observed distributions of SOMO35 levels in their spatial and temporal context. For motivation of this choice, see Section 3.3.

Table 7.3 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold for the protection of health and a SOMO35 threshold of 6 000 µg/m³·d for 2005 to 2023

Ozone		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
26th highest daily max. 8-h mean / 93.2 percentile of daily max. 8-h means																				
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	26 th high. 93.2 perc.	111.4	117.6	110.0	109.4	107.7	106.5	108.4	107.3	108.3										
Popul. exp. > TV (120 µg/m ³) [%]	26 th high. 93.2 perc.	29.5	49.8	24.9	13.6	14.9	15.8	15.0	19.0	15.0										
SOMO35																				
Pop.-w. conc. [µg/m ³ ·d]		4622	5045	4291	4164	4233	3850	4318	4174	4089	3500	4312	3619	3890	4962	4478	3945	3563	4485	4212
Pop. exp. > 6000 µg/m ³ ·d		26.8	27.1	26.3	17.0	23.2	15.9	22.0	23.2	18.8	9.4	22.2	11.7	19.1	31.3	20.0	8.6	10.6	15.3	14.3

Using the 93.2 percentile of ozone maximum daily 8-hour means it is estimated that 11.6% of the population have lived in 2023 in areas where concentrations were above the ozone target value (TV) threshold of 120 µg/m³, which is the fifth lowest value of the nineteen-year period. The overall population-weighted ozone concentration in terms of the 93.2 percentile maximum daily 8-hour means is estimated at 107.9 µg/m³ for the considered European population, which is slightly below a mean value (i.e. 108.6 µg/m³) of the whole nineteen-year period (it should be noted that for 2005-2011 the 26th highest value of the maximum daily eight-hour mean was considered instead).

Examining the time series for 2005-2023, it can be concluded that 2005, 2006, 2007, 2015 and 2018 are years with high ozone concentrations, leading to increased exposure levels compared to the other years. The years 2014, 2016, 2020 and 2021 show the lowest exposure levels in the nineteen years' time series for the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means.

The trend analysis of the population-weighted concentrations for the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means across the period 2005-2023 for the total considered mapping area does not estimate a statistically significant trend. The reason is the ozone variability strongly influenced by meteorology with higher values occurring during warm and dry summers.

A similar tendency is observed for SOMO35. In 2005-2007, a bit more than one-fourth of the population lived in areas where a level of 6 000 µg/m³·d was exceeded, with the highest level in 2006. In the period of 2008-2019, it fluctuated from about 16% to 23% of the population, except 2014 with about 9%, 2016 with about 12%, and 2018 with about one-third of the population. Since 2020, it is below 16%, while 2023 shows the fifth lowest value in nineteen-year period. The population-weighted SOMO35 concentration is estimated at 4212 µg/m³·d for the considered population, which is a medium value of the nineteen-year period. Trend analysis on the population-weighted concentration for the total mapping area shows no trend for the period 2005-2023, for the same reason as discussed above.

Figure 7.3 gives the SOMO35 population exposure for six concentration classes, for 2012-2023.

Figure 7.3 Population exposure, ozone indicator SOMO35, 2012-2023

Exposure indicators describing the agricultural and forest areas exposed to accumulated ozone concentrations above defined thresholds are summarised in Table 7.4 and Figure 7.4. Those thresholds are the target value (TV) threshold of 18 000 µg/m³·h and the long-term objective (LTO) of 6 000 µg/m³·h for the AOT40 for vegetation, and the former reporting value (RV) of 20 000 µg/m³·h and the critical level (CL) of 10 000 µg/m³·h for the AOT40 for forests.

In 2023, 10.6% of all agricultural land (crops) has been exposed to accumulated ozone concentrations (AOT40 for vegetation) above the target value (TV) threshold, which is the third lowest value of the nineteen-year period. About 91% of all agricultural land has been exposed to levels in excess of the long-term objective (LTO), which is the fourth highest value of the nineteen-year period. The agricultural-weighted AOT40 concentration for 2023 is estimated at almost 11 900 µg/m³·h, which is the fifth lowest values of the nineteen-year period.

The trend analysis of the agricultural-weighted concentrations for the AOT40 for vegetation across the period 2005-2023 for the total considered mapping area does not estimate any statistically significant trend. The reason again is the ozone variability correlated with the variability of meteorology.

Table 7.4 Percentages of the considered European agricultural and forest area (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to ozone concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold and the long-term objective (LTO) for AOT40 for vegetation, and above critical level (CL) and reporting value (RV) for AOT40 for forests and agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations for 2005 to 2023

Ozone	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
AOT40 for vegetation																			
Agr. area > TV (18 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	48.5	69.1	35.7	37.8	26.0	21.3	19.2	30.0	22.1	17.8	31.4	14.7	23.8	39.7	29.7	3.0	6.7	25.4	10.6
Agr. area > LTO (6 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	88.8	97.6	77.5	95.5	81.0	85.4	87.9	86.4	81.0	85.5	79.7	74.1	73.4	95.1	84.0	71.0	73.2	83.9	90.6
Agr.-weighted concentr. [µg/m ³ ·h]	17481	22344	14597	15214	13157	13310	13255	14041	12838	12427	14223	10942	11750	16311	13735	8544	10041	13423	11896
AOT40 for forests																			
For. area > RV (20 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	59.1	69.4	48.4	50.2	49.2	49.3	53.0	47.2	44.1	37.7	52.4	41.9	38.9	56.1	51.4	34.4	29.9	46.2	41.9
For. area > CL (10 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	76.4	99.8	62.1	79.6	67.4	63.4	68.6	65.0	67.2	68.2	59.8	60.0	55.4	86.7	84.0	58.0	59.5	60.8	72.2
For.-weighted concentr. [µg/m ³ ·h]	25900	31154	23744	21951	23532	19625	21892	21580	21753	17124	21150	17573	16798	25397	22343	14584	15070	18386	19336

Figure 7.4 Ozone exposure of agricultural (left) and forested (right) areas, 2005-2023

For the ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, the level of 20 000 µg/m³·h (earlier used reporting value, RV) has been exceeded in about 42% of the considered European forest area in 2023, which is the sixth lowest value of the whole time series. The forest area exceeding the CL has been in 2023 about 72%, which is the sixth highest percentage of the nineteen-year period. The temporal pattern of the concentrations above the AOT40 for forests CL shows some similarity with those of the AOT40 for vegetation, despite their different definitions and receptors and their natural difference in area type characteristics and occurrence. Their annual variability is, however, heavily dependent on meteorological variability.

The trend analysis of the forest-weighted concentrations for the AOT40 for forests across the period 2005-2023 for the total considered mapping area shows no trend.

The evolution of the population-weighted and the agricultural-weighted concentrations for ozone indicators SOMO35 and AOT40 for vegetation is shown in Figure 7.5.

Figure 7.5 Population-weighted concentration of ozone indicator SOMO35 (left) and agricultural-weighted concentration of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation (right) in 2005-2023

7.3 Human health NO₂ indicator

Table 7.5 summarises the development in exposure levels of the considered European population for the human health NO₂ indicator (annual average), in terms of population-weighted concentrations and percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the 2008 annual LV (40 µg/m³) and the 2030 annual LV (20 µg/m³), for the years 2005, 2009, 2010 and 2013 to 2023, for which the maps based on the current methodology are available. The population-weighted concentration is presented additionally also for 2007, although based on different mapping methodology than the other years. This 2007 value is probably slightly underestimated; based on Horálek et al. (2017b), one can suppose the true value would be of about 1 percentage point higher (i.e. it would be about 23.5 µg/m³).

Table 7.5 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the 2008 NO₂ limit value (LV) of 40 µg/m³ and the 2030 NO₂ limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) of 20 µg/m³ for the protection of health for 2005 to 2023

NO ₂	####	2006	####	2008	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####	####
Annual average																				
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	23.3	not	23.3	not	22.1	22.1	not	19.4	18.6	18.8	18.6	18.4	17.6	16.8	14.0	14.4	14.4	14.4	12.9	
Pop. exp. > LV (40 µg/m ³) [%]	7.9	mappe		mappe	5.6	4.9	not	3.2	2.8	3.2	2.8	3.0	1.8	1.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	
Pop. exp. > LV ₂₀₃₀ (20 µg/m ³) [%]	57.1	d		d	53.8	55.0	mapped	41.5	39.4	38.1	38.5	37.2	33.1	29.5	16.0	17.5	17.8	13.0		

In 2023 the fractions of the population exposed to NO₂ annual mean concentrations above the 2008 limit value of 40 µg/m³ and above the 2030 limit value of 20 µg/m³ have been 0.1% and 13% of the total population, respectively, which are the lowest values in the whole series. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean NO₂ concentration of 13 µg/m³, again the lowest in the whole series.

Trend analysis on the population-weighted concentration for the total mapping area shows a downward trend of about -0.7 µg/m³ per year, for the period 2005-2023, which is statistically significant (at the strongest level 0.001).

Figure 7.6 presents the NO₂ population exposure for six concentration classes, for 2012-2023.

Figure 7.6 Population exposure, NO₂ annual average, 2012-2023

The evolution of the population-weighted concentrations for NO₂ is shown in Figure 7.7. As the regular NO₂ maps are not available for all years, an alternative mapping results prepared based on a subset of stations for the purpose of trend analysis 2005-2019 (Horálek et al., 2022a) are also presented.

Figure 7.7 Population-weighted concentration of NO₂ annual mean. Results based on both regular maps (red) and maps for trend analysis (blue) are presented, where available

7.4 Human health BaP indicator

Table 7.6 summarises for the human health BaP indicator (annual average) the population-weighted concentration and the percentage of the considered European population exposed to BaP concentrations above the 2030 EU limit value (LV₂₀₃₀) of 1.0 ng/m³, for years 2012-2023.

Table 7.6 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the 2030 BaP limit value of 1.0 ng/m³ for the protection of health in 2012-2023

BaP	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Annual average												
Population-weighted concentration [ng/m ³]	0.84	not mapped					0.62	0.56	0.54	0.62	0.47	0.38
Population exposed > LV ₂₀₃₀ (1.0 ng/m ³) [%]	20.5	not mapped					16.4	15.1	13.9	15.5	11.9	7.5

In 2023 the population exposed to BaP annual mean concentrations above the level of 1.0 ng/m³ has been 7.5% of the total population, which is the lowest value in the whole series.

Trend analysis on the population-weighted concentration for the period 2012-2023 shows a downward trend of cc. -0.04 ng/m³ per year, which is statistically significant (at a level 0.05). However, one should have in mind both short period of the time series and the experimental character of the BaP maps.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
ALV	Annual Limit Value	
AOT40	Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 ppb (i.e. 80 µg/m ³) in a specific period	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
AQ	Air Quality	
BaP	Benzo(a)pyrene	
CL	Critical Level	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
CLC	CORINE Land Cover	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (Air Convention)	https://unece.org/environment-policy/air
CORINE	Co-ORDinated INformation on the Environment	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
CTM	Chemical Transport Model	
Defra	United Kingdom Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs	
DLV	Daily Limit Value	
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	https://www.ecmwf.int/
EBAS	EMEP dataBASE	https://ebas.nilu.no/
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme	https://www.emep.int/
ETC/ACM	European Topic Centre on Air pollution and Climate change Mitigation	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
ETC/ATNI	European Topic Centre on Air pollution, Noise, Transport and Industrial pollution	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
ETC HE	European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
EU	European Union	https://european-union.europa.eu
GMTED	Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data	
GRIP	Global Roads Inventory Dataset	
HLV	Hourly Limit Value	
ICP	International scientific Cooperative Programme	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/
ILV	Indicative Limit Value	
JRC	Joint Research Centre	https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
LV	Limit Value	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
LV ₂₀₃₀	New or revised 2030 EU Limit Value	
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research	https://www.nilu.no/
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide	
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides	
O ₃	Ozone	
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	https://www.ornl.gov/
PLA	Projected Leaf Area	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
PM ₁₀	Particulate matter with a diameter of 10 micrometres or less	
PM _{2.5}	Particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometres or less	
POD ₆	Phytotoxic Ozone Doze above a threshold of 6 nmol/m ² PLA/s	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
POD ₁	Phytotoxic Ozone Doze above a threshold of 1 nmol/m ² PLA/s	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
R ²	Coefficient of determination	
RIMM	Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping	
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error	
SOMO10	Sum of Ozone Maximum daily 8-hour means Over 10 ppb (i.e. 20 µg/m ³)	
SOMO35	Sum of Ozone Maximum daily 8-hour means Over 35 ppb (i.e. 70 µg/m ³)	
TV	Target Value	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
UN	United Nations	https://www.un.org
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe	https://unece.org/
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time	
WHO	World Health Organization	https://www.who.int/

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Annex 1 Methodology

A1.1 Mapping methodology

Previous mapping reports like Horálek et al. (2007, 2010, 2017b, 2018, 2019, 2022b), De Smet et al. (2011), Denby et al. (2011) discuss methodological developments and details on spatial interpolations and their uncertainties of air quality maps. No changes took place in the mapping methodology with respect to the preceding report (Horálek et al., 2024). This annex summarizes the currently applied methodology for all the considered indicators. The mapping method has been evaluated with the FAIRMODE Delta tool in Horálek et al. (2016). The method is called the *Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping* (RIMM).

Pseudo PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP station data estimation

To supplement PM_{2.5} measurement data, in the mapping procedure data from so-called pseudo PM_{2.5} stations are also used. These data are the estimates of PM_{2.5} concentrations at the locations of PM₁₀ stations with no PM_{2.5} measurement. These estimates are based on PM₁₀ measurement data and different supplementary data, using linear regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{PM_{2.5}}(s) = c + b \cdot Z_{PM_{10}}(s) + a_1 X_1(s) + a_2 X_2(s) + \dots + a_n X_n(s) \quad (A1.1)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{PM_{2.5}}(s)$ is the estimated value of PM_{2.5} at the station s ,
 $Z_{PM_{10}}(s)$ is the measurement value of PM₁₀ at the station s ,
 c, b, a_1, \dots, a_n are the parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the points of stations with both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurements,
 $X_1(s), \dots, X_n(s)$ are the values of other supplementary variables at the station s ,
 n is the number of other supplementary variables used in the linear regression.

When applying this estimation method, all background stations (either classified as rural, urban or suburban) are handled together for estimating PM_{2.5} values at background pseudo stations. For details, see Denby et al. (2011). For estimating PM_{2.5} values at urban traffic pseudo stations, Equation A1.1 is applied for the urban traffic stations. For details, see by Horálek et al. (2019).

To supplement NO_x measurement data, NO_x values are estimated at locations of NO₂ stations with no NO_x data. The estimates are calculated similarly as in Horálek et al. (2007), using regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{NO_x}(s) = a_1 Z_{NO_2}(s)^2 + a_2 Z_{NO_2}(s) + c \quad (A1.2)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{NO_x}(s)$ is the estimated value of NO_x at the station s ,
 $Z_{NO_2}(s)$ is the measurement value of NO₂ at the station s ,
 a_1, a_2, c are the parameters of the regression calculated based on the data at the points of measuring stations with both NO_x and NO₂ measurements.

To supplement BaP measurement data, BaP concentrations are estimated at the locations with PM_{2.5} data with no BaP measurements. These estimates are based on PM_{2.5} measurement data and different supplementary data, using exponential regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{BaP}(s) = \exp(c + b \cdot Z_{PM_{2.5}}(s) + a_1 X_1(s) + a_2 X_2(s) + \dots + a_n X_n(s)) \quad (A1.3)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{BaP}(s)$ is the estimated value of BaP at the station s ,
 $Z_{PM_{2.5}}(s)$ is the measurement (or estimated) value of PM_{2.5} at the station s ,

c, b, a_1, \dots, a_n are the parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the locations of stations with both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements,
 $X_1(s), \dots, X_n(s)$ are the values of other supplementary variables at the station s ,
 n is the number of other supplementary variables used in the linear regression.

When applying this estimation, all background stations (either classified as rural, urban or suburban) are handled together for estimating BaP values at background pseudo stations. The reason for introducing the exponential regression is the exponential relation between BaP and PM_{2.5}. In agreement with Horálek et al. (2022b), the pseudo BaP data are only calculated in areas with a lack of BaP data (see Annex 3, Section A3.5). The estimates are calculated primarily for the locations with PM_{2.5} measured data with no BaP measurements. In the limited areas with a lack of both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements, pseudo PM_{2.5} data (see Eq. A1.1) calculated for locations with PM₁₀ measurements are used.

Interpolation

The mapping method used is a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model (residual kriging). Interpolation is therefore carried out according to the relation:

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = c + a_1X_1(s_0) + a_2X_2(s_0) + \dots + a_nX_n(s_0) + \hat{R}(s_i) \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_0)$ is the estimated value of the air pollution indicator at the point s_0 ,
 $X_1(s_0), X_2(s_0), \dots, X_n(s_0)$ are the n individual supplementary variables at the point s_0 ,
 c, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are the $n+1$ parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the measurement points,
 $\hat{R}(s_i)$ is the spatial interpolation of the residuals of the linear regression model at the point s_0 calculated based on the residuals at the measurement points.

For different pollutants and area types (rural, urban background, and in the case of PM and NO₂, also urban traffic), different supplementary data are used, depending on their improvement to the fit of the regression. Ordinary kriging is used to interpolate the residuals:

$$\hat{R}(s_i) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i R(s_i), \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i = 1 \quad (\text{A1.4a})$$

where $R(s_i)$ are the residuals in the points of the measuring stations s_i ,
 $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ are the weights estimated based on the variogram,
 N is the number of the stations used in the interpolation.

The variogram (as a measure of a spatial correlation) is estimated using a spherical function (with parameters nugget, sill, range). For details, see Horálek et al. (2007), Section 2.3.5 and Cressie (1993).

For PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, both measurement data and the estimated data from the pseudo stations are used. For the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators, prior to linear regression and interpolation, a logarithmic transformation is applied to measurement and modelling concentrations. After interpolation, a back-transformation is applied. For details, see De Smet et al. (2011) and Denby et al. (2008).

For the vegetation-related indicators (AOT40 for vegetation and forests, POD, and NO_x) only rural maps are constructed based on rural background stations, based on the assumption that no vegetation is located in urban areas. For the health-related indicators, the rural and urban background map layers (and for PM and NO₂ also urban traffic map layer) are constructed separately and then merged.

Merging of rural and urban background (and urban traffic) map layers

Health related indicator map layers are created for rural and urban background areas on a grid at resolution of 1 km (for PM, NO₂ and BaP) and 10 km (for ozone), and for urban traffic areas at 1 km (for PM and NO₂). The rural background map layer is based on rural background stations, the urban background map layer on urban and suburban background stations and the potential urban traffic map layer is based on urban and suburban traffic stations. The separate treatment of the map layers is based on the assumption that the estimated rural values are lower (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and BaP) or higher (ozone) than the estimated urban background map values. In the limited areas where this criterion does not hold, a joint urban/rural map layer (created using all background stations regardless of their type) is used, as long as its value lies in between the rural and urban background map value. Thus, the adjusted rural and urban background map layers are calculated and further used. For details, see De Smet et al. (2011).

Subsequently, the separate map layers are merged into one combined final map at 1 km resolution, according to

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{Z}_F(s_0) &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_R(s_0) + w_U(s_0) \cdot \left((1 - w_T(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) + w_T(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \right) \\ &\quad \text{for PM}_{10}, \text{PM}_{2.5}, \text{ and NO}_2 \\ &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_R(s_0) + w_U(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ for ozone and BaP} \quad (\text{A1.5})\end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{Z}_F(s_0)$ is the resulting estimated concentration value in a grid cell s_0 for the final map,
 $\hat{Z}_R(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the rural background map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the urban background map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the urban traffic map layer,
 $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of the urban character of a grid cell s_0 ,
 $w_T(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of areas exposed to traffic air quality in a grid cell s_0 .

The weight $w_U(s_0)$ is based on the population density grid, while $w_T(s_0)$ is based on the buffers around the roads. For further details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

In all calculations and map presentations the EEA standard projection ETRS89-LAEA5210 (also known as ETRS89 / LAEA Europe, see www.epsg-registry.org) is used. The interpolation and mapping domain consists of the areas of all EEA member and cooperating countries, and other microstates, as far as they fall within the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018). Due to the interpolation methodology, the interpolation and mapping domain also includes the area of the United Kingdom. However, although they have been calculated, the results for the United Kingdom are not presented in this report, after this country left the EU.

A1.2 Calculation of population and vegetation exposure

Population exposure estimates are based on the interpolated concentration maps and population density data. Vegetation exposure estimates are based on the concentration maps and land cover data.

Population exposure

Population exposure is calculated for individual countries (apart from BaP), for large regions, for EU-27 and for the whole mapping area. For PM and NO₂, the separate map layers are used; for ozone and BaP, it is calculated from the final air quality maps and population density data, both at 1 km resolution. For each concentration class, the total population per country as well as the European-wide total is determined. For PM and NO₂, the population exposure is calculated separately for areas where the air quality is considered to be directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban)

areas. For each concentration class ‘j’, the percentage of population per country as well as the European-wide total is determined according to:

$$P_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{Bij} (1-w_U(i)w_T(i))p_i + \sum_{i=1}^N I_{Tij}w_U(i)w_T(i)p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

where P_j is the percentage of population living in areas of the j -th concentration class in either the country or in Europe as a whole,
 p_i is the population in the i -th grid cell,
 I_{Bij} is the Boolean 0-1 indicator showing whether the background air quality concentration (estimated by the combined rural/urban background map layer) in the i -th grid cell is within the j -th concentration class ($I_{Bij} = 1$), or not ($I_{Bij} = 0$),
 I_{Tij} is the Boolean 0-1 indicator showing whether the traffic air quality concentration in the i -th grid cell is within the j -th concentration class ($I_{Tij} = 1$), or not ($I_{Tij} = 0$),
 $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of the urban character of the a grid cell s_0 ,
 $w_T(s_0)$ is the weight representing ratio of areas exposed to traffic air quality (i.e. areas inside buffers around the roads, see Section A2.3) in a grid cell s_0 .
 N is the number of grid cells in the country, in the region or in the whole mapped area.

In addition, the exposure for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and the whole area is expressed also as the population-weighted concentration, i.e. the average concentration weighted according to the population in a 1 km x 1 km grid cell:

$$\hat{c} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i} \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

where \hat{c} is the population-weighted average concentration in the country, large region, EU-27 or in the whole mapping area,
 p_i is the population in the i^{th} grid cell,
 c_i is the concentration in the i^{th} grid cell (based on the final merged map),
 N is the number of grid cells in the country or in Europe as a whole.

Vegetation exposure

Vegetation exposure for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area is calculated based on the air quality maps and land cover data, both in the 2 km resolution grid. For each concentration class, the total agricultural and forest area per country as well as European-wide is determined.

Next to this, per-country and European-wide exposure are expressed as the agricultural- and forest-weighted concentration, i.e. the average concentration weighted according to the agricultural and forest area in a 2 km x 2 km grid cell, similarly like in Eq. A1.7.

Estimation of trends

For detecting and estimating the trends in time series of annual values of population and vegetation exposure, the non-parametric Mann-Kendall’s test for testing the presence of the monotonic increasing or decreasing trend is used. Next to that, the non-parametric Sen’s method for estimating the slope of a linear trend is executed. For details, see Gilbert (1987). The significance of the Mann-Kendal test is shown by the usual way, i.e. + for 0.1, * for 0.05, ** for 0.01, and *** for 0.001.

Geographical distribution of considered countries to large regions for use in the assessment

The population and vegetation exposure and population-, agricultural- and forest-weighted concentration is presented, apart from the individual countries, the EU-27 and the whole mapped area, also in five large European regions. For this purpose, the countries have been grouped into five large European regions as follows. (See also Map A1.1. Note that the designation of the large regions is intended primarily for the assessments of the mapping reports and does not necessarily follow common geographic or geopolitical terms.)

- 1) Northern Europe (N): Denmark (including Faroes), Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden;
- 2) Western Europe (W): Belgium, France north of 45°, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands;
- 3) Central Europe (C): Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland;
- 4) Southern Europe (S): Andorra, Cyprus, France south of 45°, Greece, Italy, Malta, Monaco, Portugal, San Marino, Spain;
- 5) South-eastern Europe (SE): Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia including Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Türkiye.

Map A1.1 Five large European regions

A1.3 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold flux Y (POD_Y) calculation

The calculation of the phytotoxic ozone dose above a threshold Y (POD_Y) as described below follows the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels of the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution Convention (CLRTAP) in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2024), including some specifications presented in the Scientific background documents of this manual (CLRTAP, 2017, 2020), as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme

on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation). The steps to be taken are presented in Table A1.1.

Table A1.1 Steps to calculate POD_Y of flux-based critical levels

1	Decide on the species and biogeographical region(s) to be included.
2	Obtain the ozone concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period.
3	Calculate the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto}).
4	Model the hourly stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto}).
5	Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto} .

Source: CLRTAP, 2024.

The cumulative stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient ozone concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to ozone. g_{sto} is calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model proposed by Jarvis (1976) and modified by Emberson et al. (2000a) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a single leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD)), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

Hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a threshold Y (expressed in $mmol/m^2$ PLA⁽⁷⁾) are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period during daylight hours, in order to get the phytotoxic ozone dose above the threshold Y (POD_Y).

Crops

For the wheat as for other crop species, the Y value is taken equal to $6 \text{ nmol}/m^2 \text{ PLA}/s$. Although several POD indicators are proposed in CLRTAP (2024), POD_6 is recommended for wheat, as the hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes above a value of 6 are more relevant for that crop. For potato and tomato, POD_6 is also recommended. Two POD_6 versions are available in CLRTAP (2024): POD_6IAM (which is a simplified version recommended for Integrated Assessment Modelling) and POD_6SPEC (which is specific to a given specie). Here, POD_6SPEC was preferred and used, in agreement with Colette et al. (2018).

Obtaining the ozone concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period

The ozone concentration at the top of the canopy ($nmol/m^3$) in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$c(z_1) = c(z_m, O_3) * \left[1 - \frac{R_a(z_{tgt}, z_m, O_3)}{R_a(d+z_0, z_m, O_3) + R_b + R_{surf}} \right] \quad (A1.8)$$

where $c(z_1)$ is ozone concentration at the top of the canopy,
 $c(z_m, O_3)$ is the ozone concentration measured at the height z_m ,
 $R_a(x, y)$ is the aerodynamic resistance between height y and height x ,
 R_b is the resistance to ozone diffusion in the laminar sub-layer,
 R_{surf} is the overall resistance to ozone deposition to the underlying surfaces,

⁽⁷⁾ PLA, or the projected leaf area, is the total area of the sides of the leaves that are projected towards the sun. PLA is different to the total leaf area, which accounts for both sides of the leaves.

while $R_a(z_{tgt}, z_{m,O3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{z_{tgt}-d} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{tgt}-d}{L} \right) \right]$ (A1.8a)

$R_a(d + z_0, z_{m,O3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{z_0} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_0}{L} \right) \right]$ (A1.8b)

$R_b = \frac{2}{k \cdot u^*} \left(\frac{Sc}{Pr} \right)^{2/3}$ (A1.8c)

$R_{surf} = \frac{1}{\frac{LAI}{R_{sto}} + \frac{SAI}{R_{ext}} + \frac{1}{R_{inc} + R_{soil}}}$ (A1.8d)

while $L = - \frac{u^{*3}}{k \cdot g \cdot \frac{H \cdot R}{P \cdot c_p}}$ (A1.8e)

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41),
 z_{tgt} is the top canopy height (the target height),
 $z_{m,O3}$ is the height of the available ozone measurement above the canopy,
 z_0 is the roughness length, usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height,
 L is the Obukhov length,
 H is the sensible heat flux in [Wm²],
 d is the displacement height, usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 u^* is the friction velocity in [m/s],
 Sc is the Schmidt number for ozone (equal to 0.41),
 Pr is the Prandtl number of air (equal to 0.71),
 P is the atmospheric pressure in [Pa],
 g is the gravity acceleration (equal to 9.8 m/s²),
 c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure (equal to 1048 J/kg/K),
 R is the specific gas constant for dry air (equal to 287.05 J/kg/K),
 LAI is the projected leaf area in [m²/m²] ⁽⁸⁾,
 SAI is the surface area of the canopy in [m²/m²],
 $\Psi_H(\dots) = \Psi_H(\zeta)$ is the similarity function for heat with ζ as the argument ⁽⁹⁾,

according to

$\begin{aligned} (\zeta) &= 2 && \text{when } \zeta < 0 \\ &= -5\zeta && \text{when } \zeta \geq 0 \end{aligned}$ (A1.8f)

with $x = (1 - 16 * \zeta)^{1/4}$ (A1.8g)

and R_{ext} is the resistance to cuticular deposition of ozone (equal to 2 500 s/m);

R_{soil} is the soil resistance (equal to 200 s/m¹),

while $R_{sto} = 1/g_{sto}$ (A1.8h)

$R_{inc} = b \cdot SAI \cdot h / u^*$ (A1.8i)

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance,

b is the empirical constant (equal to 14 m⁻¹),

h is the height of the canopy.

The calculations of LAI and SAI are based on Simpson et al. (2012) and Emberson et al. (2000b), as well as the schematics regarding LAI presented therein (see Eq. 2.8i to 2.8n).

⁽⁸⁾ For more details see LMD et al. (2020).

⁽⁹⁾ For more details see CLRTAP (2017).

$$LAI = LAI_{min} + (d - SGS) * (LAI_{max} - LAI_{min}) / SGS_{length}, \quad (A1.8j)$$

$$SAI = 5 * LAI / 3.5 \quad (A1.8k)$$

when $SGS \leq d < SGS + SGS_{length}$

$$LAI = LAI_{max}, \quad (A1.8l)$$

$$SAI = LAI + 1.5, \quad (A1.8m)$$

when $SGS + SGS_{length} \leq d < EGS - EGS_{length}$

$$LAI = LAI_{max} - (d - (EGS - EGS_{length})) * (LAI_{max} - LAI_{min}) / EGS_{length}, \quad (A1.8n)$$

$$SAI = LAI + 1.5, \quad (A1.8o)$$

when $EGS - EGS_{length} \leq d \leq EGS$

where

LAI_{min}	is the minimum (within the growing season) LAI values [m^2/m^2]
LAI_{max}	is the maximum (within the growing season) LAI values [m^2/m^2]
SGS	is the start of the growing season [day of year]
SGS_{length}	is the duration of the start of the growing season [days]
EGS_{length}	is the duration of the end of the growing season [days]
EGS	is the end of the growing season [day of year] [day of year]

Calculation of the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto})

The basis of the approach used for calculating phytotoxic ozone doses is the calculation of an instantaneous stomatal conductance g_{sto} in the given hour H, according to the equation

$$g_{sto} = g_{max} * [min(f_{phen}, f_{O3})] * f_{light} * max[f_{min}, (f_{temp} * f_{VPD} * f_{SW})] \quad (A1.9)$$

where

g_{sto}	is the actual stomatal conductance in [$mmol O_3 / m^2 PLA$ per second],
g_{max}	is the species-specific maximum stomatal conductance in [$mmol O_3 / m^2 PLA$ per second], see Table A1.2,
f_{phen}	is the relative proportion function for the phenology for the different stage of growing,
f_{O3}	is the relative proportion function for the influence of ozone on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence,
f_{min}	is the species-specific relative minimum stomatal conductance that occurs during daylight hours, see Table A1.2,
$f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}, f_{light}$	are relative proportion functions for leaf stomata respond to temperature, air humidity, soil moisture and light.

Parameters $f_{phen}, f_{O3}, f_{light}, f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}$ and f_{min} are expressed as relative proportion functions, taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} . These functions allow taking into account irradiance (f_{light}), temperature (f_{temp}), water vapour deficit at leaves level (f_{vpd}), soil moisture (f_{sw}), phenology for the different stage of growing (f_{phen}) and the influence of ozone on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence (f_{O3}). f_{min} is the minimum relative value of stomatal conductance during the daylight.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated based on the accumulation of thermal time over the growing season of the crop being considered (Colette et al., 2018), according to CLRTAP (2024). For wheat and potato, the accumulation period is defined for each year using the effective temperature sum (ETS) in °C for days in excess of 0 °C, while for tomato for days in excess of 10 °C.

For wheat, the total accumulation period during which wheat is sensitive to ozone exposure is 200 °C days and 300 °C days before mid-anthesis (mid-point in flowering) to 700 °C days to 550 °C days after

mid-anthesis for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and Mediterranean region, respectively. The timing of mid-anthesis is estimated by starting at the first date after 1 January (or just 1 January) when the temperature exceeds 0 °C. The mean daily temperature is then accumulated (temperature sum), and mid-anthesis is estimated to be a temperature sum of 1075 °C days for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and 1250 °C days for Mediterranean region, which in general corresponds to bread wheat.

For potato, the accumulation period stands between 330 °C days before the tuber initiation date and 800 °C days after this date. The tuber initiation date is considered to be homogeneous throughout Europe. The reasons for its simplification are a) heterogeneous climatic conditions in the European countries naturally lead to different time of potato planting (Pedersen et al., 2005) followed by different time of the tuber initiation and b) lack of detailed local data availability for modelling and mapping.

As discussed ⁽¹⁰⁾ with the French national Chamber of agriculture (APCA, <http://chambres-agriculture.fr>), the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplanted in the field, which occurs in May. Therefore, the fixed date for the tuber initiation was set to June 1st.

For tomato, the accumulation period is from 250 °C days to 1500 °C days after transplanted in the field over a base temperature of 10 °C. The timing of the transplanted is set on the date June 1st.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated according to following equations:

in the case of wheat:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 && \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_1_ETS}) \leq ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_4_ETS} - f_{phen_3_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) < ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 &= f_{phen_e} - \left(\frac{f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_5_ETS} - f_{phen_4_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) < ETS \leq f_{phen_5_ETS}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1.9a}$$

in the case of potato (formulated based on CLRTAP, 2017):

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_1_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } f_{phen_1_ETS} \leq ETS < 0 \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_2_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } 0 < ETS \leq f_{phen_2_ETS}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1.9b}$$

in the case of tomato (formulated based on CLRTAP, 2017):

$$f_{phen} = \frac{ETS - f_{phen_2_ETS}}{A_{start_ETS} - f_{phen_2_ETS}} \quad \text{when } A_{start_ETS} \leq ETS < A_{end_ETS} \tag{A1.9c}$$

⁽¹⁰⁾ There is a lack of information on a date of potato tuber initiation in Europe. It should ideally rely on existing models based on agricultural practices, local climatology, ground properties, and location. INERIS, while developing the POD script, relied on contents of discussions with the French National Chamber of Agriculture (consultation with APCA, March 2018; Deumier and Hannon, 2010). Based on the information given that the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplanted in the field, which occurs in May in France, a fixed date of June 1st has been chosen for France and applied also for the rest of Europe. This date should be revised according to the availability of more accurate information on potato plantations in Europe.

where ETS is the effective temperature sum in °C days using a base temperature of 0 °C for wheat and potato and a base temperature of 10 °C for tomato (see Table A1.2); for wheat, ETS is set to 0 °C days at mid-anthesis day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 200 °C days before mid-anthesis, and A_{end_ETS} will be at 700 °C days after mid-anthesis over a base temperature of 0 °C; for potato, ETS is set to 0 °C days at tuber initiation day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 330 °C days before tuber initiation and A_{end_ETS} at 800 °C days after tuber initiation over a base temperature of 0 °C; for tomato, ETS is set to 0 °C days at transplantation day in the field. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 250 °C days after transplantation in the field and A_{end_ETS} at 1500 °C days after transplantation in the field over a base temperature of 10 °C,

f_{phen_a}, f_{phen_e} is the phenology function, which consists of terms describing rate changes of g_{max} expressed as fractions (see Table A1.2),

$f_{phen_1_ETS}, f_{phen_2_ETS}, f_{phen_3_ETS}, f_{phen_4_ETS}, f_{phen_5_ETS}$ are °C days (see Table A1.2; $f_{phen_1_ETS}$ and $f_{phen_5_ETS}$ define period crops to be sensitive to ozone exposure),

A_{start_ETS} and A_{end_ETS} are the effective temperature sums (counted from the day of the mid-anthesis for wheat, from the day of the tuber initiation for potato and from the day of the transplantation in the field for tomato) above a base temperature of 0 °C for wheat and potato and 10 °C for tomato at the start and end of the O_3 accumulation period respectively; see Table A1.2.

The parameter f_{O_3} in the case of wheat is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1+(POD_0/14)^8)]^{-1} \quad (A1.9d)$$

while $POD_0 = \sum_{n=A_{start}}^{H-1} F_{sto}(n) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6}$ (A1.9e)

where POD_0 is the ozone flux already accumulated since the beginning of the vegetation period A_{start} up to the last hour $H-1$,
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly ozone flux in the hour n , calculated in the previous steps based on Equation A1.10, while $F_{sto}(A_{start})$ is equal to 0.

The parameter (ozone function) f_{O_3} in the case of potato is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1+(AOTO/40)^5)]^{-1} \quad (A1.9f)$$

where $AOTO$ is accumulated ozone concentration from the start of the vegetation period A_{start} up to the last hour $H-1$.

The parameter (ozone function) f_{O_3} in the case of tomato is not determined.

The parameter f_{light} is calculated according to

$$f_{light} = 1 - \text{EXP}[(-light_a)*PPFD] \quad (A1.9g)$$

while $PPFD = SSRD * 0.5 * 4.5$ (A1.9h)

where $PPFD$ represents the photosynthetic photon flux density [$\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per second],
 $light_a$ is a light parameter (see Table A1.2),
 $SSRD$ represents the surface net solar radiation in [W/m^2].

The parameter f_{temp} is calculated according to:

$$f_{temp} = \max \left\{ f_{min}, \left[\frac{(T - T_{min})}{(T_{opt} - T_{min})} \right] * \left[\frac{(T_{max} - T)}{(T_{max} - T_{opt})} \right]^{bt} \right\} \text{ when } T_{min} < T < T_{max}$$

$$= f_{min} \text{ when } T_{min} > T > T_{max} \quad (A1.9i)$$

$$\text{while } bt = (T_{max} - T_{opt}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min}) \quad (A1.9j)$$

where T_{min} , T_{max} and T_{opt} are minimum, maximum and optimum temperatures determining leaf stomata opening (see Table A1.2)

Table A1.2 Parametrisation for POD₆SPEC for wheat flag leaves and the upper-canopy sunlit leaves of potato and tomato, for different biogeographical regions

Parameter	Units	(Bread) Wheat		Potato	Tomato
		Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (Pannonia, Steppic)	Mediterranean	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (Mediterranean Pannonia, Steppic)	Mediterranean
g_{max}	mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	500	430	750	330
f_{min}	fraction	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06
light_a	-	0.0105	0.0105	0.005	0.0125
T_{min}	°C	12	12	13	18
T_{opt}	°C	26	28	28	28
T_{max}	°C	40	39	39	37
VPD _{max}	kPa	1.2	3.2	2.1	1
VPD _{min}	kPa	3.2	4.6	3.5	4
ΣVPD_crit	kPa	8	16	10	-
f_{O_3}	POD0 mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	14	-	-	-
f_{O_3}	AOT0, ppmh	-	-	40	-
f_{O_3}	exponent	8	-	5	-
Astart_ETS	°C day	-	-	-	250
Aend_ETS	°C day	-	-	-	1500
SGS	°C day	Astart_ETS	Astart_ETS	Astart_ETS	Astart_ETS
EGS	°C day	Aend_ETS	Aend_ETS	Aend_ETS	Aend_ETS
SGS _{length}	days	70	70	35	70
EGS _{length}	days	22	44	65	44
LAI _{min}	m ² /m ²	0	0	0	0
LAI _{max}	m ² /m ²	5	3.5	6	3.5
Leaf dimension	cm	2	2	4	3
Canopy height	m	1	0.75	1	2
f_{phen_a}	fraction	0.3	0.5	0.4	1
f_{phen_b}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_c}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_d}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_e}	fraction	0.7	0.5	0.2	0.0
$f_{phen_1_ETS}$	°C day	-200	-300	-330	0
$f_{phen_2_ETS}$	°C day	0	0	800	2770
$f_{phen_3_ETS}$	°C day	100	70	-	-
$f_{phen_4_ETS}$	°C day	525	312	-	-
$f_{phen_5_ETS}$	°C day	700	550	-	-
mid-anthesis	°C day	1075	1250	-	-

Source: CLRTAP, 2024; Emberson et al., 2000b; González-Fernández et al., 2013; González-Fernández (personal communication, May 2021).

The parameter f_{VPD} is calculated according to:

$$f_{VPD} = \min\{1, \max\{f_{min}, [(1-f_{min})*(VPD_{min} - VPD) / (VPD_{min} - VPD_{max})] + f_{min}\}\} \quad (A1.9k)$$

while $VPD = e_s(T) * (1 - RH)$ (A1.9l)
 $e_s(T) = 0.61 \exp[17.502T/(240.97+T)]$ (A1.9m)

where VPD_{min} is the minimum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening,
 VPD_{max} is the maximum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening,
 T is the air temperature [°C],
 RH is the relative humidity [%]/100 (i.e. in the range 0-1),
 $e_s(T)$ is the potential (saturation) water vapour pressure,

The ΣVPD (i.e. the function describing stomatal re-opening in the afternoon) is taken into account for maps $POD_{\gamma}SPEC$ for wheat and potato. ΣVPD (kPa) should be calculated for daylight hours until dawn of the next day. If $\Sigma VPD \geq \Sigma VPD_{crit}$, g_{sto} calculated using Equation A1.9 is valid if smaller or equal to g_{sto} of the preceding hour. If g_{sto} is larger than g_{sto} of the preceding hour, given that ΣVPD is larger than or equal to ΣVPD_{crit} , it is replaced by the g_{sto} of the preceding hour.

The parameter f_{SW} is replaced by f_{SMI} (where SMI represents Soil Moisture Index with maximum at field capacity), taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} (with 0 for soil moisture at and below wilting point), following the parameterization given in Simpson et al. (2012), similar to the plant available water (PAW) parameterization f_{PAW} as defined for wheat in CLRTAP (2024). The basic equation used for f_{SW} resp. f_{SMI} is:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{SMI} &= 0 && \text{for } SMI \leq 0 \\ &= \frac{SMI}{PAW_t} && \text{for } 0 < SMI \leq PAW_t \\ &= 1 && \text{for } SMI > PAW_t \end{aligned} \quad (A1.9n)$$

while $SMI = \frac{SWLL - PWP}{FC - PWP}$ (A1.9o)

where PAW_t is the threshold amount of water in the soil available to the plants, above which stomatal conductance is at a maximum, set to 0.5,
 $SWLL$ is the soil moisture in [m^3/m^3],
 PWP is the permanent wilting point in [cm^3/cm^3],
 FC is the field capacity in [cm^3/cm^3].

Parameter f_{SW} represents below-ground soil water, which is extremely difficult to verify due to the limited availability of measured data across Europe. Moreover, the relationship between precipitation, soil water content and soil water pressure is highly non-linear and sensitive to soil characteristics, making reliable estimation problematic. Soils and plant responses are highly heterogeneous, and simple models often fail to reflect this complexity. Therefore, using f_{SMI} provides a more practical and robust alternative for capturing the effects of soil moisture stress in large-scale modelling (CLRTAP, 2020).

The Soil Moisture Index using the EMEP methodology as described in Simpson et al. (2012) and CLRTAP (2020) is used. It is computed using the soil moisture variable available from a meteorological model, which represents the water content in m^3 of water per m^3 of ground [m^3/m^3] in a specific ground level, in dependence on the available dataset. For soil moisture, the ECWMF's ERA5-Land variable Volume of water in soil layer 3 (i.e. 28-100 cm) has been used, see Section 3.3. The level of soil layer was chosen based on recommendation of Haberle and Svoboda (2015). The soil moisture is quite a sensitive parameter in the calculation of the POD. Next to the soil moisture, the soil moisture index also takes into account the permanent wilting point and the field capacity; they are taken from JRC soil database (JRC, 2016), see Annex 2, Section A2.3.

No limitation of stomatal conductance due to soil moisture can be assumed for tomato, since it is an irrigated horticultural crop. Thus, f_{SMI} for this crop could be established to $f_{SMI} = 1$ over the whole range of SMI values to remove limitation due to soil moisture deficit.

Modelling the hourly stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto})

Once the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto}) and all relevant variables are computed, the stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto}) can be calculated, based on the assumption that the concentration of ozone at the top of the canopy represents a reasonable estimate of the concentration at the upper surface of the laminar layer for a sunlit upper canopy leaf. F_{sto} is calculated according to the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation) methodology, thus the fraction of the ozone taken up by the stomata is given using a combination of the stomatal conductance, the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance and the leaf surface resistance. The hourly stomatal flux in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$F_{sto} = c(z_1) * g_{sto} * \frac{r_c}{r_b + r_c} \quad (A1.10)$$

where F_{sto} is the hourly stomatal flux of ozone in [nmol/m² PLA per second]
 $c(z_1)$ is the concentration of ozone at canopy top in [nmol/m³]
 r_b is the quasi-laminar resistance in [s/m]
 r_c is the leaf surface resistance in [s/m]
 g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in [m/s],

while $r_c = 1/(g_{sto} + g_{ext})$ (A1.10a)

$$r_b = 1.3 * 150 * \sqrt{\frac{L}{u(z_1)}} \quad (A1.10b)$$

where g_{ext} is the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance in [m/s], equal to 1/2500 m/s
 $u(z_1)$ is the wind speed at height z_1 (z_1 is the canopy top)
 L is the cross-wind leaf dimension (2 cm, see Table A1.2)

while $u_{(z_1)} = \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1 - d}{z_0}\right)$ for wheat (A1.10c)

$$u_{(z_1)} = \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1}{z_0}\right) \quad \text{for potato and tomato} \quad (A1.10d)$$

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41)
 d is the displacement height usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 z_1 is the top of the canopy
 z_0 is the roughness length usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height
 u^* is the friction velocity.

Box A1.1 shows the conversion of stomatal conductance and ozone concentration to units demanded for POD_γ calculation.

Box A1.1 Conversion of stomatal conductance g_{sto} and ozone concentration to units demanded for POD_Y calculation

Stomatal conductance g_{sto} has to be converted from units $mmol/m^2$ per second to units m/s (since all the resistances are expressed in the unit of s/m). At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5\text{ Pa}$), the conversion is made by dividing the conductance in $mmol/m^2$ per second by 41 000 to give conductance in m/s .

To convert the **ozone concentration (C)** at canopy height from $\mu\text{g}/m^3$ resp. ppb to $nmol/m$, the following equation should be used:

$$C [nmol \cdot m^{-3}] = C [ppb] * P/(R \cdot T) = C [\mu\text{g}/m^3] / 2 * P/(R \cdot T) \quad (\text{A1.11})$$

where P is the atmospheric pressure in Pa,
 R is the universal gas constant of $8.31447\text{ J/mol per Kelvin}$
 T is the air temperature in Kelvin.

At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5\text{ Pa}$), the concentration in ppb should be multiplied by 41.56 to calculate the concentration in $nmol/m^3$.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto}

Hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a Y threshold are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period using the following equation:

$$POD_Y = \sum_n (F_{sto}(n) - Y) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6} \quad (\text{A1.12})$$

while Y (for wheat, potato or tomato) = $6\text{ nmol}/m^2\text{ PLA per second}$

where POD_Y is the phytotoxic ozone dose related to the threshold Y , in $[mmol/m^2\text{ PLA}]$,
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly ozone flux in the hour n of the accumulation period.

The value Y (in $[nmol/m^2\text{ PLA}/s]$) is subtracted from each hourly averaged F_{sto} (in $[nmol/m^2\text{ PLA}/s]$) value and the F_{sto} (after the subtracting of Y) is accumulated only when $F_{sto} > Y$, during daylight hours (when global radiation is more than $50\text{ W}/m^2$). The value is then converted to hourly fluxes by multiplying by 3 600 and to $mmol$ by dividing by 10^6 to get the stomatal ozone flux in $mmol/m^2\text{ PLA}$.

Trees

The POD maps for selected trees, i.e. beech (*F. sylvatica*) and spruce (*P. abies*), are created with calculated hourly POD values which are based on hourly O_3 concentrations, hourly meteorological parameters such as temperature, vapour pressure deficit, solar radiation and soil hydraulic property data. The hourly O_3 concentrations are calculated by combining the monitoring data from rural background stations, chemical transport modelling data and other supplementary data (Horálek et al., 2023).

The calculation of the phytotoxic O_3 dose above a threshold Y (POD_1) as described in Vlasáková et al. (2023) follows precisely the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels of the CLRTAP in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2024), including some specifications presented in the Scientific Background Documents of this manual (CLRTAP, 2017, 2020),

as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation).

A1.4 Methods for uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty estimation of the European map is based on leave-one-out cross-validation. This cross-validation method computes the quality of the spatial interpolation for each point of measurement (i.e. monitoring station) from all available information except from the point in question, i.e. it withholds one data point and then makes a prediction at the spatial location of that point. This procedure is repeated for all measurement points in the available set. The predicted and measurement values at these points are plotted in the form of a scatter plot. With help of statistical indicators (see below), the quality of the predictions is demonstrated objectively. The advantage of the nature of this cross-validation technique is that it enables evaluation of the quality of the predicted values at locations without measurements, as long as they are within the area covered by the measurements.

In addition, a simple comparison is made between the point measurement data and the estimated values of the 1 km x 1 km grid cells (for PM and NO₂) or the 10 km x10 km grid cells (for ozone) for the separate rural and urban background (and urban traffic, where relevant) map layers and the 1 km x 1 km grid cells for the final combined maps, for the health-related indicators, and the 2 x 2 km grid cells in the case of AOT40 and NO_x. Note that the grid cell value is the mean estimated value of this grid cell area. The estimated value within a grid cell will only approximate the predicted value(s) at the station(s) lying within that cell. This additional analysis has not been performed for BaP.

Cross-validation

The results of cross-validation are described by the statistical indicators and scatter plots. The main indicator used is root mean squared error (RMSE) and the additional ones are relative RMSE (RRMSE), which is expressed in relative terms (by relating the RMSE to the mean of the air pollution indicator value for all stations), and bias (mean prediction error, MPE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i))^2} \quad (A1.13)$$

$$RRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{Z}} \cdot 100 \quad (A1.14)$$

$$bias(MPE) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i)) \quad (A1.15)$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_i)$ is the air quality indicator value derived from the measured concentration at the i^{th} point, $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 $Z(s_i)$ is the air quality estimated indicator value at the i^{th} point using other information, without the indicator value derived from the measured concentration at the i^{th} point,
 $RRMSE$ is the relative RMSE, expressed in percent,
 \bar{Z} is the arithmetic average of the indicator values $Z(s_1), \dots, Z(s_N)$, as derived from measurement concentrations at the stations $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 N is the number of the measuring points.

Other indicators are R^2 and the regression equation ($y = a.x + c$) parameters slope (a) and intercept (c), following from the scatter plot between the predicted (using cross-validation) and the observed concentrations. RMSE should be as small as possible, bias (MPE) should be as close to zero as possible, R^2 should be as close to 1 as possible, slope a should be as close to 1 as possible, and intercept c should be as close to zero as possible (in the regression equation $y = a.x + c$).

In the cross-validation of PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, only stations with PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP measurement data, respectively, are used (not the pseudo PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP stations, see Annex 1 Section A1.1).

Comparison of the point measurement and interpolated grid values

The comparison of point measurement and predicted grid values is described by the linear regression equation and its parameters and statistical values. The comparison is executed separately for rural and urban background (and urban traffic, where relevant) map layers and for the final combined map. In the case of PM_{2.5} and NO_x, only the stations with actual PM_{2.5} and NO_x measurement data are used (not the pseudo PM_{2.5} and NO_x stations). This analysis is done for PM, ozone, NO₂ and NO_x, not for BaP.

The point observation – point cross-validation prediction analysis (Annex 3, sections “Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation”) describes interpolation performance at point locations when there is no observation (as it follows the leave-one-out approach). In this case, the smoothing effect of the interpolation is most prevalent.

The point observation – grid prediction approach indicates performance of the value for the grid cell (either in 1 km, 2 km or 10 km resolution) with respect to the observations that are located within that cell. As such, some variability is due to smoothing but it also includes smoothing due to spatial averaging into the grid cells. As such, the point-grid validation approach tells us how well our interpolated and aggregated grid values approximate the measurements at the actual station (point) locations. Whereas the point-point approach tells us how well our interpolated values estimate the indicator at a point where there is no actual measurement at that location, under the constraint that the point lies within the area covered by measurements.

Annex 2

Input data

The types of input data in this paper are similar as in Horálek et al. (2024), apart from the modelling data: instead of the CHIMERE model results, the EMEP model output has been used for BaP mapping, see Section A2.2. The air quality, modelling, satellite and meteorological data as used in Horálek et al. (2024) has been updated for 2023. For readability of this paper, the list of the input data is reproduced here. The key data is the air quality measurements at the monitoring stations extracted from the Air Quality e-Reporting database EEA (2025a), including geographical coordinates (*latitude, longitude*).

The supplementary data cover the whole mapping domain and are converted into the EEA reference projection ETRS89-LAEA5210 on a 1 km grid resolution (for health-related indicators apart from ozone) and a 10 km grid resolution (ozone). The data for the maps of vegetation related indicators (particularly AOT40) were converted – like in the previous reports (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein) – into a 2 km resolution to allow accurate land cover exposure estimates to be prepared for use in the EEA indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2025b).

A2.1 Air quality monitoring data

Air quality station monitoring data for the relevant year as extracted from the official EEA Air Quality e-Reporting database, EEA (2025a) in February 2025 has been used. This data set has been supplemented with British stations from the Defra (2025) database ⁽¹¹⁾ and with several EMEP rural stations from the EBAS (NILU, 2025) database not reported to the Air Quality e-Reporting database. Specifically, 7 additional stations for PM₁₀, 5 for PM_{2.5}, 12 for O₃, 9 for NO₂ and 5 NO_x from the EBAS database and 103 additional British stations for PM₁₀, 92 for PM_{2.5}, 74 for O₃, 137 for NO₂, 12 for NO_x and 28 for BaP from the Defra data archive have been added, for mapping purposes.

The following pollutants and aggregations are considered:

PM ₁₀	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
	– 90.4 percentile of the daily average values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
PM _{2.5}	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
Ozone	– 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour average values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
	– peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
	– SOMO35 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2023
	– SOMO10 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2023
	– AOT40 for vegetation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2023
	– AOT40 for forests [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2023
	– hourly values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], all hours of the year 2023 (for the purpose of POD _y mapping)
NO ₂	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
NO _x	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
NO	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023 (for the purposes of NO _x mapping only)
BaP	– annual average [ng/m^3], year 2023

The exact values of percentiles are actually 90.41 in the case of PM₁₀ daily means and 93.15 in the case of ozone maximum daily 8-hour means.

⁽¹¹⁾ The United Kingdom exited the European Union in January 2020 and does not report air quality data to the AQ e-reporting database. Nevertheless, in order to enable the interpolation across the whole mapping domain, the publicly available British data from the Defra database have also been used in the analysis.

For a considerable number of stations NO_x is measured, but it is not reported as such but separately as NO and NO_2 . For these stations reporting NO and NO_2 separately, the NO_x concentrations were derived according to the equation

$$NO_x = NO_2 + \frac{46}{30} \cdot NO \quad (A2.1)$$

In this equation, all components are expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with a molecular mass for NO of 30 g/mol and for NO_2 of 46 g/mol.

The peak season is calculated for each station as the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O_3 concentration during the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O_3 concentration. This means that for each station, twelve 6-month running averages of the daily 8-hour maximum are calculated. The first 6-month running average starts with calculations from August 1 of the previous year to January 31 of the current year, while the last 6-month running average ends with calculations from July 1 to December 31 of the current year. The maximum of these 12 values is selected as the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means.

SOMO35 is the annual sum of the differences between maximum daily 8-hour concentrations above $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (i.e. 35 ppb) and $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. SOMO10 is the annual sum of the differences between maximum daily 8-hour means above $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (i.e. 10 ppb) and $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. AOT40 is the sum of the differences between hourly concentrations greater than $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (i.e. 40 ppb) and $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, using only observations between 08:00 and 20:00 CET, calculated over the three months from May to July for AOT40 for vegetation and over the six months from April to September for AOT40 for forests.

Only the stations with annual data coverage of at least 75 percent are used. In the case of SOMO35, SOMO10 and AOT40 indicators, a correction for the missing data is applied according to the equation

$$I_{corr} = I \cdot \frac{N_{max}}{N} \quad (A2.2)$$

where I_{corr} is the corrected indicator (SOMO35, SOMO10 or AOT40 for vegetation or for forests),
 I is the value of the given indicator without any correction,
 N is the number of the available daily resp. hourly data in a year for the given station,
 N_{max} is the maximum possible number of the days or hours applicable for the indicator.

For the indicators relevant to human health (i.e. for all PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ indicators, ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means SOMO35 and SOMO10, and NO_2 and BaP annual averages), data from stations classified as *background* (for all the three types of area, *rural*, *urban* and *suburban*) are considered; for PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ and NO_2 , also *urban* and *suburban traffic* stations are considered. (Throughout the paper, the urban and suburban stations are handled together). *Industrial* stations are not considered, as they represent local concentration levels that cannot be easily generalized for the whole map. For the indicators relevant to vegetation damage (i.e. for ozone AOT40 and POD_y parameters and NO_x annual average), only *rural background* stations are considered; the relevant maps are constructed (and applicable) for rural areas only. In the case of existing data (with sufficient annual time coverage) from two or more different measurement devices in the same station location, the average of these data is used.

The stations from French overseas areas (departments), Svalbard, Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands were excluded. These areas outside the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018) were excluded from the interpolation and mapping domain, as the interpolation should be performed across a generally compact territory.

Table A2.1 shows the number of the measurement stations (not pseudo stations) selected for the individual pollutants and their respective indicators.

Table A2.1 Number of stations selected for each pollutant indicator and area type, 2023

Station type	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	Ozone				NO ₂	NO _x	BaP	
			Health rel. (3)	Peak seas.	AOT40 veg.	AOT40 for.				POD _y
Rural background	431	292	576	556	580	578	602	481	414	106
Urban/suburb. backgr.	1706	1107	1302	1226	-	-	-	1493	-	473
Urban/suburb. traffic	845	523	-	-	-	-	-	1260	-	-

For the PM_{2.5} mapping, in addition to the PM_{2.5} stations, 151 rural background, 111 urban/suburban background and 344 urban/suburban traffic PM₁₀ stations (at locations without PM_{2.5} measurement) have been also used for the purpose of calculating the pseudo PM_{2.5} station data.

In the case of NO_x, 345 stations with NO_x reported data have been used, while for 69 stations NO_x values have been calculated from reported NO₂ and NO data using Eq. A2.1. Next to this, for the NO_x mapping 65 additional rural background NO₂ stations (at locations without NO_x measurement) were also used for the purpose of calculating the pseudo NO_x station data.

For the BaP mapping, in addition to the BaP stations, 87 rural and 65 urban background pseudo BaP station data calculated based on the PM_{2.5} measurements have also been used.

A2.2 Chemical transport modelling outputs

Up to the maps for 2019, EMEP MSC-W model was used, specifically its model results for year Y based on meteorology for year Y and emissions for year Y-1. Then, the maps for 2020 and 2021 were prepared using the CAMS Ensemble Forecast (CAMS-ENS FC) model output, as the EMEP model results based on the emissions for year Y-1 were not available in these years (as 2020 was a special year due to the COVID-19 situation). In these years, the CAMS-ENS FC model output was used, in agreement with Horálek et al. (2021), which recommended this modelling product as an alternative to the EMEP model. Since 2022, both modelling products were again available, giving quite similar results in the 2022 mapping. It was decided further to use the CAMS-ENS FC model output, due to the consistency with the interim maps (for which the CAMS-ENS FC model output is used).

The CAMS-ENS FC data as provided by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) at a regional scale over Europe have been used. The European regional production consists of an ensemble of eleven air quality models run operationally. All models use the same CAMS-REG anthropogenic emissions and current meteorology from the operational ECMWF IFS forecast. The models provide (along with other products) a 96-hour forecast made available at 08:00 UTC the day of the forecast. The forecast data product is available on an hourly time resolution and at a spatial resolution of 0.1° x 0.1°, which corresponds roughly to 5-10 km (W–E) x 10 km (S–N). Each model forecast is combined into an ensemble forecast by taking the median of all used models. For further details see ECMWF (2024).

In this report, the CAMS-ENS FC data (forecast for the next 24 hours starting at 0:00 UTC every day) for 2023 have been used (CAMS, 2024). All the models used in the ensemble were run using the CAMS-REG-v5.1 REF2 v2.0.1 emissions (corresponding to year 2018) for most of the year 2023, and since November 2023, CAMS-REG-v6.1 emissions representing year 2022 were used instead (ECMWF, 2024). For more information on emissions, see Kuenen et al., 2024. All modelling data have been aggregated from the hourly means to the same set of parameters as for the air quality observations:

PM ₁₀	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023 – 90.4 percentile of the daily means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
PM _{2.5}	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
Ozone	– 93.2 percentile of the highest maximum daily 8-hour average value [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023 – peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023 – SOMO35 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2023 – SOMO10 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2023 – AOT40 for vegetation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2023 – AOT40 for forests [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2023
NO ₂	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023
NO _x	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2023

Due to the complete temporal data coverage available at the modelled data, the PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means is identical with the 36th highest daily mean and the O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means is identical with the 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean.

The data were re-gridded into the reference EEA 10 km grid (for ozone health related indicators), 1 km grid (for PM and NO₂) and 2 km grid (for vegetation related indicators).

For BaP, the chemical transport model used is GLEMOS (v2.3.0). It is a three-dimensional Eulerian multi-scale multi-compartment chemistry transport model (<https://github.com/glemos-model>). The spatial resolution of the modelling results for this application was 0.1°×0.1°. Meteorological parameters required for the model runs were generated using operational analysis data from the ECMWF (ECMWF, 2025), pre-processed with the WRF weather forecast model (WRF, 2025). The gridded BaP emissions data for 2023 for the EMEP domain were prepared by CEIP (CEIP, 2025) based on countries' official reporting 2025 to the LRTAP Convention. The model's output completely covers the mapping domain (i.e., the area of the EEA member and cooperating countries within the map extent Map_2c, EEA, 2018). The parameter used is

Benzo(a)pyrene – annual average [ng/m^3], year 2023.

A2.3 Other supplementary data

Meteorological parameters

The meteorological data used are the ECWMF data extracted from the CDS (Climate Data Store, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>). Hourly data for 2023 are used. Most of the data come from the reanalysed data set ERA5-Land at 0.1° resolution (of CDS), namely the indicators:

Surface solar radiation [MW/m^2] – variable “Surface solar radiation downwards”

Temperature [K] – variable “2m temperature”

Wind speed [m/s] – calculated based on variables “10m u-component of wind” and “10m v-component of wind” (see below Eq. A2.3)

Relative humidity [%] – calculated based on variables “2m temperature” and “2m dewpoint temperature” (see below Eq. A2.4)

Soil water – variable “Volumetric soil water layer 3”, i.e. layer of 28-100 cm (used for POD only)

Wind speed (WV) is derived from the “10m u-component of wind” (10U) and “10m v-component of wind” (10V) according to relation

$$WV = \sqrt{(10U)^2 + (10V)^2} \quad (\text{A2.3})$$

Relative humidity (RH) is derived as a function of “2m temperature” (T) and “2m dew point temperature” (D) by means of the saturated water vapour pressure (e_D and e_D), according to relation

$$RH = \frac{e_D}{e_T} \cdot 100 = \frac{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)} \cdot 100 = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)} \cdot 100, \quad (\text{A2.4})$$

where D is the dew point temperature at 2 meter height,
 T is the temperature at 2 meter height.

In the coastal areas (where the data from ERA5-Land are not available), the same parameters from the reanalysed data set ERA5 in 0.25° resolution are applied. Next to this, the following data (not available in the ERA5-Land data set) from the ERA5 data set is also used:

Friction velocity [m/s] – variable “Friction velocity”. The friction velocity (also known as the shear-stress velocity) has the dimensions of velocity.

Surface sensible heat flux [W/m^2] – variable “surface_sensible_heat_flux”.

Most of the meteorological parameters are used for POD_y maps only. For other maps than POD_y , annual aggregations based on hourly data are used, namely for the parameters:

Wind speed – annual average [m/s^1], year 2023

Relative humidity – annual average [%], year 2023

Surface solar radiation – annual average of daily sum [MW/m^2], year 2023

All meteorological data were re-gridded and converted into the reference EEA 1 km resolution grid, 10 km resolution grid and 2 km resolution grid, in the ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection.

Altitude

The altitude data field (in meters) of Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) is used, with an original grid resolution of 15 arcseconds (some 463 m at 60N). Source: U.S. Geological Survey Earth Resources Observation and Science, see Danielson and Gesch (2011). The field is converted into the ETRS 1989 LAEA projection. (The resolution after projection was 449.2 m). In the following step, the raster dataset was resampled to 100 m resolution and shifted to the extent of EEA reference grid. Finally, the dataset was spatially aggregated into 1 km, 2 km and 10 km resolutions. Next to this, another aggregation has been executed based on the 1 km grid cells, i.e. the floating average of the circle with a radius of 5 km around all relevant grid cells.

Population density and population totals

Population density (in inhbs/ km^2 , number of residents for the year 2018) is based on JRC-Geostat 2018 grid dataset, Eurostat (2020). The dataset is in 1 km resolution, in the EEA reference grid.

For regions not included in the JRC-Geostat 2018, an alternative source was used. Namely, it was GHS population grid for 2020 in the 1 km resolution as prepared by the JRC (JRC, 2023). As the GHS population data were available for 2020 only, not for 2018 (like JRC-Geostat 2018), they have been scaled to 2018 based on the country bases, based on 2018 and 2020 Eurostat data for countries (Eurostat, 2024). The areas lacking JRC-Geostat 2018 data, and supplemented with the scaled GHS data were: Andorra, Türkiye, Faroe Islands, Jan Mayen, northern Cyprus, Crown dependencies and Gibraltar (note that the data for the last two areas are used for calculation of exposure trend estimates only). As such, the JRC-Geostat 2018 data and these supplements cover the entire mapping area.

To verify the consistency of merging the JRC-Geostat 2018 with the GHS (JRC) data, these two datasets were compared based on the national population totals of the individual countries. Additionally, the national population totals for the JRC-Geostat 2018 gridded data (supplemented by the scaled GHS data) were verified with the Eurostat national population data for 2023 (Eurostat, 2025). Figure A2.1 presents both comparisons. From these verifications, one can conclude a high correlation of the national population totals of each data source. Based on this, in the further calculations on national population totals the actual Eurostat data for 2023 (Eurostat, 2025) were used, as described further.

Figure A2.1 Correlation of national population totals for GHS with JRC-GHS 2018 (left) and Eurostat 2023 with supplemented JRC-Geostat 2018 (right)

Population density data can be used to classify the spatial distribution of each type of area (rural, urban or mixed population density) in Europe. This information is used to select and weight the air quality values, grid cell by grid cell and merge them into a final combined map (Annex 1). Furthermore, it is used to estimate population health exposure and percentages above standards per country, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area, including involved uncertainties. These activities take place on the 1 km resolution grid in accordance with the recommendations of Horálek et al. (2010). The supplemented JRC-Geostat 2018 data (as described above) are used in all the calculations.

National population totals presented in the exposure tables of this paper are based on Eurostat national population data for 2023 (Eurostat, 2025). For France, Portugal and Spain, the population totals of areas outside the mapping area (i.e. French overseas departments Azores, Madeira and Canarias) are subtracted. For Andorra, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Monaco, San Marino and Faroe Islands with no data for 2023 in the Eurostat database, the population totals are based on UN (2025), as well as for Cyprus (as Eurostat does not include the population of the northern part of Cyprus).

Land cover

CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018) – 100 m resolution, Version 2020_20 is used (EU, 2020). For Andorra that is missing in this database, World Land Cover at 30m resolution from MDAUS BaseVue 2013 (MDA, 2015) resampled to 100m resolution is used. For areas that are neither included in the CLC2018 nor in the World Land Cover database (i.e. Jan Mayen and some border areas), ESA Climate Change Initiative Global Land Cover for 2018 (ESA, 2019) is used, resampled to 100m resolution.

In agreement with Horálek et al. (2017b), the 44 CLC classes have been re-grouped into the 8 more general classes. In this paper four of these general classes are used, see Table A2.2.

Table A2.2 General land cover classes, based on CLC2018 classes, used in mapping

Label	General class description	CLC classes grid codes	CLC classes codes	CLC classes description
HDR	High density residential areas	1	111	Continuous urban fabric
LDR	Low density residential areas	2	112	Discontinuous urban fabric
AGR	Agricultural areas	12-22	211-244	Agricultural areas
NAT	Natural areas	23-34	311-335	Forest and semi natural areas

Two aggregations are used, i.e. into 1 km resolution grid and into the circle with radius of 5 km. For each general CLC class, the high land use resolution is spatially aggregated into the 1 km EEA standard grid resolution. The aggregated grid square value represents for each general class the total area of this class as percentage of the total 1 km x 1 km area. For details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

Road type vector data

GRIP (Meijer et al., 2018) vector road type data provided by the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL) are used for the weighting procedure of the urban background and the urban traffic map layers (Annex 1, Section A1.1). The road types are distributed into 5 classes, from highways to local roads and streets. In agreement with Horálek et al. (2017b), road classes No. 1 “Highways”, No. 2 “Primary roads” and No. 3 “Secondary roads” are used.

Percentage of the area influenced by traffic is represented by buffers around the roads: for the individual classes 1-3 and for classes 1-3 together, at all 1 km x 1 km grid cells; a buffer of 75 metres distance at each side from each road vector is taken for the roads of classes 1 and 2, while a buffer of 50 metres is taken for the roads of class 3. For details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

Satellite data

The annual average NO₂ dataset was constructed based on data from the TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) onboard of the Sentinel-5 Precursor satellite (Veefkind et al., 2012). All available swath-based Level-2 data with an irregular pixel geometry was acquired for the year 2023. The spatial resolution of the product is cc. 5.5 km by 3.5 km. The product used is the S5P_OFFL_L2__NO2 product (van Geffen et al., 2019, 2020) and it provides the tropospheric vertical column density of NO₂, i.e. a vertically integrated value over the entire troposphere. All overpasses for a specific day were then mosaicked using HARP (<https://stcorp.github.io/harp/doc/html/index.html>) and retrievals with a quality assurance values greater than 0.75 (indicating high quality and cloud-free conditions) were gridded to a regular projected grid for all area with a 1 km spatial resolution in a ETRS89 / ETRS-LAEA (EPSG 3035) projection. The daily gridded files were subsequently averaged to an annual mean. I.e. the parameter used is

NO₂ – annual average tropospheric vertical column density (VCD) [number of NO₂ molecules per cm² of earth surface], year 2023 (aggregated from cloud-free high-quality daily data).

Soil hydraulic properties data

JRC data called "Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe" in 1 km resolution are used for POD calculations, JRC (2016). Namely the following indicators are used:

Wilting Point – water content at wilting point [cm³/cm³],
Field Capacity – water content at field capacity [cm³/cm³].

Annex 3

Technical details and mapping uncertainties

This annex contains technical details on the linear regression models and the residual kriging as used in the mapping. Furthermore, uncertainty estimates for the maps of the indicators are given.

A3.1 PM₁₀

Technical details on the mapping and uncertainty estimates for both PM₁₀ indicators maps annual average (Map 2.1) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (Map 2.3) are presented in this section.

Technical details on the mapping

Table A3.1 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c , a_1 , a_2 , ...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging, for both PM₁₀ indicators. The linear regression and ordinary kriging of its residuals are applied on the logarithmically transformed data of both measurement and modelled PM₁₀ values. In Table A3.1 the standard error and variogram parameters (nugget, sill and range) refer to these transformed data, whereas RMSE and bias refer to the interpolation after a back-transformation. Since 2017 maps, an updated methodology as developed and tested under Horálek et al. (2019) has been used, i.e. including land cover among the supplementary data and using the traffic urban map layer.

The adjusted R^2 and standard error are indicators for the fit of the regression relationship, where the adjusted R^2 should be as close to 1 as possible and the standard error should be as small as possible. The adjusted R^2 for the rural areas was 0.67 at the annual average and 0.66 at the 90.4 percentile of daily means (P90.4); for the urban background areas 0.38 at the annual average and 0.37 at the P90.4; for the urban traffic areas 0.38 at the annual average and 0.28 at the P90.4.

Table A3.1 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of PM₁₀ indicators annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means for 2023 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map

		Annual average			90.4 percentile of daily means		
		Rural areas	Urb. b. ar.	Urb. tr. ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb. b. ar.	Urb. tr. ar.
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	1.40	0.74	1.68	1.44	1.06	2.44
	a1 (log. CAMS model)	0.862	0.842	0.56	0.788	0.764	0.41
	a2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00015			<i>non signif.</i>		
	a3 (wind speed)	-0.03171		-0.053	<i>non signif.</i>		-0.075
	a4 (relative humidity)	-0.012			-0.010		
	a5 (land cover NAT)	-0.0009			-0.0011		
	Adjusted R²	0.67	0.38	0.38	0.66	0.37	0.28
Stand. Error [µg/m³]	0.23	0.32	0.29	0.22	0.33	0.33	
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	Nugget	0.020	0.024	0.026	0.020	0.023	0.031
	Sill	0.054	0.051	0.048	0.039	0.058	0.060
	Range [km]	1000	210	330	990	220	250
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [µg/m³]	3.4	6.4	4.8	6.1	11.4	9.4
	Relative RMSE [%]	24.7	31.1	23.5	25.9	32.7	26.9
	Bias (MPE) [µg/m³]	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1

RMSE (the smaller the better) and bias (the closer to zero the better), highlighted by orange, are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map. The bias indicates to what extent the predictions are under- or overestimated on average. Further in this section, more detailed uncertainty analysis is presented.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Using RMSE as the most common indicator, the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map at areas 'in between' the station measurements (i.e. at locations without measurements, as long as they are within the area covered by the measurements) can be expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Table A3.1 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of PM₁₀ annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means expressed by RMSE is 3.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 6.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the rural areas, 6.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 11.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the urban background areas, and 4.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 9.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the urban traffic areas, respectively. Alternatively, one can express this uncertainty in relative terms by relating the absolute RMSE uncertainty to the mean air pollution indicator value for all stations. This relative mean uncertainty (Relative RMSE) of the final combined map of PM₁₀ annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means is 24.7% and 25.9% for rural areas, 31.1% and 32.7% for urban background areas, and 23.5% and 26.9% for urban traffic areas, respectively. These quite high numbers in urban background areas compared to previous years up to 2015 are caused by inclusion of Türkiye since 2016 mapping. For the mapping results without Türkiye, the relative mean uncertainty is 19.8% and 19.6% for rural areas, 19.5% and 22.1% for urban background areas and 18.0% and 20.4% for urban traffic areas, respectively. Nevertheless, the relative uncertainty values including Türkiye fulfil the data quality objectives for models as set in Annex I of the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Figure A3.1 shows the cross-validation scatter plots, obtained according to Annex 1, Section A1.4 for rural, urban background and urban traffic areas, for both PM₁₀ indicators. The R² indicates that the variability is attributable to the interpolation for about 70% and 67% at the rural areas, for 66% and 65% at the urban background areas, and for about 72% and 68% at the urban traffic areas, for the annual average and the 90.4 percentile of daily means, respectively.

Figure A3.1 Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for PM₁₀ indicators annual average (top) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (bottom) for 2023 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

The trend line in the scatter-plots deviates at the lowest values somewhat above, and at higher values below the symmetry axis, indicating that the interpolation methods tend to underestimate the high concentrations and overestimate the low concentrations. For example, in urban background areas for annual average an observed value of 40 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 36 µg/m³, about 10% lower. This underestimation at high values is common to all spatial interpolation methods. It could be reduced by either using a higher number of stations with an improved spatial distribution, or by introducing an improved regression that uses either other supplementary data or more advanced chemical transport model (or a model in finer resolution).

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

In addition to the above point observation – point prediction cross-validation, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated prediction values spatially averaged at grid cells. This point observation – grid averaged prediction comparison indicates to what extent the predicted value of a grid cell represents the corresponding measurement values at stations located in that cell. The comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers at 1 km resolution. (One can directly relate this comparison result to the cross-validation results of Figure A3.1). Apart from this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at the same 1 km resolution. Figure A3.2 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons, for PM₁₀ annual average only as an illustration. The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.1 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers, and for the final combined maps are summarised in Table A3.2 for both PM₁₀ indicators.

Figure A3.2 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left), urban background (upper middle) and urban traffic (upper right) map layer and final combined map (all bottom) (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) for PM₁₀ annual average 2023

Table A3.2 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for PM₁₀ indicators annual average (top) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (bottom) for 2023

PM ₁₀	Rural background stations				Urban/suburban background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Annual average								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	3.4	0.0	0.699	y = 0.720x + 3.8	6.4	0.1	0.657	y = 0.782x + 4.6
grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	2.3	-0.2	0.861	y = 0.796x + 2.6	4.3	0.0	0.838	y = 0.834x + 3.3
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	2.6	0.2	0.823	y = 0.846x + 2.3	7.4	-0.3	0.831	y = 0.835x + 3.4
90.4 percentile of daily means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	6.1	-0.1	0.668	y = 0.669x + 7.7	11.4	0.0	0.654	y = 0.724x + 9.6
grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	4.7	-0.4	0.814	y = 0.739x + 5.7	7.5	-0.5	0.855	y = 0.805x + 6.5
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	5.0	0.2	0.780	y = 0.804x + 4.8	7.5	-0.2	0.847	y = 0.807x + 6.6

PM ₁₀	Urban/suburban traffic stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Annual average				
cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	4.8	0.0	0.716	y = 0.748x + 5.2
grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	3.8	-0.1	0.830	y = 0.806x + 3.9
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	5.2	-2.4	0.745	y = 0.752x + 2.7
90.4 percentile of daily means				
cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	9.4	-0.1	0.675	y = 0.691x + 10.7
grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	7.0	-0.2	0.822	y = 0.774x + 7.7
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	10.1	-4.2	0.688	y = 0.682x + 6.9

By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers with the final combined map, one can evaluate the level of representation of the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas in the final combined map. Both the rural and the urban air quality are fairly well represented in the 1 km final combined map, while the traffic air quality is underestimated in this spatial resolution. One can conclude that the final combined map in 1 km resolution is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas.

The Table A3.2 shows a better relation (i.e. lower RMSE, higher R², smaller intercept and slope closer to 1) between station measurements and the interpolated values of the corresponding grid cells at either rural, urban background or urban traffic areas than it does at the point cross-validation predictions. That is because the simple comparison between point measurements and the gridded interpolated values shows the uncertainty at the actual station locations (points), while the point cross-validation prediction simulates the behaviour of the interpolation at point positions assuming no actual measurement would exist at that point. The uncertainty at measurement locations is introduced partly by the smoothing effect of the interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 1 km grid cells. The level of the smoothing effect leading to underestimation at areas with high values is there smaller than in situations where no measurement is represented in such areas. For example, in urban background areas the predicted interpolation gridded annual average value in the separate urban background map will be about 37 µg/m³ at the corresponding station with the measurement value of 40 µg/m³. This means an underestimation of about 8%. It is a slightly less than the prediction underestimation of 10% at the same point location, when leaving out this one actual measurement point and the interpolation is done without this station (see the previous subsection).

A3.2 PM_{2.5}

Technical details and uncertainty estimates for Map 2.5 with the PM_{2.5} annual average are presented in this section.

Technical details on the mapping

Like for PM₁₀, an updated methodology as developed and tested under Horálek et al. (2019) has been used, i.e. including the land cover among supplementary data and using the traffic urban map layer.

Table A3.3 presents the regression coefficients determined for pseudo PM_{2.5} stations data estimation, based on the 1205 rural and urban/suburban background and 458 urban/suburban traffic stations that have both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurements available (see Section 2.1.1).

Table A3.3 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model for generating pseudo PM_{2.5} annual average data for 2023 in rural and urban background (left) and urban traffic (right) areas

PM _{2.5} , Annual average		Rural and urban background areas	Urban traffic areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.1)	c (constant)	22.0	42.3
	b (PM ₁₀ measurement data)	0.625	0.444
	a1 (surface solar radiation)	-0.003	-0.004
	a2 (latitude)	-0.261	-0.552
	a3 (longitude)	0.078	0.106
	Adjusted R²	0.82	0.74
Standard Error [µg.m⁻³]		1.7	2.0

Due to sufficient data coverage of PM_{2.5} measurements in urban background areas in some countries, the pseudo PM_{2.5} stations have not been used in urban background areas of these countries. This refers to Austria, Benelux, Czechia, Croatia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Slovakia and Spain. Table A3.4 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c, a₁, a₂,...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging of its residuals.

Table A3.4 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of PM_{2.5} annual average 2023 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for final combined map

PM _{2.5}		Annual average		
		Rural areas	Urban b. areas	Urban tr.. areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	0.55	0.56	0.73
	a1 (log. CAMS model)	0.820	0.780	0.706
	a2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00030		
	a3 (wind speed)	-0.055		
	a4 (land cover NAT1)	<i>non signif.</i>		
	Adjusted R²	0.65	0.46	0.59
Standard Error [µg.m⁻³]		0.26	0.29	0.25
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	0.028	0.023	0.016
	sill	0.076	0.052	0.035
	range [km]	1000	220	180
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [µg.m⁻³]	2.2	2.9	2.4
	Relative RMSE [%]	27.0	25.7	21.9
	Bias (MPE) [µg.m⁻³]	-0.1	0.0	-0.1

The same supplementary data as in Horálek et al. (2019) has been used. Like in the case of PM₁₀, the linear regression is applied on the logarithmically transformed data of both measurement and modelled PM_{2.5} values. Thus, the standard error and variogram parameters refer to these transformed data, whereas RMSE and bias refer to the interpolation after the back-transformation.

The adjusted R² and standard error are indicators for the quality of the fit of the regression relation. The adjusted R² is 0.65 for the rural areas, 0.46 for urban background areas and 0.59 for urban traffic areas. Quite weaker regression relation in the urban background areas causes a higher impact of the interpolation part of the interpolation-regression-merging mapping methodology in these areas.

RMSE and bias – highlighted in orange – are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map; the bias indicates to what extent the predictions are under- or overestimated on average. Only stations with PM_{2.5} measurement data are used for calculating the RMSE and the bias (i.e. the pseudo PM_{2.5} stations are not used). These statistical indicators are calculated excluding the pseudo stations because they are estimated values only, not actual measurement values. According to Denby et al (2011), the pseudo PM_{2.5} data does not satisfy the quality objectives for fixed monitoring alone. The pseudo stations are used as they improve the mapping estimate, whereas the actual measurements can be used for evaluating the quality of the map. For the future, it will be considered to quit the application of the PM_{2.5} pseudo stations as the current number of the actual PM_{2.5} measurement stations has increased over time such that the use of pseudo PM_{2.5} stations may not contribute enough any longer to improve the mapping estimates.

Due to the lack of rural stations in Türkiye for PM_{2.5}, no proper interpolation results could be presented for this country in a rural map, so the estimated PM_{2.5} values for Türkiye are not presented in the final map. Thus, the stations located in Türkiye have not been used in the uncertainty estimates (although used in the mapping process), as they lie outside the mapping area.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.4 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of PM_{2.5} annual average expressed as RMSE is 2.62 µg/m³ for the rural areas, 2.9 µg/m³ for the urban background areas and 2.4 µg/m³ for the urban traffic areas. On the other hand, the relative mean uncertainty (Relative RMSE) of the final combined map of PM_{2.5} annual average is 27% for rural areas, 26% for urban background areas and 22% for urban traffic areas. These relative uncertainty values fulfil the data quality objectives for models as set in Annex I of the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Figure A3.3 shows the cross-validation scatter plots, obtained according to Section A1.3, for different area types. The R² indicates that about 75% of the variability is attributable to the interpolation for the rural areas, 78% for the urban background areas and 74% for the urban traffic areas.

The scatter plots indicate that in areas with high concentrations the interpolation methods tend to underestimate the levels. E.g., in urban background areas an observed value of 25 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 22 µg/m³, which is an underestimated prediction of about 11%.

Figure A3.3 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for PM_{2.5} annual average 2023 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

Like for PM₁₀, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated prediction values spatially averaged in grid cells, in addition to the cross-validation. The comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers at 1 km resolution. Next to this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at the same 1 km resolution. Figure A3.4 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure A3.4 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left), urban background (upper middle) and urban traffic (upper right) map layer and final combined map (all bottom) (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) for PM_{2.5} annual average 2023

The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.3 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation Figure A3.4 for separate map layers and for the final combined map are summarised in Table A3.5.

By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers with the final combined maps, one can evaluate the level of representation of the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas in the final combined map. Similar results as for PM₁₀ can be observed: the final combined map in 1 km resolution is fairly well representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas. Like in the case of PM₁₀ and for the same reason, Table A3.5 shows a better correlated relation with the station measurements for the simply interpolated gridded values than for the point cross-validation predictions, at all area types.

The uncertainty at measurement locations is introduced partly by the smoothing effect of the interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 1 km grid cells. For example, in urban background areas the predicted interpolation gridded value in the final map will be about 23 µg/m³ at the corresponding station with the measurement value of 25 µg/m³ (calculated based on the linear regression equation), which coincides with an underestimation of about 8%.

Table A3.5 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for PM_{2.5} annual average 2023

PM _{2.5} , Annual average	Rural background stations				Urban/suburban background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	2.2	-0.1	0.749	y = 0.709x + 2.3	2.9	0.0	0.780	y = 0.794x + 2.3
Grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	1.6	-0.2	0.861	y = 0.765x + 1.7	2.0	0.0	0.845	y = 0.852x + 1.7
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final merged map	1.6	0.0	0.849	y = 0.787x + 1.7	2.0	0.0	0.831	y = 0.842x + 1.8

PM _{2.5} , Annual average	Urban/suburban traffic stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, urban traffic map layer	2.4	-0.1	0.738	y = 0.725x + 2.8
Grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	1.7	0.2	0.853	y = 0.873x + 1.5
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final merged map	2.3	-0.6	0.787	y = 0.861x + 1.0

A3.3 Ozone

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates are presented for the maps of ozone health-related indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 (Maps 3.1, 3.3-3.5), as well as for the maps of ozone vegetation-related indicators AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests (Maps 3.7 and 3.8). Next to this, the details of POD_v (i.e. POD₆ and POD₁) maps are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

Table A3.6 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models and of the residual kriging, including the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging.

The adjusted R² and standard error show the quality of the fit of the regression relation. For the rural areas, all indicators show the value of the adjusted R² between 0.37 and 0.53. For the urban areas, the adjusted R² is in between 0.26 and 0.28 for all indicators apart from SOMO10, for which it is 0.12.

For the vegetation-related indicators the urban maps are not constructed. RMSE and bias – highlighted by orange – are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map.

Table A3.6 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hourly means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hourly means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 in rural and urban areas and for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation and for forests in rural areas for 2023

		93.2 perc.		Peak seas. avg		SOMO35		SOMO10		AOT40v	AOT40f
		Rur. ar.	Urb. ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Rur. ar.
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	-6.5	38.8	6.0	33.9	332	2007	4268	6571	3422	3802
	a1 (CAMS model)	1.11	0.76	0.93	0.68	0.90	0.58	0.76	0.62	0.91	0.90
	a2 (altit. GMTED)	0.0149		0.0119		3.17		3.79		7.81	14.31
	a3 (wind speed)		-2.98		-2.05		-335.6		<i>n. sign.</i>		
	a4 (s. solar rad.)	<i>n.sign.</i>	<i>n.sign.</i>	<i>n.sign.</i>	<i>n.sign.</i>	<i>n.sign.</i>	0.22	<i>n.sign.</i>	<i>n. sign.</i>	<i>n. sign.</i>	<i>n. sign.</i>
	Adjusted R²	0.48	0.28	0.47	0.26	0.47	0.27	0.37	0.12	0.46	0.53
	St. Err. [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{x}$]*	9.4	13.7	7.4	11.0	1779	2011	2732	3572	5513	9031
Ord. krig. (OK) of LRM	Nugget	51	69	33	35	2.2E+06	1.3E+06	4.9E+06	3.8E+06	1.4E+07	4.1E+07
	Sill	59	109	38	61	2.6E+06	4.0E+06	5.3E+06	6.2E+06	2.5E+07	7.0E+07
	Range [km]	700	120	390	80	690	1000	700	380	1000	1000
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{x}$]*	9.1	11.6	7.2	8.9	1764	1759	2648	2799	5125	8747
	Rel. RMSE [%]	8.2	10.6	7.8	9.9	33.0	39.0	12.2	14.3	35.5	35.8
	Bias [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{x}$]*	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	3	101	14	-19	-13	-22

* Units: 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums and peak season average of daily 8-h maximums: [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], SOMO35 and SOMO10: [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d}$], AOT40v and AOT40f: [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{h}$].

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

The basic uncertainty analysis is provided by cross-validation. Table A3.6 shows both absolute and relative mean uncertainty, expressed by RMSE and Relative RMSE. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2023 ozone map is around 7-11% for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h means and the peak season average of maximum daily 8-h means, around 33-39% for SOMO35, around 12-15% for SOMO10 and around 35-36% at AOT40 indicators. The small levels of the relative uncertainty for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h means, the peak season indicator and SOMO10 are highly influenced by the low ratio between the relevant standard error and mean calculated based on all annual station concentration data: for these three indicators the ratio is at the level of about 0.11-0.19, while for SOMO35 and for both AOT40 indicators it is at the level of about 0.46-0.54.

Figure A3.5 shows the cross-validation scatter plots for both the rural and urban areas of the 2023 map for the health-related ozone indicators. Based on the R², one can see that for the health-related ozone indicators, about 41-52% of the variability is attributable to the interpolation. The scatter plots indicate that the higher values are underestimated and the lower values somewhat overestimated by the interpolation method; a typical smoothing effect inherent to the interpolation method with the linear regression and its residuals kriging. For example, in the case of the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums, in urban areas (Figure A3.5, upper right panel) an observed value of 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is estimated in the interpolation as 130 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is 13% lower. Or, in the case of SOMO35, in rural areas (Figure A3.5, lower middle left panel) an observed value of 8 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d}$ is estimated in the interpolation as about 6 900 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d}$, which is 19% lower. In addition, an overestimation at the lower end of predicted values occurred.

Figure A3.5 Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hourly means (top), peak season average of maximum daily 8-hourly means (higher middle), SOMO35 (lower middle) and SOMO10 (bottom) for 2023 for rural (left) and urban (right) areas

Figure A3.6 shows the cross-validation scatter plots of the AOT40 for both vegetation and forests. R^2 indicates that about 53% of the variability is attributable to the interpolation in the case of AOT40 for vegetation, while for AOT40 for forests it is about 56%. The cross-validation scatter plots show again that in areas with higher accumulated ozone concentrations the interpolation methods tend to deliver underestimated predicted values. For example, in agricultural areas (Figure A3.6, left panel) an observed value of 25 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ is estimated in the interpolation as about 20 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. an underestimation of about 19%.

Figure A3.6 Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation (left) and AOT40 for forests (right) for 2023 for rural areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

In addition to the above point observation – point prediction cross-validation, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated predicted grid values.

For health-related indicators, the comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural and separate urban background maps at 10 km resolution. (One can directly relate this comparison result to the cross-validation of the previous section.) Next to this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at 1 km resolution.

Figure A3.7 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons, for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means only, as an illustration. The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.5 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for the separate rural and the separate urban background map, and for the final combined maps are summarised in Table A3.7. By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for the separate rural and separate urban background map with the final combined maps, one can again evaluate the level of representation of the rural resp. urban background areas in the final combined maps. Both the rural and the urban air quality are fairly well represented in the 1 km x1 km final combined map.

The uncertainty of the map layers at measurement locations is caused partly by the smoothing effect of interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 10 km x 10 km grid cells. The level of smoothing, which leads to underestimation in areas with high values, is weaker in areas where measurements exist than in areas where a measurement point is not available. For example, in the case of the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums, in urban areas an observed value of 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is estimated in the interpolation as about 133 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is about 11% lower. It is less than the cross-validation underestimation of 13% at the same point location, when leaving out this one actual measurement point and the interpolation without this station is done (see the previous subsection).

Figure A3.7 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left) and urban (bottom left) 10 km resolution and final combined 1 km resolution (both right) map (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (top) or urban/suburban (bottom) background stations (x-axis) for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of daily maximum 8-hourly means for 2023

Table A3.7 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted point values based on cross-validation and the predicted grid values from separate (rural resp. urban) 10 km resolution and final merged 1 km resolution map versus the measurement point values for rural (left) and urban (right) background stations for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of daily max 8h means (top), peak season average of daily max 8h means (higher middle), SOMO35 (lower middle) and SOMO10 (bottom) for 2023

Ozone	Rural background stations				Urban/suburban background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
93.2 percentile of daily max. 8-hour means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	9.1	0.1	0.511	y = 0.523x + 53.42	11.6	-0.1	0.483	y = 0.511x + 53.49
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	8.2	0.6	0.606	y = 0.579x + 47.71	8.8	-0.3	0.711	y = 0.626x + 40.71
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	8.4	-0.1	0.586	y = 0.566x + 48.49	9.0	0.0	0.696	y = 0.619x + 41.81
Peak season average of daily max. 8-hour means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	7.2	0.1	0.495	y = 0.498x + 46.87	8.9	-0.2	0.518	y = 0.540x + 40.99
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	6.4	0.3	0.598	y = 0.557x + 41.44	6.3	-0.4	0.768	y = 0.669x + 29.22
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	6.5	-0.3	0.580	y = 0.550x + 41.48	6.5	-0.1	0.749	y = 0.659x + 30.36
SOMO35								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	1764	3	0.476	y = 0.484x + 2758	1759	101	0.443	y = 0.433x + 2659
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	1614	46	0.562	y = 0.539x + 2508	1393	-48	0.660	y = 0.578x + 1853
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	1608	-94	0.569	y = 0.531x + 2410	1420	11	0.642	y = 0.576x + 1927
SOMO10								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	2648	14	0.410	y = 0.402x + 12980	2799	-19	0.457	y = 0.468x + 10356
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	2461	40	0.494	y = 0.449x + 11995	2302	-45	0.645	y = 0.556x + 8627
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	2474	-234	0.493	y = 0.451x + 11668	2349	68	0.626	y = 0.553x + 8798

Table A3.8 presents the results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.6 and those of the point-grid validation for the rural map, for vegetation related indicators AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests. Again, one can see for both indicators a better correlation between the station measurements and the averaged interpolated predicted values of the corresponding grid cells, than at the point cross-validation predictions, of Figure A3.6.

Table A3.8 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for predicted point values based on cross-validation and predicted grid values from rural 2 km resolution map versus measurement point values for rural background stations for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation (top) and forests (bottom) for 2023

Ozone	Rural background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Linear regression equation
AOT40 for vegetation				
cross-valid. prediction, rural map	5125	-13	0.532	y = 0.558x + 6355
grid prediction, 2 km resolution rural map	4227	-1	0.684	y = 0.638x + 5220
AOT40 for forests				
cross-valid. prediction, rural map	8747	-22	0.556	y = 0.574x + 10389
grid prediction, 2 km resolution rural map	7315	0	0.692	y = 0.647x + 8626

Details of POD_Y maps

POD_Y (i.e. POD₆ and POD₁) maps have been calculated using the ozone based on the hourly ozone rural maps, hourly meteorological data and soil hydraulic properties data, according to the methodology described in Annex 1, Section A1.3.

The hourly ozone maps needed for POD_Y calculation have been calculated at the 2 km resolution, based on rural background measurements. The maps for each hour of the year 2023 have been constructed using the same methodology as for the annual maps, i.e. the multiple linear regression followed by the kriging of its residuals (see Annex 1, Section A1.1) based on the measurement data, CAMS-ENS Forecast model output, altitude and the surface solar radiation. Table A3.9 presents the summary results of the RMSE, RRMSE and bias for the whole year, based on the annual average and percentiles of these three statistics. For bias, annual sum is also shown in addition.

Table A3.9 Annual statistics average, 2nd percentile, 25th percentile, 50th percentile (median), 75th percentile, 98th percentile and sum (where relevant) for average ozone concentration, number of stations considered, and cross-validation parameters RMSE, RRMSE and Bias of hourly ozone maps, 1.1.2023-31.12.2023. Units: µg/m³ apart from N and RRMSE

	Rural background areas						Sum
	avg	p2	p25	p50	p75	p98	
N	539	509	534	540	545	553	
avg	63.5	41.0	52.0	61.0	73.3	98.6	
RMSE	16.1	10.5	13.7	15.5	18.0	24.7	
RRMSE	26.6%	14.2%	19.7%	26.1%	32.4%	44.0%	
Bias	0.00	-0.33	-0.09	-0.02	0.08	0.43	11.8

Figure A3.8 presents the averages of the cross-validation indicators Bias and RMSE in the individual hours of the year 2023.

Figure A3.8 Cross-validation statistical indicator Bias (above) and RMSE (below) of hourly ozone maps, average at rural background stations, 1.1.2023-31.12.2023

In the POD_Y calculations, the module to estimate phytotoxic ozone doses from a given atmospheric ozone exposure developed by INERIS and adapted by CHMI has been used.

During the POD_Y maps calculation, different biogeographical regions were considered. Plant stomatal functioning varies per plant species and can vary by biogeographical region, reflecting different adaptations of plants to climate and soil water in these regions. Parametrization for POD_6 (i.e. for wheat, potato and tomato) is currently available for all different biogeographic regions of Europe apart from Alpine region, i.e. for Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic, and Mediterranean regions (CLRTAP, 2024). In the case of wheat, the parametrization is the same for most of these regions (namely Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, and Steppic), while for Mediterranean regions is different. For Alpine region, the parametrization of the Continental and several other regions are used. For potato and tomato, only one parametrization exists – in the case of potato, the parametrization is set for all regions apart from the Alpine one, while for tomato for the Mediterranean region only (see Table 1.2). In the calculations, the existing parametrization has been applied for the entire mapping

area. Parametrization for POD_1 for spruce is available for all biogeographical regions apart from the Mediterranean, Anatolian and Black Sea ones.

The values calculated in 0.1° resolution were converted into the standard ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection and transferred into the EEA 2 km resolution grid.

A3.4 NO₂ and NO_x

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates for the maps of NO₂ annual average and NO_x annual average, for Maps 4.1 and 4.3, are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

In agreement with Horálek et al. (2007) and Annex 1, the NO_x measurements are supplemented by the so-called pseudo NO_x stations. The pseudo NO_x data are calculated based on the NO₂ data, using quadratic regression Eq. A1.2a. The regression coefficients were estimated based on 375 rural background stations with both NO_x and NO₂ measurements (see Annex 1, Section A1.1). The estimated coefficients of Eq. A1.2 are: $a = 0.0230$, $b = 1.017$, $c = 0.97$. Adjusted R^2 is 0.94, the standard error is $1.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Table A3.10 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models and of the residual kriging and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging. Only stations with actual measurement data of the relevant pollutant (i.e. not the pseudo stations) have been used for calculating the cross-validation parameters RMSE and bias.

Table A3.10 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of NO₂ annual average for 2023 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map (left) and NO_x annual average for 2023 in rural areas (right)

		NO ₂ Annual average			NO _x Annual average
		Rural areas	Urb. b. areas	Urb. tr. areas	Rural areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	4.3	12.8	21.05	2.2
	a1 (CAMS model)	0.239	<i>non signif.</i>	<i>non signif.</i>	0.655
	a2 (altitude)	-0.0057		<i>non signif.</i>	-0.0041
	a3 (altitude_5km_radius)	0.0056		<i>non signif.</i>	
	a4 (wind speed)	-0.66	-2.19	-2.94	-1.42
	a5 (solar radiation)				0.002
	a6 (satellite TROPOMI)	1.43	2.27	2.26	
	a7 (population*1000)	0.00114	0.00032		
	a8 (NAT_1km)		-0.0349		
	a9 (AGR_1km)		-0.0220		
	a10 (TRAF_1km)		0.0719		
	a11 (LDR_5km_radius)	<i>non signif.</i>	<i>non signif.</i>	0.0010	
	a12 (HDR_5km_radius)		0.0008	0.0035	
	a13 (NAT_5km_radius)	-0.00040			
	Adjusted R²	0.69	0.45	0.36	0.46
	Standard Error [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	2.1	5.8	8.2	4.1
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	2	9	15	7
	sill	4	16	34	16
	range [km]	80	21	15	1000
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1.9	4.4	6.2	3.3
	Relative RMSE [%]	33.7	28.8	26.1	43.4
	Bias (MPE) [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.10 shows both absolute and relative mean uncertainty, expressed by RMSE and Relative RMSE. The absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of NO₂ annual average expressed as RMSE is 1.9 µg/m³ for the rural areas, 4.4 µg/m³ for the urban background areas and 6.2 µg/m³ for the urban traffic areas. For the NO_x rural map it is 3.3 µg/m³. The relative mean uncertainty of the NO₂ annual average map is 34% for rural areas, 29% for urban background areas and 26% for urban traffic areas. The NO_x annual average rural map has a relative mean uncertainty of 43%.

Figure A3.9 shows the point observation – point prediction cross-validation scatter plots for NO₂ annual average. The R² indicates that about 75% of the variability is attributable to the interpolation for the rural areas, while for the urban background areas it is 69% and for the urban traffic 64%.

Figure A3.9 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for NO₂ annual average 2023 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

Like in the case of other pollutants, the cross-validation scatter plots show the underestimation of predictions at high concentrations at locations with no measurements. For example, in urban background areas an observed value of 40 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 34 µg/m³, which is an underestimated prediction of about 16%.

Figure A3.10 shows the cross-validation scatter plot for NO_x annual average rural map. The R² indicates that about 65% of the variability is attributable to the interpolation.

Figure A3.10 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for NO_x annual average 2023 for rural areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

Next to the above presented cross-validation, a simple comparison was made between the point observation values and interpolated predicted 1 km and 2 km grid values, respectively.

For NO₂ annual average, the comparison has been made primarily for the separate map layers at 1 km resolution. Besides, the comparison has been done also for the final combined map. Table A3.11 presents the results of this comparison, together with the results of cross-validation prediction of Figure A3.10. One can conclude that the final combined map in 1 km resolution is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas.

Table A3.11 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for NO₂ annual average 2023

NO ₂ , Annual average	Rural backgr. stations				Urban/suburban background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	1.9	0.0	0.745	y = 0.756x + 1.4	4.4	0.0	0.686	y = 0.738x + 4.0
Grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	1.3	-0.1	0.877	y = 0.835x + 0.8	2.7	0.2	0.880	y = 0.846x + 2.6
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	2.2	0.4	0.736	y = 0.930x + 0.8	3.2	0.8	0.846	y = 0.884x + 2.5

NO ₂ , Annual average	Urban/suburban traffic stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	6.2	-0.1	0.639	y = 0.669x + 7.7
Grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	3.5	0.0	0.889	y = 0.816x + 4.4
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	9.6	-7.0	0.612	y = 0.504x + 4.8

Table A3.12 presents the cross-validation results of Figure A3.11 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for the rural map of NO_x annual average.

Table A3.12 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for predicted point values based on cross-validation and predicted grid values from rural 2 km resolution map versus measurement point values for rural background stations for NO_x annual average 2023

NO _x	Rural background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Linear regression equation
Cross-valid. prediction, rural map	3.3	0.1	0.647	y = 0.660x + 2.63
Grid prediction, 2 km resolution, rural map	2.7	0.1	0.765	y = 0.720x + 2.16

A3.5 BaP

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates for Map 5.1 of BaP annual average are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

The methodology as developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2022b) has been used. Table A3.13 presents the regression coefficients determined for pseudo BaP stations data estimates, based on the 341 rural and urban/suburban background that have both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements available (see Annex 1 Section A1.1). Looking at the parameters of the regression, one can note that the adjusted R² of 0.62 is a quite poor correlation. Based on this and in agreement with Horálek et al. (2022b), the pseudo stations have only been used in areas with a significant lack of the BaP measurements. The pseudo stations have been applied for countries and areas, as follows. For the rural areas: All the mapping area, apart from Austria, Benelux, Czechia, Germany, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, and Italy north

of 44 degrees latitude. For the urban background areas: Finland, Greece, Iceland, Norway, Portugal, Sweden and west Balkan countries (namely, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Northern Macedonia, and Serbia including Kosovo).

Table A3.13 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model for generating pseudo BaP annual average data for 2023 in rural and urban background areas

		Rural and urban background areas
Nonlinear regression model (NLRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	-6.31
	a1 (PM _{2.5} annual average)	0.148
	a2 (latitude)	0.061
	a3 (longitude)	0.045
	a4 (land cover NAT_1km)	-0.0071
	a5 (land cover NAT_5km_r)	0.0110
Adjusted R²		0.62

Table A3.14 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c, a₁, a₂,...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging of its residuals. The same supplementary data as in Horálek et al. (2022b) has been used.

Table A3.14 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of BaP annual average 2023 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map

BaP		Annual average	
		Rural areas	Urban b. areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	0.74	1.43
	a1 (log. EMEP model)	0.370	0.442
	a2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00120	
	a3 (wind speed)	-0.354	
	a4 (temperature)	<i>n. sign.</i>	-0.12
	a5 (land cover NAT_1km)	-0.0059	
Adjusted R²		0.37	0.42
Standard Error [ng/m³]		1.01	0.89
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	0.333	0.187
	sill	0.794	0.678
	range [km]	300	530
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [ng/m³]	0.37	0.55
	Relative RMSE [%]	136.5	67.3
	Bias (MPE) [ng/m³]	0.06	0.01

The adjusted R² is 0.37 for the rural areas and 0.42 for urban background areas.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.14 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of BaP annual average expressed as RMSE is 0.37 ng/m³ for the rural areas and 0.55 ng/m³ for the urban background areas. The RRMSE of this map is 136.5% for rural areas and 67.3% for urban background areas. The cross-validation relative uncertainty RRMSE is still at the considerably higher level (especially in the rural areas) compared to the 60%, being the data quality objective for the modelling uncertainty in the European directive (EC, 2004).

Annex 4

Concentration maps including stations

Throughout the report, the concentration maps presented do not include the concentration values measured at the stations. The reason is to better visualise the health-related indicators with their distinct concentration levels at the more fragmented and smaller urban areas.

As presented in Annex 3, the kriging interpolation methodology somewhat smooths the concentration field. Therefore, it is valuable to present in this Annex 4 the indicator maps including the concentration values resulting from the measurement data at the stations. These points provide important additional visual information on the smoothing effect caused by the interpolation. For instance, maps A4.1 and A4.2 present PM₁₀ indicators annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means and include the stations points used in the interpolation. They correspond to Maps 2.1 and 2.3 of the main report, which do not have stations. Table A4.1 provides an overview of the maps in the main report and the corresponding maps including stations point values as presented in this annex.

Both the rural and the urban/suburban background stations and also urban/ traffic stations for PM and NO₂ are included in the maps of the health-related indicators, while the rural stations only are shown in the maps of vegetation related indicators. For PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, only the stations with relevant measured data (i.e. not the pseudo stations) are presented.

Table A4.1 Overview of maps presented in this Annex 4 and their relationship with the maps presented in the main report

Air pollutant	Indicator	Map including stations	Map without stations
PM ₁₀	Annual average	A4.1	2.1
	90.4 percentile of daily means	A4.2	2.3
PM _{2.5}	Annual average	A4.3	2.5
Ozone	93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means	A4.4	3.1 left
	Peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means	A4.5	3.3
	SOMO35	A4.6	3.4
	SOMO10	A4.7	3.5
	AOT40 for vegetation ^(a)	A4.8	3.7 left
	AOT40 for forests ^(a)	A4.9	3.8
NO ₂	Annual average	A4.10	4.1
NO _x	Annual average ^(a)	A4.11	4.3
BaP	Annual average	A4.12	5.1

^(a) Rural map, applicable for rural areas only.

Map A4.1 Concentration map of PM₁₀ annual average including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.2 Concentration map of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.3 Concentration map of PM_{2.5} annual average including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.4 Concentration map of ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.5 Concentration map of ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2023

Map A4.6 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO35 including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.7 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO10 including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.8 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2023

Map A4.9 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for forests including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2023

Map A4.10 Concentration map of NO₂ annual average including station measurement values, 2023

Map A4.11 Concentration map of NO_x annual average including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2023

Map A4.12 Concentration map of benzo(a)pyrene annual average including station measurement values, 2023, experimental map

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